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Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GVs) for selected phthalates

Deliverable Report

D5.6

WP5 - Translation of results into policy

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Entity	Name of person responsible	Short name institution	Date [Received]
Coordinator	Marike Kolossa-Gehring	UBA	03/08/2020
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Entity	Name of person responsible	Short name institution	Date [Approved]
Pillar Leader	Greet Schoeters	VITO	25/10/2019
Work Package Leader	Greet Schoeters	VITO	25/10/2029
Task leader	Petra Apel	UBA	26/09/2019

Responsible author	Petra Apel
Short name of institution	UBA
Co-authors	Eva Ougier, Fatoumata Sissoko, Christophe Rouselle, Rosa Lange

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 2

Table of contents – overview

Part I	3
Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GVs) for DPHP (Di-2-propylheptyl phthalate, CAS no. 53306-54-0) referring to the general population and workers	3
Part II	53
Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GVs) for DnBP (Di-n-Butylphthalate, CAS no. 84-74-2) referring to the general population and workers	53
Part III	97
Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GVs) for DiBP (Diisobutyl phthalate, CAS no. 84-69-5) referring to the general population and to workers	97
Part IV	145
Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GVs) for Butyl benzyl phthalate (BBzP, CAS-No.: 85-68-7) referring to the general population and to workers	145

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 3

Part I

Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GVs) for DPHP (Di-2-propylheptyl phthalate, CAS no. 53306-54-0) referring to the general population and to workers

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 4

Table of contents

1	Authors and acknowledgements	6
2	Glossary.....	7
3	Introduction	9
4	General information and properties of DPHP	10
4.1	Identification of the substance	10
4.2	Physico-chemical properties	10
4.3	Uses	11
4.4	EU legislation and regulation, classification	11
4.5	Human exposure	11
4.5.1	General population	11
4.5.2	Workers	12
5	General toxicological profile	13
5.1	Toxicokinetics and metabolism	13
5.1.1	Animal studies	13
5.1.2	Studies with human volunteers	13
5.2	Toxicity	17
5.2.1	Human health effects	17
5.2.2	Animal studies and in vitro tests.....	17
5.2.2.1	Acute toxicity.....	17
5.2.2.2	Skin and eye irritation	18
5.2.2.3	Sensitisation.....	18
5.2.2.4	Repeated-dose toxicity	18
5.2.2.5	Genotoxicity and mutagenicity.....	22
5.2.2.6	Carcinogenicity	22
5.2.2.7	Effects on reproduction and development	23
5.2.3	Assessment by different bodies and conclusion.....	26
6	Selected biomarker(s) for the HBM-GV proposal and analytical method	30
6.1	Choice of biomarkers.....	30
6.1.1	For HBM measurements in the general population	30
6.1.2	For HBM measurements in the occupational field	30
6.2	Analytical methods	30
7	Choice of the HBM-GVs derivation method.....	31
7.1	Derivation of HBM-GVs for the general population based on a reference dose	31
7.1.1	RfD - Underlying POD and assessment factors	31

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 5

7.1.2	Calculation of HBM-GVs for the general population	32
7.2	Derivation of HBM-GVs for the occupational field based on an animal POD.....	33
7.2.1	Choice of a POD from a key study	33
7.2.2	Calculation of HBM-GVs for workers.....	33
8	Level of confidence attributed to the derived HBM-GVs	35
9	Discussion	36
10	Factsheets	38
10.1	Factsheet on the HBM-GV for the general population.....	38
10.2	Factsheet on the HBM-GV for workers	42
11	References	46

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 6

1 Authors and acknowledgements

Authors

Petra Apel, UBA, Germany

Eva Ougier, ANSES, France

Fatoumata Sissoko, ANSES, France

Christophe Rouselle, ANSES, France

Rosa Lange, UBA, Germany

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Entity	Contributing expert
NH Austria	Maria Uhl (EAA)
NH Belgium	Jos Bessems (VITO)
NH Belgium	Greet Schoeters (VITO)
NH Finland	Hanna Tolonen (FIOH)
NH Germany	Holger M. Koch (IPA)
NH Netherlands	Marcel Mengelers (RIVM)
NH Netherlands	Wieneke, Bil (RIVM)
NH Spain	Maribel Casas (ISGLOBAL)
NH Switzerland	Rex Filtzgerald (SCAHT)
NH Switzerland	Nancy Hopf (IST)
NH UK	Fiona Fordyce (BGS)

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 7

2 Glossary

ADI	Acceptable Daily Intake
ADME	Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism, and Excretion
AF	Assessment Factor
AF _A	Assessment factor for interspecies differences
AF _H	Assessment factor accounting for intraspecies differences
ANSES	French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety
BE	Biomonitoring Equivalent
BfR	German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment
BGV	Biological Guidance Value
BLV	Biological Limit Value
BMD	Benchmark Dose
BMDL	Benchmark Dose Lower Confidence Limit
BW	Body weight
CLP	Classification, Labelling and Packaging
CoRap	Community Rolling Action Plan
cx-MPHP	Mono(2-propyl-6-carboxyhexyl)phthalate
DEHP	Di(2-ethylhexyl)phthalate
DFG	German Research Foundation
DiDP	Di-isodecyl phthalate
DiNP	Di-isononyl phthalate
DNEL	Derived No-Effect Level
DPHP	Di(2-propylheptyl)phthalate
ECHA	European Chemicals Agency
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
EU	European Union
F _{ue}	Urinary excretion factor (factor for metabolic conversion)
HBM-GV	HBM-Guidance Value (developed under the project HBM4EU)
HBM	Human Biomonitoring
HBM4EU	European Biomonitoring Initiative
HED	Human Equivalent Dose
HPLC-MS/MS	High performance liquid chromatography –tandem mass spectrometry
HPT axis	Hypothalamic-Pituitary-Thyroid axis

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 8

MAK Commission	German Permanent Senate Commission for the Investigation of Health Hazards of Chemical Compounds in the Work Area
MEHP	Mono(2-ethylhexyl)phthalate
MOE	Margin of Exposure
MPHP	Mono(2-propylheptyl)phthalate
NICNAS	National Industrial Chemical Notification and Assessment Scheme
NO(A)EL	No Observed (Adverse) Effect Level
NO(A)EC	No Observed (Adverse) Effect Concentration
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OEL	Occupational Exposure Limit
OH-MPHP	Mono(2-propyl-6-hydroxyheptyl)phthalate
oxo-MPHP	Mono(2-propyl-6-oxoheptyl)phthalate
PBPK/PBTK	Physiologically Based Pharmacokinetic/Toxicokinetic
POD	Point of departure
PP	Peroxisome Proliferator
PPAR	Peroxisome Proliferator-activated Receptor
REACH	Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals
RfD	Reference dose
TDI	Tolerable Daily Intake
TRV	Toxicity reference value

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 9

3 Introduction

Within the framework of task 5.2 of HBM4EU, Human Biomonitoring guidance values (HBM-GVs) are derived for HBM4EU priority substances. The methodology applied to derive these values is described in the concept paper previously released in the HBM4EU task 5.2 workframe (Apel et al., 2020). For the time being, HBM-GVs to be derived shall be agreed on at HBM4EU project level, further adoption of derived HBM-GVs at EU level has to be discussed among partners and the EU Commission.

In the current report, general population HBM-GVs ($\text{HBM-GV}_{\text{GenPop}}$) and an occupational HBM-GV ($\text{HBM-GV}_{\text{Worker}}$) are derived and discussed for di(2-propylheptyl)phthalate (DPHP).

The state of epidemiological knowledge based on human exposure to DPHP on whether and how it might cause human health effects is not sufficient to derive HBM-GVs directly based on human data, be it for the general population or for workers. Thus, the derivation of HBM-GVs for the general population and for workers relies on an animal point of departure (POD) value identified from a key toxicity study, as described in the HBM4EU concept document.

Effects of DPHP on the thyroid observed in sub-chronic and two-generation studies on rats are selected as critical effects.

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 10

4 General information and properties of DPHP

4.1 Identification of the substance

Name	di(2-propylheptyl)phthalate (DPHP)
Synonyms	bis-(2-propylheptyl) phthalate; phthalic acid, bis(2-propylheptyl)ester; 1,2-benzenedicarboxylic acid, bis(2-propylheptyl)ester
Trade names	Palatinol® 10-P; Palatinol® DPHP
CAS Number	53306-54-0
EC Number	258-469-4
IUPAC Name	1,2-bis(2-propylheptyl)phthalate
Molecular weight	446.67 g/mol
Molecular formula	C ₂₈ H ₄₆ O ₄
Structural formula	<p>Figure 1: Structural formula of DPHP (Source: CAS DataBase – ChemicalBook)</p>

4.2 Physico-chemical properties

At room temperature, DPHP is a clear, colourless and viscous liquid. The vapour pressure is estimated to be $3.7 \cdot 10^{-8}$ hPa at 20°C. 1 ml/m^3 (ppm) = 18.53 mg/m^3 ; $1 \text{ mg/m}^3 \triangleq 0.054 \text{ ml/m}^3$ (ppm) (MAK Value Documentation, 2017). Table 1 lists the key physico-chemical properties of DPHP.

Table 1: Physico-chemical data on technical DPHP (BASF, 1995a, 1999 and RIVM, 2006)

State at room temperature	Clear, colourless, viscous liquid
Melting point	-48 °C
Boiling point	252.5 - 253.4 °C at 7 hPa
Relative density	0.9624 g/cm ³ at 20 °C
Vapour pressure	3.7×10^{-8} hPa at 20°C
Partition coefficient log Kow	>> 6.0 at 25 °C
Water solubility	< 0.1 µg/L at 25 °C

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 11

4.3 Uses

Di(2-propylheptyl) phthalate (DPHP, also known as bis(2-propylheptyl) phthalate) was developed as an alternative plasticizer to replace other high molecular weight phthalates such as di(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (DEHP), di-isononyl phthalate (DiNP) and di-isodecyl phthalate (DiDP) which were subjected to authorisation under REACH in 2015. DPHP is a specific isomer of DiDP (NICNAS, 2003). The two phthalates differ in terms of the structure of their side-chains. According to the German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR, 2011), technical grade DPHP contains about 81 % di(2-propylheptyl)phthalate, about 18 % 2-propylheptyl-/2-propyl-4-methylhexyl phthalate and 1 % di(2-propyl-4-methylhexyl)phthalate.

DPHP is used as a plasticizer for PVC and vinyl chloride copolymers. Because of its low volatility it is used in materials and articles made of soft PVC, such as roofing, tarpaulin coverings, cable and wire coatings, and vehicle interior accessories (BfR, 2011; Schmidtkunz et al., 2019). It is also used in flooring, furniture, toys, construction materials, curtains, footwear, leather products as well as an ingredient in paints and adhesives (NICNAS, 2003).

According to the ECHA justification document for the selection of DPHP as a CoRAP substance (2014), DPHP is manufactured and/or imported in the European Economic Area in a high (aggregated) tonnage of 100 000 - 1 000 000 tonnes per year.

4.4 EU legislation and regulation, classification

There is no harmonised classification for DPHP according to Annex VI of Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 (Classification, Labelling and Packaging (CLP)).

DPHP is not listed in Annex XVII, item 51 or 52, to Regulation EU No. 1907/2006 (REACH), implying it is not restricted in plasticised material in toys and childcare articles in general and also not specifically in toys and childcare articles which can be placed in the mouth by children.

On the other hand, DPHP is not allowed as food contact material because it is not on the Union List of substances that are permitted for use in the manufacture of plastic food contact materials (Annex I of EU Regulation (EU) No 10/2011 of 14 January 2011 on plastic materials and articles intended to come into contact with food).

4.5 Human exposure

The ECHA justification document for the selection of DPHP as a CoRAP (Community Rolling Action Plan) substance (2014) attributes to DPHP a wide and dispersive use with consumer and worker exposure.

4.5.1 General population

Because plasticizers are not chemically bound in PVC products and thus can migrate out of these products, exposure of humans and the environment is possible (Leng et al. 2014). The typical DPHP concentration in end-use products is as high as 30–60% (NICNAS, 2003). Hence, exposure of the general population to DPHP may be expected, for instance via plasticizer vapours released into car interiors, via dust [abrasion](#) from flexible [PVC](#) articles, or via skin contact with such products (Schmidtkunz et al. 2019).

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 12

4.5.2 Workers

Occupational exposure to DPHP may occur through dermal contact or inhalation during production, packaging or cleaning of equipment (NICNAS 2003 cited by Klein et al., 2016). These scenarios are mainly associated with skin exposures. Inhalation exposures are usually associated with dust or heated processes.

Exposures during manufacturing are present although lower compared to workers' exposures during production of goods where the material contains the phthalate. Hines et al. (2008) show that workers operating machines where heat is applied were exposed to aerosols when opening the heated vessel such as during extrusion or compounding.

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 13

5 General toxicological profile

5.1 Toxicokinetics and metabolism

5.1.1 Animal studies

Klein et al. (2016) investigated the blood concentration-time profile of DPHP and its metabolites in rats after oral administration of single doses of DPHP of 0.7 and 100 mg/kg bw by gavage. The maximum concentration in blood of DPHP was reached about 1.5 h after the administration of 100 mg/kg bw. Regardless of the dose, the maximum concentrations of the metabolites mono(2-propylheptyl)phthalate (MPHP), hydroxy-mono(2-propylheptyl) phthalate (OH-MPHP) and oxo-mono(2-propylheptyl) phthalate (oxo-MPHP) were reached after about 1 h. The peak of mono(2-propyl-6-carboxyhexyl)phthalate (cx-MPHP) occurred about 2 h later than those of the other metabolites. Among all compounds, MPHP showed the highest maximal levels in blood. The elimination half-lives in blood ranged from about 2.4 h for DPHP, 2.5 h for MPHP and 8.2 h for cx-MPHP. Glucuronidation of the monoesters formed from DPHP (MPHP, OH-, oxo-, cx-MPHP) accounted for less than 5% of the total compound; therefore, they are apparently scarcely glucuronidated in rat blood (Klein et al., 2016).

5.1.2 Studies with human volunteers

Three studies on human volunteers investigated renal excretion and metabolic conversion of DPHP by measuring three oxidised metabolites in the urine following oral exposure: Wittassek and Angerer (2008), Leng et al. (2014) and Klein et al. (2018). The most recent study (Klein et al., 2018) also provides data on the concentrations of DPHP and its metabolites in the volunteer's blood.

Initially, indicative investigations of the DPHP metabolism and of the urinary excretion of its metabolites were described by Wittassek and Angerer (2008). They showed that DPHP is metabolised similarly to the DEHP, i.e., the monoester is formed by ester cleavage in a first step and is then further metabolised to the hydroxyl (OH-MPHP), oxo (oxo-MPHP) and carboxy monoester (cx-MPHP) through ω - and ω -1 oxidation.

Figure 2: Metabolic pathway of DPHP (Klein et al. 2018, according to Gries et al., 2012)

In the human volunteer study by Wittassek and Angerer (2008), 61 hours after oral administration of an unspecified dose of DPHP to a healthy male volunteer, the subject excreted approximately 34% of the dose in the urine, mainly as hydroxy (OH-MPHP; ~ 17%) and oxo metabolites (oxo-MPHP; ~

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 14

16%), with a lesser amount as carboxy metabolites (cx-MPHP; < 5%). Only traces (<1 %) of the non-oxidised monoester were detected.

Leng et al. (2014) also investigated the urinary metabolite's excretion after oral intake of DPHP. The three metabolites oxo-MPHP, OH-MPHP and cx-MPHP were monitored in the urine following oral uptake by five volunteers. Five male volunteers aged between 27 and 49 years of age received a single dose of about 50 mg of DPHP with their breakfast. Stable-isotope labeled DPHP-d4 was used to exclude possible background exposures. Urine samples were collected before administration of the DPHP and over a 48h period thereafter. The urine was treated with glucuronidase to hydrolyse any metabolite glucuronides, followed by determination of metabolite concentrations in the urine using HPLC-MS/MS. On average (\pm SD), 22.9 ± 7.3 % of the deuterium-labelled oral dose was found in urine within the first 24 h, with oxo-MPHP representing the main metabolite (12.6 ± 3.9 %), followed by OH-MPHP (9.9 ± 3.5 %), and cx-MPHP occurring only in trace amounts (0.42 ± 0.1 %) (Table 2 and 3). The total fraction excreted in urine reached 24.7% of the oral dose after 48 h, with virtually no change in the relative contribution of the three metabolites.

In 2018, Klein et al. published a study involving 6 healthy male volunteers aged between 30 and 64 years, who ingested a single ring-deuterated DPHP(-d4) dose (0.7 mg/kg bw) after breakfast. DPHP and selected metabolites were monitored in blood and urine. Blood samples were collected at intervals up to 24 h and urine samples at intervals up to 46 h. LC-MS/MS was used for the analysis of samples. The metabolites (MPHP, oxo-MPHP and OH-MPHP) always appeared in the blood earlier than the parent diester DPHP that displayed a lag phase of about 2 h. Half-lives of the elimination from the blood were similar among the compounds (between 4.1 and 4.6 h). A large interindividual difference in the areas under the concentration-time curves (AUCs) in blood was observed. In urine, half-lives of the elimination phase were almost identical for MPHP, OH-MPHP and oxo-MPHP (around 5 h). Cx-MPHP was eliminated slower (half-live in urine: 8.7 h). At 22 h, the cumulative urinary excretion of the 4 measured metabolites was 5.48% (dose on molar basis), i.e. 90 ± 6 % of that after 46 h. Oxo-MPHP and OH-MPHP were the most abundant metabolites representing respectively 60 % and 37 % (mean values) of the total amount excreted in urine; MPHP and cx-MPHP represented in sum only 4 % of the total amount excreted. The (cumulative) urinary excretion of DPHP metabolites expressed in percentage of dose on molar basis at 22 h is presented in table 2 and 3 and at 46 h in table 3.

Table 2: Molar excretion fractions of DPHP(-d4) metabolites at about 24 h (% of the oral dose administered)

Metabolite	Excretion at 24 h, Leng et al. (2014) [%]	Excretion at 22 h, Klein et al. (2018) [%]	Mean calculated excretion at about 24 h [%]
OH-MPHP	9.91 ± 3.45	2.03 ± 1.23	5.97
Oxo-MPHP	12.61 ± 3.90	3.28 ± 3.63	7.95
cx-MPHP	0.42 ± 0.11	0.095 ± 0.116	0.26

The observed molar urinary excretion fractions of DPHP metabolites measured by Wittassek and Angerer (2008) and Leng et al. (2014) are similar to each other. In comparison, the molar excretion fractions of the urinary metabolites were lower (of about a factor 4) in the study of Klein et al., (2018). According to these authors, formation and absorption of MPHP in the mouth of the volunteers who ingested the DPHP as ethanolic solution mixed in a coffee or tea containing waffle

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 15

cup during breakfast i.e. in the study conducted by Leng et al. (2014), could have been a cause for the increased urinary metabolite excretion as compared to their study in which a bolus dose was swallowed immediately.

As mentioned in a recent study of Shih et al. (2018), the knowledge regarding DPHP metabolism is limited. The authors reported in addition to the already identified four metabolites in human urine, three tentative novel biomarkers which were considered suitable DPHP exposure biomarkers because they had higher peak intensity ratios compared with all four previously reported DPHP metabolites. Two of these three tentative novel biomarkers were DPHP structure-specific metabolites (without further details). According to the authors, these novel biomarkers should be further investigated for their use in human exposure assessment. It is also necessary to further investigate if the large differences in detected metabolite fraction in urine possibly relate to these unexplained part of metabolism.

At this stage it seems reasonable to assign urinary excretion factors by taking the average of the molar excretion factors for each metabolite of DPHP from the studies performed by Leng et al. (2014) and Klein et al. (2018). The rationale for this is that there is no reason to prefer one study to the other. The studies were performed by the same laboratory according to the same method and by using comparable doses. The only difference was a different manner of administration (dosage form: dissolved in ethanol and mixed in an edible waffle cup with a chocolate surface containing coffee or tea (Leng et al., 2014) *versus* in an aqueous saccharose solution via a graduated disposable syringe (Klein et al., 2018); on an empty stomach during breakfast (Leng et al., 2014), versus after breakfast 45 and 140 min before DPHP ingestion (in order to stimulate intestinal lipase secretion) (Klein et al., 2018)). Both scenarios mirror realistic conditions and cover the possible spectrum of exposure.

Similar elimination half-lives were calculated for DPHP metabolites compared to the respective metabolite half-lives of DiNP (Koch and Angerer, 2007; Anderson et al., 2011) and DEHP (Kessler et al., 2012), whereas the molar excretion fraction of the urinary metabolites clearly differ (see table 3).

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 16

Table 3: Comparison of the molar excretion fraction of the DPHP metabolites and other phthalate's metabolites in the urine, in % of the oral dose administered

		Urinary metabolite	T1/2 (h)	Tmax (h)*	Molar excretion fraction (%) at about 24h	Molar excretion fraction (%) at about 48 h
C10	DHPH (Leng et al., 2014)	OH-MPHP	6.87	3.65	9.91	10.70
		oxo-MPHP	6.51	3.65	12.61	13.52
		cx-MPHP	8.16	4.05	0.42	0.48
					Total= 22.9	Total=24.7
C10	DHPH (Wittasek et al., 2008)	MPHP	-	-	-	~ 1
		OH-MPHP	-	-	-	~ 15
		oxo-MPHP	-	-	-	~ 16
		cx-MPHP	-	-	-	~ 3
					Total (at 61h)=34	
C10	DHPH (Klein et al., 2018)	MPHP	5.3	-	0.077**	0.083***
		OH-MPHP	5.2	-	2.03**	2.27***
		oxo-MPHP	5.4	-	3.28**	3.63***
		cx-MPHP	8.7	-	0.095**	0.116***
				Total= 5.48**	Total=6.09*** (at 46h)	
C9	DiNP (Koch and Angerer, 2007)	MiNP	~3	-	2.12	2.15
		OH-MiNP	~5	-	18.4	10.6
		oxo-MiNP	~5	-	9.97	20.18
		cx-MiNP	~5	-	9.1	10.68
				Total= 39.6	Total= 43.2	
C9	DiNP (Anderson et al., 2011)	MiNP	4-8	-	3.0	3.1
		OH-MiNP	4-8	-	11.4	12.3
		oxo-MiNP	4-8	-	6.3	6.6
		cx-MiNP	4-8	-	9.9	10.9
				Total=30.6	Total=32.9	
C8	DEHP (Koch et al., 2005)	MEHP	5	2	6.2	7.34
		OH-MEHP	10	4	23.1	24.7
		oxo-MEHP	10	4	15.5	14.9
		cx-MEPP	12-15	4	17.3	21.9
				Total=62.1	Total (at 44h)=68.9	

* T1/2: half-life, Tmax: time to obtain peak concentration

** Cumulative urinary excretion of DPHP metabolites (% of dose on molar basis) at 22 h

*** Cumulative urinary excretion of DPHP metabolites (% of dose on molar basis) at 46 h

C10, C9, C8: total number of carbon atoms of the alkyl chain of 10, 9, 8

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 17

Conclusion:

Data on the metabolism of DPHP in humans and the urinary excretion of its metabolites after oral exposure are available, albeit limited. These data indicate a rapid oral absorption of DPHP and allow in addition the establishment of preliminary molar excretion factors for the metabolites.

The molar excretion factors of DPHP metabolites determined by both Leng et al. (2014) and Klein et al. (2018) seem reliable. The analytical method used and the laboratory which performed the analysis were the same. Thus, the differences seen with comparable doses are probably not attributed to errors in measurement, but are reasoned by a different protocol for the intake of the single dose of DPHP, which was in both cases a realistic one. Furthermore, knowledge gaps relating to the formation of other metabolites could be accountable for the observed differences. For these reasons, it is proposed to use the average of the molar excretion factors for each metabolite of DPHP to cover different exposure scenarios and uncertainties (results of calculation see table 2).

No data concerning the toxicokinetics of DPHP after inhalation or after exposure *via* the cutaneous route are available. Giovanoulis et al. (2018), who calculated the relative importance of different uptake pathways for various phthalates in the general population, specify that inhalation seems negligible for the higher molecular weight phthalates, including DPHP. Using read-across with DiDP, dermal absorption of DPHP is expected to be very low (MAK Commission, 2017).

5.2 Toxicity

5.2.1 Human health effects

The current knowledge based on human exposure to DPHP on whether and how it might cause human health effects is not sufficient to derive HBM-GVs directly based on human data, be it for the general population or for the workers. Thus, HBM-GVs are based on a point of departure (POD) identified in a key animal study.

5.2.2 Animal studies and *in vitro* tests

The toxicity data of DPHP are largely coming from unpublished reports of studies carried out by the manufacturer BASF according to OECD guidelines. These study reports also form the fundament of the assessment by NICNAS (2003), the German HBM Commission (2015) and the German MAK Commission (2017). The manufacturer made available all completed study reports to these panels. Bhat et al. (2014) were also allowed to look at the study reports.

5.2.2.1 Acute toxicity

For the tests, a mixture from a process run on a pilot-plant scale was used instead of commercial-grade DPHP. This mixture contained 91.3% DPHP and 8.7% 2-propylheptyl/4-methyl-2-propylhexyl phthalate - di-4-methyl-2-propylhexyl phthalate, and was tested for acute oral, dermal and inhalation toxicity.

No mortality or unusual behaviour were observed with rats within the 14-day observation period following administration by gavage of 5000 mg/kg bw. Hence, the LD50 (oral) is > 5000 mg/kg bw (OECD, 2001a; BASF, 2009a).

Acute dermal toxicity is also very low. 2000 mg/kg bw of a mixture of the same composition as stated above were applied to the clipped backs of male and female rabbits. No mortality or unusual behaviour were observed within the 14-day post-exposure observation period. The LD50 (dermal) is > 2000 mg/kg bw (OECD, 1987; BASF, 2009a).

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 18

Male and female rats were exposed via inhalation to an aerosol mixture of the same composition as stated above (20.5 g/m³, droplet size 3–5 µm) for a period of one hour. This caused temporarily agitation, ruffled fur and raspy breathing in the animals, however no mortality or other abnormalities were noted within the 14-day post-exposure observation period. The LC50 for 1 h inhalation exposure is > 20.5 g/m³ (OECD, 2009; BASF, 2009a).

These data indicate a low acute oral, dermal and inhalation toxicity of DPHP.

5.2.2.2 Skin and eye irritation

In a test conducted according to OECD Guideline 404 (OECD, 2002a), DPHP induced slight erythema in all three test rabbits 1 h after removal of the patch. The slight erythema persisted in one animal up to 24 h, but within 48 h after patch removal, these skin reactions were reversed. The resulting mean irritation scores for 24-72 hours were 0.1 for erythema/eschar and 0.0 for oedema, respectively. Thus, DPHP was found to be not irritating to the skin (BASF, 2002a and 2003a). Also, in the acute test described above, no erythema or oedema occurred, neither on the clipped nor the abraded skin and the primary skin irritation score was found to be 0.

In an eye irritation study following the guideline OECD 405 (OECD, 2002b), DPHP caused slight to moderate conjunctival redness and slight discharge 24 h after exposure. These effects subsided within 48 h in all three animals. No other effects on the eye occurred (BASF, 2002b, 2003b). In another study, DPHP (mixture as mentioned above) had no eye irritation effects 1–168 h following exposure.

Overall, based on its slight to moderate reversible skin and eye irritation effects, classification of DPHP as “irritant” is not warranted.

5.2.2.3 Sensitisation

In a modified Buehler test, the shaved skin of five male and five female guinea pigs was treated ten times, each time for 24 h, with a DPHP mixture of the same composition as stated above. Fourteen days after the last treatment the animals were tested for sensitisation with two doses each applied for 24 h and showed no indication of a skin sensitisation (BASF, 2009a).

5.2.2.4 Repeated-dose toxicity

Results relating to repeated-dose toxicity are available from studies in Wistar and Alpk:APfSD rats.

A subchronic feeding study (BASF, 1995b) was performed over 3 months with 10 Wistar rats per sex and dose (doses: 0; 500, 2500 and 15,000 ppm¹). The highest dose (15,000 ppm in the diet) led to retarded body weight gain and reduced body weight at the end of the exposure period in both sexes. Findings at the highest dose in both sexes also included clinical-chemical and haematological changes, with an increase in alkaline phosphatase (AP) activity, cyanide-insensitive palmitoyl-CoA oxidation (8–10-fold), elevated serum albumin and increased urinary volume. Haemoglobin level, mean corpuscular haemoglobin and plasma chloride level were decreased in both sexes. Absolute and relative liver weights were increased as a result of liver cell hypertrophy. In addition, follicular hypertrophy of the thyroid gland was observed, as was, in male rats, an increase in basophilic (thyrotropic) cells in the anterior part of the pituitary gland (8/10). The medium dose (2500 ppm) induced increased activity of cyanide-insensitive palmitoyl-CoA-oxidase in females and changes to the liver (female: absolute weight; male: relative weight, hypertrophy in one animal), thyroid gland (female, male: hypertrophy) and pituitary gland (male: increased basophilic cells), although these changes were less pronounced (see Table 4). No effects were observed on reproductive organs.

¹ Corresponding to 0, 36, 181 and 1187 mg/kg bw/d for males and 0, 42, 211 and 1344 mg/kg bw/d for females

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 19

The effects on the liver and the stimulation of cyanide-insensitive palmitoyl-CoA oxidation were attributed by the authors of the study to the peroxisomal proliferation effect which phthalates are known to exhibit. The reduced blood triglyceride levels in males at the highest dose are a result of the increased lipid metabolism. The observed thyroid and pituitary glands changes were discussed as being related to the observed changes in liver metabolism. It is hypothesised by the authors that this may have led to faster metabolism of thyroid hormones T3 and T4 (however not measured or experimentally confirmed), followed by stimulation of the hypothalamic-pituitary-thyroid (HPT) axis.

Concurrent liver and thyroid hypertrophy have been relatively well characterised. For example, Elcombe et al. (2012) indicate that the activation of PPAR α , CAR, and PXR may result in increased uptake, metabolism, and elimination of thyroid hormones leading to a compensatory release of TSH to the circulation and a proliferative response in the thyroid follicular epithelium. Nevertheless, it has to be recognised that no adequate study is available to confirm this plausible mode of action, specifically for DPHP.

The changes in some erythrocyte parameters were assessed by the authors as being treatment related, as was the change in some clinical-chemical parameters, although no effect mechanism could be allocated to these changes. The slightly increased urine volumes, in combination with the decreased chloride and increased creatinine levels in serum, are seen by the authors to be indicative of a minor nephrotoxic effect of DPHP at the highest tested dose.

Compared with the controls, the slightly higher number of exposed animals with diffuse thyroid hypertrophy found at the lowest dose (2/10 at 500 ppm *versus* 1/10 at 0 ppm) was not judged to be a substance-related effect. No other effect was reported at 500 ppm.

Thus, the authors of the study derived a NOAEL of 500 ppm corresponding to 39 mg/kg bw/d as average across the NOAEL for males (36 mg/kg-day) and females (42 mg/kg-day).

In a second subchronic feeding study in rats (AlpK: APfSD, 12/sex/dose, doses²: 0; 500; 5000; and 12,000 ppm for 90 days³), of which only a summary is available (Union Carbide Corporation, 1998), the highest dose (12,000 ppm in the diet corresponding to 1000 mg/kg bw/d) caused significantly decreased body weight gain. In this study as well, peroxisome proliferation and effects on the liver (increased liver weight and unspecified liver lesions) were the main findings. In addition, vacuolisation of cells of the zona glomerulosa in the adrenal gland occurred; the severity of the lesion was dose-dependent. This effect was also thought to be related to DPHP's peroxisome proliferation effect. While histological examination of the testes did not reveal any abnormalities, the spermogram showed significant and marked reductions in sperm velocity at the highest dose, and average sperm velocity was also significantly reduced at the medium dose. This effect was fully reversible within the recovery period. Other sperm parameters including percent motile sperms were unaffected. The authors of the study indicate that the observed effect of DPHP on sperm velocity may be explained by the nutritional status and the reduced body weights. Based on the findings of this study, the authors derived a NOAEL of 500 ppm in the diet (40 mg/kg bw/d).

² Corresponding to 0, 40, 420 and 1000 mg/kg bw/d

³ Two additional groups receiving 0 or 1000 mg/kg bw/d were included for a four-week recovery period

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 20

Table 4: Repeated-dose effects of DPHP

Species, strain, sex and number/dose	Duration	Dose	NOAEL	Effects at dose/remarks	Reference
Rat, Wistar, 10 m/10 f	3 months	0, 500, 2500, 15,000 ppm in the diet (m: 0, 36, 181,1187 mg/kg bw/d; f: 0, 42, 211, 1344 mg/kg bw/d)	500 ppm m: 36 mg/kg bw/d f: 42 mg/kg bw/d Averaged m + f: 39 mg/kg bw/d	500 ppm m: thyroid gland: diffuse hypertrophy (2/10, control: 1/10)	BASF, 1995b
				2500 ppm m+ f: liver weight ↑, thyroid gland: diffuse follicular hypertrophy, m: albumin ↑, liver cell hypertrophy (1/10), pituitary gland: basophilic cells↑, f: cyanide insensitive palmitoyl CoA oxidation ↑	
				15,000 ppm m+f: bw, bw gain ↓, urine volume ↑, AP ↑, cyanide insensitive palmitoyl-CoA oxidation ↑, albumin ↑, Hb ↓, MCH ↓, Cl ⁻ ↓, liver weight ↑, liver cell hypertrophy, thyroid gland: diffuse follicular hypertrophy, m: thrombocytes ↑, haematocrit ↓, TG ↓, pituitary gland: basophilic cells ↑, f: creatinine ↑, glucose ↓	
Rat, Alpk: APfSD, 12 m/12 f	14 weeks	0, 500, 5000, 12,000 ppm in the diet (0, 40, 420, 1000 mg/kg bw/d) Satellite group: 0, 12,000 ppm, 4-week recovery period	500 ppm 40 mg/kg bw/d	500 ppm m+f: liver weight ↑, adrenal gland: zona glomerulosa vacuolisation (minimal)	Union Carbide Corporation (1998)
				5000 ppm m+f: cyanide insensitive palmitoyl-CoA oxidation ↑, cholesterol ↓, TG ↓, adrenal gland: zona glomerulosa vacuolisation (slight), liver: peroxisome proliferation, m: bw gain ↓, food consumption ↓, RBC ↓, Hb ↓, haematocrit ↓, thrombocytes ↑, testes: sperm velocity ↓, reversible within recovery period	

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 21

Species, strain, sex and number/dose	Duration	Dose	NOAEL	Effects at dose/remarks	Reference
				12,000 ppm: m+f: bw gain ↓, RBC ↓, Hb ↓, haematocrit ↓, thrombocytes ↑, Na+↓, K+ ↑, cholesterol ↓, TG ↓, cyanide insensitive palmitoyl-CoA oxidation ↑, adrenal gland: zona glomerulosa vacuolisation (moderate), peroxisome proliferation, m: testes: sperm velocity ↓, reversible within recovery period	
<i>m: male, f: female, bw: body weight, AP: alkaline phosphatase, Hb: Haemoglobin, MCH: mean corpuscular haemoglobin, TG: triglyceride, RBC: red blood corpuscles = erythrocytes</i>					

Chronic oral animal studies for DPHP were not identified in the literature.

A short-term repeated dose inhalation toxicity study⁴ (exposure 6 h/day during 5 days) on 10 male Wistar rats per dose was conducted in 2012 at doses of 0, 50, 250, 1000 mg/m³ (ECHA registration dossier; MAK Commission, 2017).

After inhalation exposure (nose/head-only) of rats to aerosol concentrations of 1000 mg/m³ for 5 days, increases in the absolute and relative liver (+30%) and lung weights (+37%) were observed. The following secondary effects can be seen as sequels of the overloading of the lungs and macrophages with the oily, insoluble material: foam cell infiltrations in the terminal bronchioles and slight to moderate alveolar histiocytosis, combined with a slight to moderate lymphoreticular reaction in the mediastinal lymph nodes.

In addition, there was slight to moderate hypertrophy in the terminal bronchial epithelium and in the trachea (MAK Commission, 2017). At 250 mg/m³, the effects in the respiratory tract were much less pronounced. Also, a minimal to moderate granulomatous inflammation was observed in the lungs of two males in test group 2 (250 mg/m³) and in nine males of test group 3 (1000 mg/m³) which were regarded as treatment related (ECHA registration dossier). At concentrations of 50 mg/m³ and above, the incidence of goblet cells in certain areas of the nasal conchae was increased in all animals more or less regardless of the test concentration. The increased presence of goblet cells is a physiological reaction to an overload phenomenon as a reaction to the impaction of the oily particles and does not represent a substance-specific adverse effect, but is an adaptive process, resulting in proliferative effects (MAK Commission, 2017). A NOAEC of 50 mg/m³ for local effects was established by the authors of the study based on effects on the respiratory tract.

Systemic effects not reported in the MAK Commission document have been reported on the ECHA website: In rats exposed to 1000 mg/m³, globulin and total protein levels were decreased, whereas cholesterol levels were increased. These effects were considered test-substance related and adverse by the authors of the study. Cyanide sensitive Palmitoyl CoA oxidation (Pal CoA) in liver

⁴ <https://echa.europa.eu/en/registration-dossier/-/registered-dossier/14145/7/6/3>

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 22

tissue was also higher in this group compared to controls. The mean body weights of all test groups were not statistically significant different from the control group. However, the mean body weight change of test group 3 (1000 mg/m³) was slightly, though significantly lower than in the control. The following significant body weight changes were observed, but not regarded as treatment related by the authors of the study:

- Test group 1 (50 mg/m³), from study day 0 to 4 (-1.9 g, p< 0.05)
- Test group 3 (1000 mg/m³) from study day 0 to 4 (-5.1 g, p< 0.01)

A NOAEC of 250 mg/m³ for systemic effects was set. It has to be kept in mind that the doses for the rats were very high compared to what one would encounter among the workers in phthalate compounding and vehicle filter production (Hines et al. 2008).

5.2.2.5 Genotoxicity and mutagenicity

In vivo studies on DPHP are missing.

In vitro

In a bacterial mutagenicity test according to OECD Guideline 471 (OECD, 1997a), DPHP showed no mutagenic effects in *Salmonella typhimurium* strains TA98, TA100, TA1535 and TA1537 in a standard plate test and a pre-incubation procedure with and without metabolic activation. The doses tested ranged from 20 to 5000 µg/plate, whereby precipitations occurred from 500 µg/plate upwards. The positive controls induced the expected increased mutation rates (BASF, 1995c).

In a test according to OECD Guideline 476 (OECD, 1997b) for induction of mutations in an HPRT (hypoxanthine-guanine phosphoribosyl transferase) assay with Chinese hamster ovary (CHO) cells, the test substance Palatinol 10-P showed no mutagenic effect in two trials with different exposure duration both in the absence and presence of an exogenous metabolic activation system. The test substance Palatinol 10-P, an isomer mixture (purity about 99 %), was dissolved in acetone and added to the culture medium in concentrations of up to 5.2 mg/ml. Even the highest concentration was non-cytotoxic, but visible precipitation occurred from 0.65 mg/ml upwards. The positive controls induced the expected effect (BASF, 2010).

In testing for chromosomal aberration according to OECD Guideline 473 (OECD, 1997c) with Chinese hamster V79 cells, three experiments with different exposure and incubation periods were carried out. The test substance Palatinol 10-P was dissolved in acetone and tested at concentrations of up to 5.2 mg/ml. However, at concentrations from 0.2 mg/ml upwards turbidity occurred because solubility was exceeded. After an exposure period of 18 h and another 18 or 28 h of incubation, a slight increase in the number of aberrant metaphasic cells occurred at concentrations near the solubility limit in the absence of an exogenous metabolic activation system. The increase was neither dose-related nor statistically significant, however. The positive controls induced the expected effect (BASF, 2011).

In summary, DPHP is not genotoxic *in vitro*.

5.2.2.6 Carcinogenicity

Due to the lack of carcinogenicity data, there is inadequate information to assess carcinogenic potential of DPHP.

Pursuant to the German MAK Commission (2017) the critical effect for the evaluation of DPHP systemic toxicity is the peroxisome proliferating activity of DPHP in rat liver after oral administration which has also been observed with other phthalates. DPHP is less potent as a peroxisome proliferator than the structurally very similar DEHP, which is a rat liver carcinogen. Beyond that, the

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 23

data available at present indicate that the peroxisome proliferation in the liver of rodents activated by the PPAR α receptor is generally of little relevance for humans. In *in vitro* studies conducted with primary hepatocytes, phthalic acid esters had no effects in guinea pigs and primates (Elcombe et al., 1996). The PPAR α receptor is found in the human liver in considerably lower concentrations (1% to 10%) than those found in the liver of rats and mice (Palmer et al. 1998).

Nevertheless, as no carcinogenicity study has been performed on DPHP, but due to the similarity to DEHP⁵, liver carcinogenicity cannot be excluded. Therefore, DPHP is classified in Category 3B⁶ for suspected carcinogens (MAK Commission, 2017).

5.2.2.7 Effects on reproduction and development

Studies have been performed on rats.

Reproductive toxicity

Reproduction toxicity to rats was assessed in a two-generation study (BASF, 2009b) complying to OECD Guideline 416 (OECD, 2001c). The test substance (Palatinol 10-P) was administered to groups of 25 male and 25 female Wistar rats *via* the diet at doses of 0, 40, 200 or 600 mg/kg bw/d. From day 75, the animals within each dose group were paired to produce offspring (F1 generation). After weaning, groups of 25 males and 25 females from the F1 generation received corresponding doses of the test substance and, like the generation before them, were paired to produce offspring (F2 generation). The study ended with the weaning of the F2 generation.

Effects on reproduction and development

The test substance did not influence the fertility and reproductive performance of parental animals up to the highest dose tested. Substance-induced effects on sperm or spermatid number, number of normal or abnormal sperm, and sperm motility were not found in any of the dose groups.

Viability, sex ratio and sexual development and maturation of offspring were also unaffected up to highest dose. In particular, male offspring did not show any changes in anogenital distance or the number and percentage of pups having areolae which would have to be considered as an indication of feminisation and, thus, of an oestrogenic or anti-androgenic effect of the test substance. The NOAEL (for fertility and reproduction toxicity) was 600 mg/kg bw/d in this study.

F1 and F2 offspring exposed to the highest dose gained less body weight than the control offspring from lactation day 14 onwards and also had lower body weights than the latter. In addition, the spleen and thymus weights of these animals were decreased. The NOAEL (for developmental toxicity) was 200 mg/kg bw/d.

Systemic effects

The highest dose (600 mg/kg bw/d) led to intermittent diminutions in food consumption and to reductions of body weight gain or decrease in body weights in F0 animals (males and females) and F1 males during various phases. Furthermore, the rats of both sexes in the F0 and F1 generation showed a mild anaemia.

From the medium dose level (200 mg/kg bw/d), clinical-chemical changes concerning liver cells and bone metabolism were noted in the F0 and F1 generation of males and females. Histopathological examination revealed a hepatocellular hypertrophy along with cytoplasmic eosinophilia, which is indicative of peroxisome proliferation. Also changes in liver and kidney organ

⁵ DEHP is classified in category 4 (substances with carcinogenic potential for which genotoxicity plays no or almost a minor part)

⁶ Substances for which *in vitro* or animal studies have yielded evidence of carcinogenic effects that is not sufficient for classification of the substance in one of the other categories. Further studies are required before a final decision can be made.

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 24

weight and morphological changes in the kidneys, thyroid and pituitary glands were observed and regarded by the authors of the study as secondary to the peroxisome proliferation effect (see table 5 taken from Bhat et al. (2014) for an overview and the statistical significance of the effects).

The changes observed at 40 mg/kg bw/d were assessed by the authors of the study as not being substance-related, so that this lowest dose was identified as NOAEL for systemic-toxic effects.

Table 5: Selected statistically significant effects in adult F0 and/or F1 generation Wistar rats fed DPHP (Bhat et al., 2014 according to BASF, 2009b)^a

	F ₀ male				F ₀ female			
	0	38.1	190.2	573.2	0	38.7	193.4	583.4
F ₀ rat consumed dose (mg/kg/day)	0	38.1	190.2	573.2	0	38.7	193.4	583.4
F ₀ human equivalent dose (mg/kg/day) ^b	0	10.7	53.2	157	0	9.4	46.9	141.3
Terminal body weight	–	-1%	-4%**	-13%**	–	-2%	-1%	-3%
Liver weight (absolute/relative)	–	+1%/+3%*	+21%**/26%**	+55%**/78%*	–	-4%/-2%	+11%**/ 13%**	+47%**/ 51%**
Kidney weight (absolute/relative)	–	0%	+10%**/15%**	+14%**/32%*	–	+3%/4%*	+1%/+3%	+4%/7%*
Increased serum alkaline phosphatase	–	+9%	+31%**	+145%**	–	-5%	+15%	+56%**
Increased serum inorganic phosphorous	–	+2%	+9%*	+8%*	–	-5%	+1%	+9%
Decreased serum calcium	–	0%	-3%*	-6%**	–	0%	-1%	-3%
Decreased serum cholesterol	–	-6%	-33%**	-56%**	–	-12%	-30%**	-36%**
Decreased serum triglycerides	–	-13%	-35%**	-48%**	–	-4%	-30%*	-47%**
Hepatocyte hypertrophy, diffuse eosinophilic	–	0	25	25	0	0	2	25
Renal lesions ^c	Not observed							
	F ₁ male				F ₁ female			
F ₁ rat consumed dose (mg/kg/day)	0	38.0	191.3	575.1	0	38.6	192.8	579.3
F ₁ human equivalent dose (mg/kg/day) ^b	0	10.7	54.0	157.6	0	9.2	46.0	138.2
Terminal body weight	–	-2%	-3%	-14%**	–	+2%	0%	0%
Liver weight (absolute/relative)	–	0%/+2%	+20%**/ +24%**	+46%**/ +71%**	–	+5%/ +3%	+12%**/+11%**	+46%**/ +46%**

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 25

Kidney weight (absolute/relative)	-	+1%/+3%	+9% ^{**} /+12% ^{**}	+7%/+25% ^{**}	-	+3%/+1%	0%/0%	+7%/+7% ^{**}
Thyroid weight (absolute/relative)	-	+15% ^{**} / +33% ^{**}	+19% ^{**} / +33% ^{**}	+7% [*] /+33% ^{**}	-	+3%/0%	+6%/0%	+17% ^{**} / +11% ^{**}
Increased serum alkaline phosphatase	-	+7%	+57% ^{**}	+148% ^{**}	-	+8%	+5%	+60% ^{**}
Increased serum inorganic phosphorous	-	-2%	+7%	+12% [*]	-	+5%	+11%	+5%
Decreased serum calcium	-	0%	-2% [*]	-3% ^{**}	-	+1%	0%	-3% ^{**}
Decreased serum cholesterol	-	-8%	-32% ^{**}	-61% ^{**}	-	-1%	-16% ^{**}	-24% ^{**}
Decreased serum triglycerides	-	-26% ^{**}	-39% ^{**}	-56% ^{**}	-	-14%	-28% ^{**}	-50% ^{**}
Hepatocyte hypertrophy, diffuse eosinophilic	0	0	22	25	0	0	0	23
Renal eosinophilic tubules-all severity grades (1 or 2) combined	0	0	11	24	0	0	0	6
Thyroid altered colloid	9	11	21	25	4	5	9	17
Thyroid follicular hypertrophy/hyperplasia - all severity grades (1 or 2) combined	2	3	13	16	2	3	6	18
Thyroid follicular hypertrophy/hyperplasia-grade 2	0	0	0	4	0	0	1	9

^a Target organ effects; 25 male and female rats per dose were sacrificed at 16 or 10 weeks of age, respectively.

^b Based BW 3/4 power scaling (U.S. EPA, 2011) using mean body weight at sacrifice in each dose group and 70 kg in humans.

^c Thyroid histology not included in F0 adults.

* Statistically significant at $p < 0.05$

** Statistically significant at $p < 0.01$

Developmental toxicity

Two studies are available, performed complying to OECD Guideline 414 (OECD, 2001b). In one of the two studies (BASF, 2009), developmental toxicity effects were observed at maternally toxic doses, whilst another older study with a shorter dosing period found neither maternal nor developmental toxicity (BASF 1995d).

In the study from 2003 (BASF, 2003c), pregnant Wistar rats received the test substance Palatinol 10-P (DHPH stabilised with 0.5% BPA) by gavage at dose levels of 0, 40, 200 or 1000 mg/kg bw/d in 5 ml olive oil from day 6 to day 19 post-coitum. This means that the exposure also covered the time window critical for the identification of anti-androgenic effects (gestational days 16 – 18) in the late phase of pregnancy (Carruthers and Foster, 2005). Delivery by caesarean section was on day 20. No substance-related effects were found at the lowest and medium dose levels. At the highest dose, signs of maternal toxicity were found in form of urine-smearred fur and reductions in food

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 26

consumption (-11 %), body weight gain (-30 %) and final body weight (-6 %) compared to the control. The mean uterus weight was lower (-19 %) than that of the control, but there were three dams which had no live foetuses at all, but only very early resorptions. The increased rate of early post-implantation loss (23.1 % compared to 6.2 % in the control group) is primarily due to these three dams. Foetuses showed a slight but significant increase in soft tissue variations (renal pelvis and ureter dilation) and skeletal variations (unossified sternebra and supernumerary ribs). The NOAEL for maternal toxicity and developmental toxicity in this study was 200 mg/kg bw/d.

In an earlier study (BASF, 1995d), pregnant Wistar rats were administered DPHP at doses of 0, 40, 200 and 1000 mg/kg bw/d in olive oil from day 6 to day 15 post-coitum. Caesarean section was on day 20. In none of the DPHP-treated groups, signs of maternal toxicity or developmental toxicity including teratogenicity were observed. As skeletal variation, accessory ribs, occurred in the medium and (significantly) in the highest dose group, but since the incidence even at the highest dose was in the range of historical control values, this finding was not assessed to be a substance-related effect.

Furr et al. (2014) applied a short-term screening protocol to detect disruption of fetal testosterone synthesis (Fetal Phthalate Screen - FPS). They administered pregnant rats (n=3-4 dams per group) from GD 14 to 18 daily 0 and 750 mg/kg bw/d test substance by gavage. At GD 18, fetal testes were removed and 3 testes per litter were used to measure ex vivo testosterone production. DPHP did not inhibit testosterone production at a dose of 750 mg/kg bw/d.

5.2.3 Assessment by different bodies and conclusion

No adverse effects on the sexual organs of rats were observed in a 90-day feeding-study in which the animals were given DPHP in doses of up to 1266 mg/kg bw/d (males: 1187 mg/kg bw/d and females 1344 mg/kg bw/d), or in a developmental toxicity study with doses up to 1000 mg/kg bw/d, or in a 2-generation study with doses up to 600 mg/kg bw/d.

The liver, kidneys, as well as thyroid, pituitary and adrenal gland were target organs following subchronic dietary DPHP exposure of rats based on changes in organ weights, clinical blood parameters, and/or histopathology. Similar to subchronic exposure in Wistar rats (BASF, 1995b), some F0 and/or F1 generation dose groups of the two-generation study (BASF, 2009b) had altered blood parameters and liver, kidney, thyroid and pituitary gland effects.

Based on observed incidences and on benchmark dose (BMD) results, Bhat et al. (2014) considered the thyroid gland as the most sensitive target organ. A NOAEL for male rats from the two-generation study was not identified by Bhat et al. (2014), because of the statistically significant increase of mean thyroid weights (absolute and relative to body weight) for the F1-generation males at all doses (Table 5). A NOAEL based on thyroid follicular hypertrophy/hyperplasia for the F1-generation females was set at 39 mg/kg bw/d (with a LOAEL at 193 mg/kg bw/d). Altogether, considering both, the results from the subchronic and two-generation studies (BASF 1995b and 2009b), the NOAEL can be considered 40 mg/kg bw/d in both sexes. Bhat et al. (2014) performed benchmark dose modelling with a 10% benchmark response level for comparison to the NOAEL/LOAEL values. A human equivalent BMD_{10L95} of 10 mg/kg bw/d for thyroid follicular hypertrophy/hyperplasia observed in F1 adults from the two-generation study on DPHP (BASF, 2009b) was obtained, as well as a human equivalent BMD_{10L95} of 6.1 mg/kg bw/d for thyroid follicular hypertrophy after subchronic exposure (BASF, 1995b). The rodent thyroid gland effects were considered potentially relevant to human health given qualitative similarities in thyroid axis function between humans and rodents. The BMD_{10L95} of 10 mg/kg bw/d was thereby considered as POD for deriving a Reference dose (RfD). An AF of 10 for intraspecies variability, 3 for study duration (subchronic → chronic) and another factor of 3 to account for the incomplete database

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 27

(lack of carcinogenicity and second-species systemic and developmental toxicity data) were applied. An additional AF to account for the toxicodynamic component of interspecies variability was not applied, since rodents are more sensitive than humans to thyroid gland effects (Fisher, 2012). The RfD calculated by Bhat et al. (2014) using the BMD method is thus 0.1 mg/kg bw/d.

The **German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR, 2011)** rates the DPHP effects on the thyroid and the pituitary gland observed in subchronic oral toxicity studies on rats as critical effects. A NOAEL of 40 mg/kg bw/d (rounded from 39) was determined and used for further risk assessment. Application of a total assessment factor of 1000 (10 for intra-, 10 for interspecies differences, and an additional children factor of 10) lead to the TDI-like value of 0.04 mg/kg bw/d DPHP below which – according to the knowledge on the substance at that time – there was negligible risk for adverse health effects for children anticipated. The corresponding TDI-like value for adults was therefore estimated at 0.4 mg/kg bw/d.

Like the BfR (2011), the **National Industrial Chemicals Notification and Assessment Scheme (NICNAS, 2003)** consulted the subchronic BASF study on rats (BASF, 1995b) and used the NOAEL of 39 mg/kg bw/d as POD for the calculation of a Margin of Exposure (MOE). A TDI or an analogous value was however not derived.

In a 2011 report of the **U.S. Consumer Product Safety Commission (CPSC)**, an acceptable daily intake value (ADI) for DPHP was not estimated on grounds of missing confirmatory data on toxicological endpoints.

DPHP is registered under the REACH regulation by the manufacturer BASF as lead registrant of a registration consortium (ECHA, 2010). The summary toxicological report is available on ECHA's website. Except for the studies from 2009 and 2010, it is almost identical to the published IUCLID-5 dataset. The applicant reported a DNEL for long-term systemic oral exposure of the general population at 5 mg/kg bw/d, as well as a DNEL for long-term systemic inhalation exposure of the workers at 35.3 mg.m⁻³. Both DNELS are based on a NOAEL at 200 mg/kg bw/d identified from the BASF (2009b) two-generation study. However, systemic effects are already seen at doses lower than 200 mg/kg bw/d, as assessed by various bodies. This applicant DNELS are thus not retained for deriving the HBM-GVs.

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 28

Table 6: Overview of NOAELs and corresponding TDI/RfD/DNEL values derived for DPHP

Evaluating panel/author	Critical effects	Key study	Point of departure (mg/kg bw/ d)	Assessment factors	TDI/RfD/DNEL
General population					
Bhat et al. (2014)	thyroid follicular hypertrophy/hyperplasia, observed in F1 adults	two-generation study (BASF, 2009b)	BMD_{10L}: 10 mg/kg bw/d (human equivalent dose)	100 AF _H 10 AF _S 3 AF _D 3	RfD: 0.1 mg/kg bw/d
BfR (2011)	effects on thyroid and pituitary gland	subchronic oral toxicity study on rats (BASF, 1995b)	NOAEL: 40 mg/kg bw/d	1000	Children, TDI-like value: 0.04 mg/kg bw/d
NICNAS (2003)	effects on thyroid and pituitary gland	subchronic oral toxicity study on rats (BASF, 1995b)	NOAEL: 39 mg/kg bw/d	-	MOE
CPSC	-				Not derived
BASF (2009b)	thyroid follicular hypertrophy/hyperplasia, observed in F1 adults	two-generation study	NOAEL: 200 mg/kg bw/d	40 AF _A 4 AF _H 10	DNEL (Gen. pop, oral): 5 mg/kg bw/d
BASF (2009b)	thyroid follicular hypertrophy/hyperplasia, observed in F1 adults	two-generation study	Starting POD NOAEL: 200 mg/kg bw/d Modified POD NOAEC : 87 mg/m³	10 AF _H 10	DNEL (Gen. pop, long-term inhalation): 8,7 mg/m³
BASF (1995b)	effects on thyroid and pituitary gland	subchronic oral toxicity study on rats	NOAEL: 39 mg/kg bw/d		Not derived
Workers					
BASF (2009b)	thyroid follicular hypertrophy/hyperplasia, observed in F1 adults	two-generation study	Starting POD NOAEL: 200 mg/kg bw/d Modified POD NOAEC : 176.3 mg/m³	5 AF _H 5	DNEL (workers, long-term; inhalation): 35,3 mg/m³
MAK Commission (2017)	Peroxisome proliferation in rat liver		-		Not derived

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 29

Conclusion

Thyroid effects reported in the subchronic and two-generation studies in rats (BASF, 1995b and 2009b) are selected as critical effects for DPHP. There are indeed drawbacks of these studies using a rodent model: firstly, the observed thyroid and pituitary gland changes are probably related to the observed changes in the liver. It is hypothesised that modification of the liver physiology may have led to faster degradation of the thyroid hormones, followed by stimulation of the HPT axis. Unfortunately, no thyroid hormone levels were measured in the studies in order to assess this mechanism. Secondly, rodents are recognised to be more sensitive to thyroid hormone disruption than humans. However, the indirect effects of DPHP on thyroid signalling are considered adverse and as their potential relevance to human health cannot be discounted, these effects are selected for deriving HBM-GVs.

Bhat et al. (2014) developed a human equivalent $BMD_{10L_{95}}$ of 10 mg/kg bw/d based on thyroid follicular hypertrophy/hyperplasia observed in F1 adults from the two-generation study on DPHP (BASF, 2009b). This BMDL is considered adequate as POD for deriving a toxicity reference value aimed to protect the general population.

A similar human equivalent $BMD_{10L_{95}}$ (6.1 mg/kg bw/d) is obtained by the same authors based on thyroid follicular hypertrophy observed in F0 rats after subchronic exposure (study from BASF 1995b, 6-weeks old rats at the start of the exposure) suggesting that *in utero* exposure does not increase sensitivity to thyroid lesions. This $BMD_{10L_{95}}$ is selected for deriving the $HBM-GV_{worker}$. According to the methodology for deriving $HBM-GV_{worker}$ (Apel et al., 2020), it is adequate to consider effects observed in toxicity studies exposing adult-grown animals for deriving a value aimed to protect the adult working population (in contrast to F1 animals whose exposure lasted during gestation and lactation until weaning), where the effect is not reprotoxic. It is important here to highlight that the selected critical effect on the thyroid gland does not seem to be mediated by a reprotoxic mechanism, and should not affect offspring of occupationally-exposed women.

Bhat et al. (2014) conducted their BMD modelling with the BMDS software (US EPA, Version 2.4, 2013b⁷) and, as described in the supplementary data, constraints were applied to the models for obtaining the BMDLs consistent with the US EPA guideline. However, the BMDL values would be probably different if recommendations of the current BMD modelling EFSA guideline (EFSA, 2017) were followed, or if the updated version of the BMDS software v.3.1.1 (US EPA, 2019⁸) was used. Indeed, the choice of the best mathematical dose-response model to fit the data would likely not be the same. Currently, the model averaging approach is recommended by EFSA as the preferred method for calculating the BMD confidence interval, while acknowledging that the respective tools are still under development and may not be easily accessible to all. Where the software is not performing model averaging, EFSA recommends to consider the lowest BMDL and highest BMDU from the selected good-fitting models to define the BMD confidence interval.

Despite this however, it seems reasonable to consider the BMDL values from Bhat et al (2014) as conservative PODs, compared to the NOAEL/LOAEL approach (considering also the advantage of BMDLs being less dependent on the experimental dose selection and sample size).

⁷ Benchmark Dose Software Version 2.4. National Center for Environmental Assessment, Office of Research and Development, Available at: <http://www.epa.gov/ncea/bmds.htm> according to Bhat et al 2014

⁸ <https://www.epa.gov/bmds/benchmark-dose-software-bmds-version-311-download>

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 30

6 Selected biomarker(s) for the HBM-GV proposal and analytical method

6.1 Choice of biomarkers

6.1.1 For HBM measurements in the general population

Data on DPHP metabolism and excretion in humans are available (see chapter 2.1.2). The secondary oxidised metabolites are specific biomarkers to determine DPHP exposure, they have an added analytical benefit in that they are not subject to issues of sample contamination (Gries et al., 2012; Leng et al., 2014). Moreover, the monoester MPHP is only a minor metabolite (<1% formed from the parent compound and excreted with urine), which is typical for all high molecular weight phthalates. The main metabolites found were oxo-MPHP and OH-MPHP (Leng et al., 2014, Klein et al., 2018). The average Fue (urinary excretion factor, here after ca. 48 h) for oxo-MPHP is 0.0858 and for OH-MPHP is 0.0649 (after calculation of a mean value as described above under chapter 2.1.2).

However, it has to be pointed out, that the studies on metabolism did not consider metabolite excretion in female subjects, nor age-specific differences or the potential dependency of the metabolism on the exposure level.

6.1.2 For HBM measurements in the occupational field

Studies in the workplace reporting levels of metabolites in biological matrices are currently not available. The specific secondary oxidised metabolites are also retained as biomarkers to determine DPHP exposure in the occupational field (Gries et al., 2012; Leng et al., 2014). The average Fue (urinary excretion factor, here after about 24 h) for oxo-MPHP is 0.0795 and for OH-MPHP is 0.0597, after calculation of a mean value as described above under chapter 2.1.2.

6.2 Analytical methods

A specific determination of DPHP metabolites in human urine in presence of DiNP and/or DiDP is possible if gas chromatography/high-resolution mass spectrometry is used instead of LC MS/MS (poor peak resolution) (see also HBM4EU D9.2 on selected biomarkers and analytical methods). This specific method has been developed and described in detail by Gries et al., (2012). Following enzymatic hydrolysis using glucuronidase, the three main substance-specific metabolites OH-MPHP, oxo-MPHP and in smaller amounts than the former cx-MPHP are extracted from urine, derivatised and, after gas chromatographic separation, quantified using high-resolution mass spectrometry. The detection limits for the metabolites range between 0.05 and 0.1 µg/l (0.05 µg/l for cx-MPHP; 0.08 µg/l for oxo-MPHP; 0.1 µg/l for OH-MPHP), and the corresponding limits of quantification range between 0.15 and 0.3 µg/l (0.15 µg/l for cx-MPHP; 0.25 µg/l for oxo-MPHP and 0.3 µg/l for OH-MPHP).

In special cases (e.g. low co-exposure to DiNP/DiDP or use of deuterated DPHP) the LC-MS/MS method is acceptable too.

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 31

7 Choice of the HBM-GVs derivation method

The existing database on biomonitoring data on DPHP does not allow for the derivation of HBM-GVs for the general population or for workers based on a relationship between human internal concentrations (parent compound or biomarker(s)) and health effects. Regarding workers, there is also neither evidence of a relationship between the atmospheric concentration of DPHP and the urinary concentration of the biomarkers of exposure nor an OEL available. Thus, it has been investigated if HBM-GVs could be derived on the basis of other external toxicity reference values. As a result, the reference dose (RfD) established by Bhat et al., (2014) from NSF International as an U.S. accredited, independent third-party certification has been chosen as output value for deriving the HBM-GV_{GenPop}.

Factsheets summarising the data which are relevant to perform the derivation of the HBM-GVs, as described here below, are provided in the section 7 of this report: section 7.1 summarises the information used for the HBM-GV derivation for the general population, and section 7.2 summarises the information used for the workers HBM-GV derivation.

7.1 Derivation of HBM-GVs for the general population based on a reference dose

7.1.1 RfD - Underlying POD and assessment factors

The two-generation feeding study with rats (BASF, 2009b) is regarded as the key study and the effects on the thyroid (follicular hypertrophy/hyperplasia) observed in F1 adults are rated assessment-relevant (Bhat et al., 2014). The human equivalent BMDL₁₀ determined for those effects by Bhat et al. (2014) is 10 mg/kg bw/d. Applied assessment factors (AFs) refer to the intraspecies variability (10), the study duration (3) and to the incomplete database (lack of carcinogenicity and second-species systemic and developmental toxicity data, 3). Extrapolation from a two-generation study to chronic exposure with a factor 3 is explained by the authors as follows: “.....since the additional in utero and longer exposure duration of the F1 adults exposed to DPHP (BASF AG, 2009) in the present assessment did not alter sensitivity to thyroid lesions, a study duration extrapolation factor of 3x was considered adequate to address the lack of a lifetime exposure study for DPHP.”

The toxicodynamic component of the interspecies variability is not addressed with an additional AF with the justification of rodents being more sensitive than humans to thyroid gland effects. For example, while humans have a lower T4 secretion rate compared to rats, humans, unlike rats, have thyroxine-binding globulin to bind and thus increase the half-life of T4 (5–9 days) compared to rats (<1 day) (Fisher et al., 2012).

This latter approach to abstain from a further AF referring to the toxicodynamic component of the interspecies variability is plausible, albeit unusual. On the other hand, one could argue that the use of an AF of 3 for the extrapolation from the two-generation study to chronic exposure and in addition, the use of an AF of 3 for reasons of incomplete database is in this case a protective line of action. In conclusion, the order of magnitude of the total AF (about 100) is supported and thus the RfD of 0.1 mg/kg bw/d taken up as toxicity reference value at which the corresponding urinary biomarker(s) concentration will be calculated to obtain the HBM-GV_{GenPop}.

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 32

7.1.2 Calculation of HBM-GVs for the general population

HBM-GVs are given for the sum of the two metabolites oxo-MPHP and OH-MPHP as preferred approach, but also for the single metabolites oxo-MPHP and OH-MPHP in case of data availability for only one metabolite (see table 7).

Input parameters for the calculation are the molecular weights of DPHP and its measured metabolites, the *F_{ue}* of the measured metabolites after 24 h and the daily urine volume adjusted to the body weight (Kommission Human-Biomonitoring, 2007). The 24 h values for excretion are preferred because a large proportion of OH- and oxo-MPHP is excreted in urine within 24 h and the mass conservation equation was established considering an excretion during 24 h: DPHP has a molecular weight of 446.7 g/mol; the molecular weights of the metabolites oxo-MPHP (C₁₈H₂₄O₅) and OH-MPHP (C₁₈H₂₆O₅) are 320.4 and 322.4 g/mol, respectively. The *F_{ue}* (24 h) for oxo-MPHP is 0.0795 and for OH-MPHP is 0.0597. The daily urine volume adjusted to the body weight is according to the current state of knowledge 0.03 l/kg bw/d for children and 0.02 l/kg bw/d for adults. (Recent data on the daily urine volume adjusted to the body weight are evaluated at the moment and might change the default value in future.)

$$\text{HBM - GV}(\text{GenPop}) = \frac{\text{TRV} \cdot \left[\frac{\text{MW}(\text{Metabolite1}) \cdot \text{Fue}(\text{Metabolite1}) + \text{MW}(\text{Metabolite2}) \cdot \text{Fue}(\text{Metabolite2})}{\text{MW}(\text{Substance})} \right]}{\text{Daily urine volume adjusted to the BW}}$$

TRV = Toxicity Reference Value; *MW* = Molecular Weight; *Fue* = proportional urinary excretion factor; *BW* = Body Weight

HBM-GV calculation for the sum of oxo-MPHP and OH-MPHP

a) Bodyweight-related urine excretion rate adjustment (0.02 l/kg bw/d for adults):

$$\text{HBM - GV}(\text{GenPop}) = \frac{0.1 \text{ mg/kg bw/d} \cdot \left[\frac{320.4 \text{ g/mol}(\text{oxo-MPHP}) \cdot (0.0795) + 322.4 \text{ g/mol}(\text{OH-MPHP}) \cdot (0.0597)}{446.7 \text{ g/mol}(\text{DPHP})} \right]}{0.02 \text{ l/kg bw/d}}$$

The HBM-GV_{GenPop} referring to the sum of the metabolites oxo-MPHP and OH-MPHP in human urine is therefore for adults: 0.50 mg/l

b) Bodyweight-related urine excretion rate adjustment (0.03 l/kg bw/d for children):

The HBM-GV_{GenPop} referring to the sum of the metabolites oxo-MPHP and OH-MPHP in human urine is therefore for children: 0.33 mg/l

HBM-GV calculation for oxo-MPHP and OH-MPHP measured as single metabolites

Table 7 gives an overview of derived HBM-GVs for the general population with respect to oxo-MPHP and OH-MPHP alone and also as sum.

Table 7: HBM-GV_{GenPop} referring to the sum of oxo-MPHP and OH-MPHP and to the respective single metabolites

Measured biomarker	HBM-GV _{GenPop} for adults [mg/l]	HBM-GV _{GenPop} for children [mg/l]
oxo-MPHP and OH-MPHP	0.50	0.33
oxo-MPHP	0.29	0.19
OH-MPHP	0.22	0.14

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 33

7.2 Derivation of HBM-GVs for the occupational field based on an animal POD

7.2.1 Choice of a POD from a key study

The subchronic feeding study on adult rats from BASF (BASF, 1995b), is regarded as the key study for deriving the HBM-GV_{Worker}. The BMD_{10L95} of 6.1 mg/kg bw/d modelled by Bhat et al. (2014) on the incidence of thyroid follicular hypertrophy in F0 rats after subchronic exposure is selected for deriving the HBM-GV_{Worker}. Several limits regarding the BMD modelling by Bhat et al. (2014) were noticed (see above), nonetheless the BMD approach was preferred over the NOAEL/LOAEL approach.

7.2.2 Calculation of HBM-GVs for workers

The method for deriving the HBM-GV_{Worker} is based on calculating the concentrations of both OH- and oxo-MPHP consistent with the extrapolated and uncertainty-accounting human equivalent BMD_{10L95} of 6.1 mg/kg bw/d identified in the study from BASF (1995b).

An AF for intraspecies differences (AF_H) of 5 is applied to the human equivalent BMD_{10L95}. An AF_H of 5 is usually set when workers are the targeted population for which the HBM-GV is derived, in line with ECHA's R8 guidance for deriving DNELs for workers (Apel et al., 2020). The underlying reasoning for not applying an AF_H of 10, as for the general population, is that the population of workers does not include the very young, old, and very ill individuals.

An AF_S of 3 accounting for the study duration (subchronic → chronic) is applied as for the derivation of the RfD by Bhat et al. (2014). According to ECHA, an AF of 2 had to be applied here, but for the sake of harmonisation with the HBM-GV_{GenPop}, the same AF as applied by Bhat et al. (2014) has been taken. Furthermore, an AF of 3 accounting for the uncertainties in the DPHP database is also applied, in line with the justification given by Bhat et al. 2014 that is explained in the section 4.1.1 on the HBM-GV_{GenPop} derivation.

An overall AF of 45 is applied to the POD of 6.1 mg/kg/day to obtain a "TRV-like value" of 0.14 mg/kg bw/day. Input parameters for the calculation are the molecular weights of DPHP and its measured metabolites, the F_{ue} of the measured metabolites after 24h and the daily urine volume adjusted to the body weight. The 24h values for excretion are preferred because a large proportion of OH- and oxo-MPHP is excreted in urine within 24h and the mass conservation equation was established considering an excretion during 24h. DPHP has a molecular weight of 446.7 g/mol; the molecular weights of the metabolites oxo-MPHP (C₁₈H₂₄O₅) and OH-MPHP (C₁₈H₂₆O₅) are 320.4 and 322.4 g/mol, respectively. The F_{ue} (at about 24h) for oxo-MPHP is 0.0795 and for OH-MPHP is 0.0597 (mean values, see chapter 2.1.2). The daily urine volume adjusted to the body weight is considered to be 0.02 l/kg bw/d for adults⁹.

⁹ Recent data on the daily urine volume adjusted to the body weight are evaluated at the moment and might change the default value in future

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 34

HBM-GV_{Worker} calculation for the sum of urinary oxo-MPHP and OH-MPHP, based on body weight-related urine excretion rate adjustment (0.02 l/kg bw/d for adults)

$$= \frac{TRV\text{-like value} \times [(MW_{\text{oxo-MPHP}} \times F_{ue\text{ oxo-MPHP}}) + (MW_{\text{OH-MPHP}} \times F_{ue\text{ OH-MPHP}})] / MW_{\text{DPHP}}}{\text{Amount daily volume of urine (L/kg bw/d)}}$$

$$= \frac{0.14 \times [(320.4 \times 0.0795) + (322.4 \times 0.0597)] / 446.7}{0.02}$$

HBM-GV_{Worker} = 0.7 mg/l for urinary oxo-MPHP and OH-MPHP concentrations

MW = molecular weight; *F_{ue}* = factor for metabolic conversion

For information, alternative HBM-GVs_{Worker} were also calculated for single biomarker of exposure, i.e. for oxo-MPHP or OH-MPHP (Table 8).

Table 8: HBM-GVs_{Worker} referring to the sum of oxo-MPHP and OH-MPHP and to the respective single metabolites

Measured biomarker	HBM-GV _{worker} for adults [mg/l]
oxo-MPHP and OH-MPHP	0.7
oxo-MPHP	0.4
OH-MPHP	0.3

The oxidative metabolites oxo- and OH-MPHP having excretion half-lives ranging between 5.2-8.7h, accumulation during the working week is likely in case of 8h exposure per day. Therefore, sampling of the urine at the end of the week is recommended, as well as at the end of the working shift, as this would be the peak of exposure (assuming the worker is exposed to the same amount for the full shift).

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 35

8 Level of confidence attributed to the derived HBM-GVs

As mentioned in the HBM4EU concept paper to derive HBM-GVs, it is suggested to attribute a level of confidence (low, medium or high) to each calculated HBM-GV. The level of confidence should reflect the uncertainties identified during the elaboration of the value and could constitute a good incentive to revise later on values with estimated 'lower' level of confidence.

However, it should be specified that the levels of confidence proposed in this document are not determined according to an established recognised methodology, but rather rely on expert judgment regarding the reliability of the data and the calculation method used to derive the HBM-GV values.

The levels of confidence attributed to the HBM-GV_{GenPop} are set to '**low**'. Please, refer to the n°2 note of the factsheet presented in section 7.1 for explanation on this level of confidence appreciation.

The level of confidence attributed to the HBM-GV_{Worker} is set to '**low**'. Please, refer to the n° 2 note of the factsheet presented in section 7.2 for explanation on this level of confidence appreciation.

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 36

9 Discussion

For evaluating exposure to DPHP in the general population it is recommended to determine the sum of the concentrations of the DPHP metabolites oxo-MPHP and OH-MPHP in urine and to compare the analytical results with the HBM-GVs for the general population derived here above: 0.36 mg/l for children and 0.54 mg/l for adults.

The HBM-GV_{GenPop} derived here is lower than the German HBM-I values (Kommission Human-Biomonitoring, 2015; Apel et al., 2017), which is substantiated by inclusion of more current data on metabolite's excretion, as well as by focussing on a reference dose established from a BMDL₁₀ of a two-generation study instead on a NOAEL from a subchronic feeding study.

For assessing DPHP exposure in the occupational field, measurement of the sum of both biomarkers of exposure oxo-MPHP and OH-MPHP should be performed at the end of the workshift and of the working week, for comparison of the concentration to the suggested HBM-GV_{worker} of 0.7 mg/L.

As mentioned previously in this report, some limits regarding the BMDL modelling as performed by Bhat et al. (2014) were noticed (see section 2.2.3), especially regarding the constraint applied to the model for fitting the data, which is against current EFSA recommendations. Modelling BMDs according to current EFSA recommendations would require further work.

The derivation of the HBM-GVs for the general population, as well as for workers, is based on the conversion of an adjusted external human equivalent dose to internal metabolite doses. It has to be kept in mind that the toxicokinetic data on urinary excretion fractions for the metabolites come solely from two human studies of controlled exposure with only one dose administered to 5 or 6 adult volunteers. The extent of variability among individuals in the studies was moderate, however, the range of variability occurring in the general population is not known and the possible variability due to age, sex, level of exposure and other influencing factors has not been examined until now. Thus, potential under- or over-estimations by taking a default F_{ue} cannot be excluded.

Taking these uncertainties together and considering the likely variations in measured urinary concentrations resulting from the short biological half-lives of the metabolites, the HBM-GVs for DPHP (relating to its oxidised metabolites) have their limitations on the individual level and should be interpreted carefully in terms of the likelihood of an adverse health effect in an individual case. The derived HBM-GV_{GenPop} are most appropriate as a screening tool to evaluate population-based biomonitoring data in the context of possibly necessary risk management on a regulatory level. In this connection it should also be thought about the fact that HBM-GV_{GenPop} are expected to be protective over a lifetime of exposure. Nevertheless, exceedance should serve as a hint to avoid exposure sources, thus allowing for risk minimisation.

Considering the relative high uncertainties related to the HBM-GV_{worker} derivation, it is not recommended to use it for the effective control of the health risks related to DPHP in the practice of occupational health. The EU reference value for workers that will be established for DPHP under T10.4 of HBM4EU should be rather used to assess whether the exposure at the workplace is adequately controlled or not.

It should be taken into account that due to the short half-life of excretion of the mono-ester metabolites more reliable evaluations of the extent of exposure could be made based on 24h urine collections rather than spot samples. Moreover, a current publication by Casas et al. (2018) quantifying the variability of biomarker measurements of many non-persistent chemicals during several time windows shows that for many of these compounds a few dozen samples are required to accurately assess exposure over periods encompassing several trimesters or months. Exposure misclassification in epidemiological studies is expected to be high.

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 37

DPHP is included in the ECHA Community Rolling Action Plan (CoRAP) and will be evaluated in 2019 on the following grounds: high aggregated tonnage (> 1000 tons per annum), wide dispersive use, exposure of sensitive populations, potential endocrine disruptor. The resulting evaluation should be used for a future examination of the values proposed here.

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 38

10 Factsheets

10.1 Factsheet on the HBM-GV for the general population

Compound: DPHP (Di(2-propylheptyl)phthalate)			Factsheet General population
Parameter	Note	Value / descriptor	Comments
HBM-GV_{GenPop} and Status			
HBM-GV _{GenPop}	1	oxo-MPHP & OH-MPHP in urine: Children: 0.33 mg/l Adults: 0.50 mg/l	
Level of confidence	2	Low	See note for explanation
HBM-GV _{GenPop} status	3	Provisional	See note for explanation
HBM-HBGV _{GenPop} year of issue	4	2019	
General Information			
CLP-INDEX-Nr.	5	None	
EC-Nr.	6	258-469-4	
CAS-No.	7	53306-54-0	
Harmonised CLP classification	8	None	
Molar mass	9	446.7 g/mol	
Biomarker(s)			
Identification	10	Oxo-MPHP, OH-MPHP	
Molar mass of biomarker(s)	11	Oxo-MPHP: 320,4 g/mol OH-MPHP: 322,4 g/mol	
Toxicokinetic data			
Key studies for TK data, authors, year	12	Leng et al., 2014 and Klein et al., 2018	
Type of study	13	Human study	
Route of exposure	14	Oral	
Half-life of biomarker(s) (second phase)	15	Urinary metabolite T1/2 (h)* OH-MPHP 6.87/ 5.2 oxo-MPHP 6.51/ 5.4	
Factor for metabolic conversion (F _{ue}) 24 h	16	Oxo-MPHP: 0.0795 (7.95%) OH-MPHP: 0.0597 (5.97%)	
Derivation method and calculation			
Derivation method	17	Based on a reference dose derived from an animal study	
Key study, Author(s), Year	18	Bhat et al., 2014; BASF, 2009b	
Species	18	Wistar rats	
Route/type of study	18	Oral	
Exposure duration	18	Two-generation	
Critical endpoint	18	Effects on thyroid gland	
POD value	18	10 mg/kg bw/d	Human equivalent BMDL ₁₀
Assessment factors	19	3 · 3 · 10	Adjustment to study length, data quality, intraspecies

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 39

			differences
RfD	20	0.1 mg/kg bw/d	
HBM-GV_{GenPop}			
Calculated HBM-GV_{GenPop}	21	Children: 0.33 mg/l Adults: 0.50 mg/l	

Explanation of notes:

- 1) HBM-GV_{GenPop}: numerical value of the HBM-GV_{GenPop} value in mg/l
- 2) Level of confidence of the HBM-GV_{GenPop}: reflects the reliability of the proposed HBM-GV. The level of confidence takes into account the various uncertainties underlying the derivation of the HBM-GV (e.g. reliability of the key study used to derivate the TRV, uncertainties related to the calculation of the TRV, to toxicokinetic data on the substance of interest, to the extrapolations and calculation of the final HBM-GV). Attribution of a global level of confidence for the proposed DPHP HBM-GV_{GenPop} is suggested, considering:
 - the nature and quality of the DPHP toxicological and epidemiological data: the database on DPHP is based solely on animal studies. Repeated-dose toxicity studies mainly concern rat exposed by oral route. Chronic or carcinogenicity studies were not identified in the scientific literature. The determination of the factor for metabolic conversion (F_{ue}) is based on two studies with 5 respectively 6 male volunteers. Data gaps exist to compare adults and children: data are missing to ensure that metabolism and sensitivity are similar in adults and children → **low**
 - the critical endpoint and mode of action: the evidence of the DPHP effects on thyroid gland and pituitary gland is based on two animal studies (subchronic and 2-generation). These data do not include mechanistic explanation. Investigations on the thyroid are very limited. The evidenced effect is not substantiated by hormonal data. Thus, the data do not allow to draw conclusions with respect to the mechanism of DPHP on thyroid signalling. No evidence for these effects in humans is available from the scientific literature. No conclusions about the transposability of these effects to humans can be taken out from available studies on DPHP without complementary measurements. → **low**
 - the selected key study for identification of the BMDL₁₀: unpublished industrial study from BASF realised on rats (BASF, 200b). The study was reported to be conducted according to OECD guideline 416 (Two-generation Reproduction Toxicity Study). The best case for deriving an HBM-GV would have been availability of human data. → **medium**
 - the selected POD: BMDL₁₀ chosen as POD from Bhat et al. (2014), no use of the updated BMDS software nor according to the recommendations of the EFSA guidelines on BMD modelling → **medium**
 - regarding the extrapolations for the RfD calculation: using default AFs according to intra individual variability (AF_H), time and data quality → **low**

Altogether the global level of confidence for the DPHP HBM-GVs in the general population is set to '**low**'.
- 3) HBM-GV_{GenPop} status: the status value is fixed to 'provisional', thereby reflecting that this value could be revised later on in the project, if uncertainties underlying the data could be reduced. For example, the uncertainties of the TK data could be reduced by means of a validated PBPK model for DPHP. A higher level of confidence attributed to the value would lead to a 'confirmed' value status.
- 4) HBM-GV_{GenPop} year of issue: year of setting the HBM-GV_{GenPop} in the HBM4EU workframe
- 5) CLP Number: according to Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 on classification, labelling and packaging (CLP) of substances and mixtures, implementing the globally harmonised system of chemical classification or GHS http://guidance.echa.europa.eu/docs/guidance_document/clp_introduutory_en.pdf
- 6) EC Number: under European Inventory of Existing Commercial chemical Substances (EINECS), ELINCS (European List of Notified Chemical Substances) in support of Directive 92/32/EEC, the 7th amendment to Directive

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 40

67/548/EEC, NLP (No-Longer Polymers), see: ESIS: European chemical Substances Information System:
https://web.archive.org/web/20131106181548if_/http://esis.jrc.ec.europa.eu/

- 7) CAS Number: collection of disclosed chemical compound information by Chemical Abstracts Service. Almost all molecule databases can be searched by CAS Registry Number.
- 8) Harmonised CLP classification: CLP classification including CMR and other health relevant effects. In the case that classification is not harmonised, this should be stated. For self-classifications by industry the ECHA- CLP inventory can be searched at: <http://echa.europa.eu/web/guest/information-on-chemicals/cl-inventory-database>
- 9) Molar mass: mass of DPHP per amount of this substance expressed in g/mol
- 10) Biomarker(s) identification: the biomarkers identified as relevant for assessing the exposure to DPHP are oxidation products of the alkyl side chain of the monoester (Gries et al., 2012; Leng et al., 2014). The main metabolites retrieved in urine are oxo-MPHP and OH-MPHP. Consequentially, those 2 metabolites are selected for the HBM-GV derivation.
- 11) Molar mass of the biomarker(s): mass of the selected biomarkers (expressed in g/mol)
- 12) Study for TK data, Authors, Year: Leng et al. (2014) examined the metabolism of DPHP in humans. The metabolites and the elimination kinetics were determined by means of chromatographic-mass spectrometric methods (LC-MS/MS). Five male volunteers 18 to 65 years of age received a single dose of about 50 mg of DPHP with their breakfast. Stable-isotope labelled DPHP-d4 was used to exclude possible background exposures. Urine samples were collected before administration of the DPHP and over a 48h period thereafter.

Klein et al. (2018) published a study involving 6 healthy male volunteers (aged between 30 and 64 years) who ingested a single ring-deuterated DPHP(-d4) dose (0,7 mg/kg bw) after breakfast. DPHP and selected metabolites were monitored in blood and urine. Blood samples were collected at intervals up to 24 h and urine samples at intervals up to 46 h. LC-MS/MS was used for the analysis of samples.
- 13) Type of study: human oral study
- 14) Route of exposure: oral single administration of 50 mg DPHP
- 15) Half-life of biomarker: estimated elimination half-lives for the DPHP biomarkers of exposure
- 16) Factor for metabolic conversion (F_{ue}): fractional urinary excretion ratios of biomarkers relative to the oral dose of DPHP taken up, at 24. The 24 h values for excretion are preferred because a large proportion of OH- and oxo-MPHP is excreted in urine within 24 h and the mass conservation equation was established considering an excretion during 24 h.
- 17) Derivation method: the existing database on DPHP does not allow for the derivation of health-based guidance values from human data, based on internal concentration and health effects relationship. Therefore, a derivation method based on a RfD established from an animal study is used.
- 18) POD: the BASF two-generation feeding study (BASF, 2009b), based on which a human equivalent BMDL₁₀ of 10 mg/kg bw/d was modelled by Bhat et al. 2014 is regarded as the pivotal study for deriving the HBM-GV_{GenPop}. The critical effects considered assessment-relevant are the effects on the thyroid.
- 19) Assessment factors: extrapolation to a concentration of DPHP below which – according to the actual knowledge on the substance – there is negligible risk for adverse human health effects anticipated needs application of assessment factors (3 for the study duration (subchronic → chronic), 3 for data quality, 10 for intraspecies variability)
- 20) RfD: application of a total assessment factor of 100 to the human equivalent BMDL₁₀ leads to a RfD of 0.1 mg/kg bw/d
- 21) HBM-GVs: Ideally, the HBM-GVs should refer to a complete 24-hour urine sample, stating the quantity of a substance in µg/d, especially if the monitored substance has a short half-life of excretion. For reasons of

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 41

simplification, in accordance with the approach described in the concept paper, the excretion is referred to a body weight-related urine excretion of 30 ml/kg bw/d for children and 20 ml/kg bw/d for the remaining subgroups of the population.

The resulting HBM-GV_{GenPop} for the sum of the concentrations of oxo-MPHP & OH-MPHP are as follows:

Children: 0.33 mg/l oxo-MPHP & OH-MPHP

Adults including adolescents: 0.50 mg/l oxo-MPHP & OH-MPHP

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 42

10.2 Factsheet on the HBM-GV for workers

Compound	DPHP Di(2-propylheptyl)phthalate		Factsheet Occupational field
Parameter	Note	Value / descriptor	Comments
HBM-GV_{Worker} and Status			
HBM-GV _{Worker}	1	Urinary [oxo- & OH-MPHP] at the end of the work shift, end of the working week: 0.7 mg/l	
Level of confidence	2	Low	See note for explanation
HBM-GV _{Worker} status	3	Provisional	See note for explanation
HBM-GV _{Worker} year of issue	4	2019	
General Information			
CLP-INDEX-Nr.	5	None	
EC-Nr.	6	258-469-4	
CAS-Nr.	7	53306-54-0	
Harmonised CLP classification	8	None	
Molar mass	9	446.7 g/mol	
Biomarker(s)			
Identification	10	Oxo-MPHP, OH-MPHP	
Molar mass of biomarker(s)	11	Oxo-MPHP: 320.4 g/mol OH-MPHP: 322.4 g/mol	
Toxicokinetic data			
Study for TK data, authors, year	12	Leng et al., 2014 and Klein et al., 2018	
Type of study	13	Human study	
Route of exposure	14	Oral	
Half-life of selected biomarker(s)	15	urinary OH-MPHP 6.87h / 5.2h urinary oxo-MPHP 6.51h / 5.4h	Data from Leng et al. (2014) and Klein et al. (2018)
Factor for metabolic conversion (F _{ue}) (24h)	16	For oxo-MPHP: 0.0795 (7.95%) For OH-MPHP: 0.0597 (5.97%)	Calculated mean F _{ue} based on the F _{ue} retrieved from the Leng et al., 2014 and Klein et al. 2018 studies
Derivation method and calculation			
Derivation method	17	Based on an animal point of departure (POD)	
Key study, Author(s), Year	18	BASF (1995b)	Human equivalent BMD _{10L95} modelled by Bhat et al., 2014 on the results from the BASF (1995b) study
Species	18	Wistar rats (six weeks old at the start of the study)	
Route of study	18	Oral	
Exposure duration	18	Sub-chronic (13 weeks)	
Critical endpoint	18	Thyroid follicular cell hypertrophy	
POD value	18	Human equivalent BMD _{10L95} of 6.1 mg/kg bw/d	

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 43

Adjustments (AFs)	19	Global AF of 45 5 x 3 x 3	Adjustment to study length, data quality, intraspecies differences AF _H = 5 (workers) AF _S = 3 (subchronic to chronic study duration adjustment) AF database = 3
TRV-like value	20	0.14 mg/kg bw/d	
HBM-GV_{Worker}			
Calculated HBM-GV_{Worker}	21	Urinary [oxo- & OH-MPHP] at the end of the working week and end of the work shift: 0.7 mg/l	

Explanation of notes:

- 1) HBM-GV_{worker}: numerical value of the HBM-GV_{worker} value in mg/l
- 2) Level of confidence of the HBM-GV_{Worker}: reflects the reliability of the proposed HBM-GV. The level of confidence takes into account the various uncertainties underlying the derivation of the HBM-GV (e.g. reliability of the key study used to derivate the TRV, uncertainties related to the calculation of TRV, to toxicokinetic data on the substance of interest, to the extrapolations and calculation of the final HBM-GV). Attribution of a global level of confidence for the proposed DPHP HBM-GV_{Worker} is suggested, considering:
 - the nature and quality of the DPHP toxicological and epidemiological data: the database on DPHP is based solely on animal studies. Repeated-dose toxicity studies mainly concern rats exposed by oral route. Chronic or carcinogenicity studies were not identified in the scientific literature. The determination of the factor for metabolic conversion (F_{ue}) is based on two studies with 5 respectively 6 male volunteers (see note 12). A made assumption is that the volunteers have a steady-state intake of DPHP. It is also assumed that the rate of excretion based on the total 24h urinary excretion following an acute exposure will reflect the steady-state rate of excretion under steady-state intake → **low**
 - the critical endpoint and mode of action: the evidence of the DPHP effects on the thyroid gland is based on two animal studies (subchronic and 2-generation). These data do not include mechanistic explanation and investigations on the thyroid are very limited. The evidenced effect is not substantiated by hormonal data. Thus, the data do not allow to draw conclusions with respect to the mechanism of DPHP on thyroid signalling. No evidence for these effects in humans is available from the scientific literature. No conclusions about the transposability of these effects to humans can be taken out from available studies on DPHP without complementary measurements. → **low**
 - the selected key study for identification of the POD: unpublished industrial study from BASF realised on rats. The study is reported to be conducted according to OECD guideline 408 (Repeated Dose 90-Day Oral Toxicity in Rodents). The best case for deriving an HBM-GV for workers would have been availability of field studies with evidence of internal dose-effect relationship. The second-best case would have been an inhalation animal study. → **medium**
 - the selected POD: BMDL₁₀ was chosen as POD from Bhat et al. (2014). The human equivalent BMD_{10L95} modelled by Bhat et al. (2014) does not comply with current EFSA recommendations on BMD modelling. In addition, The BMD is associated with a wide confidence interval, reflecting a significant uncertainty underlying the value. → **medium**
 - the extrapolations for the TRV-like value: the human equivalent BMDL selected as POD is based on an allometric scaling assumption, whereas functional aspects of the HPT axis in the rat or human may not scale across species in a simple allometric manner; default AFs have been used: intra individual variability (AF_H of 5 for workers), study duration adjustment with an AF of 3 (subchronic -> chronic) and an additional AF of 3 for reasons of incomplete database (lack of carcinogenicity and second-species systemic and developmental toxicity data) → **low**

Altogether the global level of confidence for the DPHP HBM-GV for workers is set to '**low**'.

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 44

- 3) HBM-GV_{worker} status: the status value is fixed to 'provisional', thereby reflecting that this value could be revised later on in the project, if uncertainties underlying the data could be reduced. For example, the uncertainties of the TK data could be reduced by means of a validated PBPK model for DPHP. A higher level of confidence attributed to the value would lead to a 'confirmed' value status.
- 4) HBM-GV_{worker} year of issue: year of setting the HBM-GV_{worker} in the HBM4EU workframe
- 5) CLP Number: according to Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 on classification, labelling and packaging (CLP) of substances and mixtures, implementing the globally harmonised system of chemical classification or GHS
http://guidance.echa.europa.eu/docs/guidance_document/clp_introduutory_en.pdf
- 6) EC Number: under European Inventory of Existing Commercial chemical Substances (EINECS), ELINCS (European List of Notified Chemical Substances) in support of Directive 92/32/EEC, the 7th amendment to Directive 67/548/EEC, NLP (No-Longer Polymers), see: ESIS: European chemical Substances Information System:
https://web.archive.org/web/20131106181548if_/http://esis.jrc.ec.europa.eu/
- 7) CAS Number: collection of disclosed chemical compound information by Chemical Abstracts Service. Almost all molecule databases can be searched by CAS Registry Number.
- 8) Harmonised CLP classification: CLP classification including CMR and other health relevant effects. In the case that classification is not harmonised, this should be stated. For self-classifications by industry the ECHA- CLP inventory can be searched at: <http://echa.europa.eu/web/guest/information-on-chemicals/cl-inventory-database>
- 9) Molar mass: mass of DPHP per amount of this substance expressed in g/mol
- 10) Biomarker(s) identification: biomarkers identified as valid for a diagnosis of exposure to DPHP include oxidation products of the alkyl side chain of the monoester (Gries et al., 2012; Leng et al., 2014). The main metabolites found were oxo-MPHP and OH-MPHP. Consequentially, those 2 metabolites should be taken into consideration for the HBM-GV derivation.
- 11) Molar mass of the biomarker(s): mass of the selected biomarkers (expressed in g/mol)
- 12) Study for TK data, Authors, Year: Leng et al., (2014) examined the metabolism of DPHP in humans. The metabolites and the elimination kinetics were determined by means of chromatographic-mass spectrometric methods (LC-MS/MS). Five male volunteers, aged 18 to 65 years received a single dose of about 50 mg of DPHP with their breakfast. Stable-isotope labelled DPHP-d4 was used to exclude possible background exposures. Urine samples were collected before administration of the DPHP and over a 48h period thereafter.

Klein et al. (2018) published a study involving 6 healthy male volunteers (aged between 30 and 64 years) who ingested a single ring-deuterated DPHP(-d4) dose (0,7 mg/kg bw) after breakfast. DPHP and selected metabolites were monitored in blood and urine. Blood samples were collected at intervals up to 24 h and urine samples at intervals up to 46 h. LC-MS/MS was used for the analysis of samples.
- 13) Type of study: human study
- 14) Route of exposure: oral single administration of about 50 mg DPHP
- 15) Half-life of biomarker: estimated elimination half-lives for the DPHP metabolites
- 16) Factor for metabolic conversion (F_{ue}): fractional urinary excretion ratios of biomarkers relative to the oral dose of DPHP taken up (at about 24 h). The 24 h values for excretion are preferred because a large proportion of OH- and oxo-MPHP is excreted in urine within 24 h and the mass conservation equation was established considering an excretion during 24 h
- 17) Derivation method: the existing database on DPHP does not allow for the derivation of health-based guidance values from human data, based on internal concentrations and health effects relationship. No evidence of a relationship

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 45

between atmospheric concentration of DPHP and urinary concentration of oxo- and OH-MPHP is also available. Therefore, a derivation method based on a POD established from an animal study is used.

- 18) POD: the BASF oral subchronic study (BASF, 1995b) is considered as the key study for deriving the HBM-GV_{Worker}. The effects selected as critical are the effects on the thyroid gland. Based on the results of this key study, the human equivalent BMD_{10L95} of 6.1 mg/kg bw/d modelled by Bhat et al. (2014) was chosen as POD. Limits regarding the BMD modelling as performed by Bhat et al. (2014) are underlined, but using the BMD method appears to be a more conservative approach than selecting the NOAEL of 39 mg/kg bw/d for the thyroid effects observed at higher doses.
- 19) Assessment factors: extrapolation to a concentration of DPHP below which – according to the actual knowledge on the substance – there is negligible risk for adverse human health effects anticipated needs application of assessment factors (an AF of 5 for the intraspecies variability among the working population, an AF of 3 for the study duration (subchronic → chronic) and an additional AF of 3 justified by the incomplete database on DPHP (lack of carcinogenicity and second-species systemic and developmental toxicity data). The AF of 3 for taking into account the study duration adjustment does not follow ECHA's recommendation (AF of 2 recommended). Nonetheless, it was decided to select this AF of 3 in order to be consistent with the RfD setting by Bhat et al. (2014), which constitutes the basis for the HBM-GV_{GenPop} derivation.
- 20) TRV-like value: application of a total assessment factor of 45 to the human equivalent BMD_{10L95} of 6.1 mg/kg bw/d leads to a TRV-like value of 0.14 mg/kg bw/d.
- 21) HBM-GV_{Worker}: the resulting HBM-GV for the sum of urinary oxo- and OH-MPHP calculated on the basis of a mass balance equation with a daily body weight-related excretion for adults of 20 ml/kg bw is 0.7 mg/L. Sampling should be performed at the end of working shift and working week.

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 46

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D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 47

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Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 48

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WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 49

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D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
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WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 51

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WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 52

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D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 53

Part II

Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GVs) for DnBP (Di-n-Butylphthalate, CAS no. 84-74-2) referring to the general population and to workers

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 54

Table of contents

1	Authors and Acknowledgements	56
2	Glossary.....	57
3	Introduction	59
4	General information on DnBP	60
4.1	Identification of the substance	60
4.2	Physico-chemical properties	60
4.3	Uses.....	61
4.4	EU Harmonised Classification and Labelling	61
4.5	EU regulations.....	61
4.6	Human exposure	64
4.6.1	General population	64
4.6.2	Occupationally exposed adults	64
5	General toxicological profile	65
5.1	Toxicokinetics and metabolism	65
5.2	Toxicity	66
5.2.1	Human toxicity studies.....	67
5.2.2	Animal studies	70
6	Selected biomarker(s) for the HBM-GV proposal and analytical method	72
6.1	Choice of biomarkers of exposure	72
6.2	Analytical method	72
7	Choice of HBM-GVs derivation method.....	73
7.1	Derivation of HBM-GVs for the general population	73
7.1.1	Method for the HBM-GV _{GenPop} derivation	73
7.1.2	Review of relevant toxicity reference values and selection of a TRV	73
7.1.2.1	EFSA	74
7.1.2.2	ECHA	74
7.1.2.3	CHAP	74
7.1.2.4	Selection of a TRV	74
7.1.3	Calculation of the HBM-GV _{GenPop}	75
7.2	Derivation of a HBM-GV _{Worker} for the occupational population.....	75
7.2.1	Method for the HBM-GV _{Worker} derivation	75
7.2.2	Choice of a POD value from a key study	76
7.2.3	Calculation of the HBM-GV _{Worker}	76
8	Level of confidence attributed to the derived HBM-GVs	78

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 55

9	Discussion	79
10	Factsheets	80
10.1	Factsheet on the HBM-GV for the general population.....	80
10.2	Factsheet on the HBM-GV for workers	84
11	References	88
12	Annex.....	96

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 56

1 Authors and acknowledgements

Authors

Petra Apel, UBA, Germany

Eva Ougier, ANSES, France

Rosa Lange, UBA, Germany

Christophe Rousselle, ANSES, France

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Entity	Contributing expert
NH Austria	Maria Uhl (EAA)
NH Belgium	Jos Bessems (VITO)
NH Belgium	Greet Schoeters (VITO)
NH France	Claude Viau (Chair of the ANSES BEI Working Group)
NH Germany	HBM Commission
NH Netherlands	Marcel Mengelers (RIVM)
NH Netherlands	Wieneke, Bil (RIVM)
NH Netherlands	Marjolijn Woutersen (RIVM)
NH Portugal	Teresa Borges (DGS)
NH Portugal	Susana Viegas (ESTeSL)
NH Spain	Isabel Maya Rubio (Mutua Universal -Spain)
NH Spain	Maribel Casas (ISGLOBAL)
NH Switzerland	Rex Filtzgerald (SCAHT)
NH Switzerland	Nancy Hopf (IST)
NH United Kingdom	Dorothy Ubong

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 57

2 Glossary

AF	Assessment factor
AGD	Anogenital distance
BBzP	Benzyl butyl <i>phthalate</i>
CHAP	Chronic Hazard Advisory Panel on Phthalates and Phthalate Alternatives
CLP	Classification, Labelling and Packaging
DnBP	Di-n-butyl phthalate
DEHP	Bis(2-ethylhexyl) <i>phthalate</i>
DFI	DNA fragmentation index
DiBP	Diisobutyl phthalate
DNEL	Derived No-Effect level
DPP	Dipentyl phthalate
ECHA	European Chemicals Agency
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
FCM	Food Contact Material
FT	Free testosterone
GD	Gestational day
GM	Geometric mean
HED	Human equivalent dose
HPLC-MS/MS	High-performance liquid chromatography with tandem mass spectrometry
IQR	Interquartile Range Increase
MADL	Maximum Allowable Dose Level
MnBP	Mono-n-butyl phthalate
MCPP	Mono-3-carboxypropyl phthalate
MEHP	Mono-(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate
MEHH	Mono(2-ethyl-5-hydroxyhexyl) phthalate
MEOHP	Mono(2-ethyl-5-oxohexyl) phthalate
MEP	Monoethyl phthalate
MHBP	Mono-3-hydroxy-n-butyl phthalate
N(L)OAEL	No (Lowest) Observed Adverse Effect Level
OEL	Occupational Exposure Limit
PND	Postnatal day
POD	Point of departure
PVA	Polyvinyl alcohol

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 58

PVC	Polyvinyl chloride
Qms	Quantum Maximum
RAC	Risk Assessment Committee
SML	Specific Migration Limits
SVHC	Substance of very high concern
TDI	Tolerable daily intake
TDS	Testicular dysgenesis syndrome
TRV	Toxicity reference value

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 59

3 Introduction

Within the framework of task 5.2 of HBM4EU, Human Biomonitoring guidance values (HBM-GVs) are derived for HBM4EU priority substances. The methodology applied to derive these values is described in the concept paper previously released in the HBM4EU task 5.2 workframe (Apel et al., 2020). For the time being, HBM-GVs to be derived shall be agreed on at HBM4EU project level, further adoption of derived HBM-GVs at EU level has to be discussed among partners and the EU Commission.

In the current report, general population HBM-GVs (HBM-GV_{GenPop}) and an occupational HBM-GV (HBM-GV_{Worker}) are derived and discussed for di-n-butyl phthalate (DnBP), based on its anti-androgenic effects.

The state of epidemiological knowledge based on human exposure to DnBP on whether and how it might cause human health effects is not sufficient to derive HBM-GVs directly based on human data, be it for the general population or for workers. Thus, the derivation of HBM-GVs for the general population and for workers relies on an animal point of departure (POD) value identified from a key toxicity study, as described in the HBM4EU concept document.

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 60

4 General information on DnBP

4.1 Identification of the substance

Name	Di-n-butyl phthalate (DnBP)
IUPAC Name	Dibutyl benzene-1, 2-dicarboxylate
CAS Number	84-74-2
EC Number	201-557-4
Molecular weight	278.35 g/mol
Molecular formula	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ O ₄
Structural formula	<p>Figure 3: Structural formula of DnBP (source: PubChem https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov)</p>

4.2 Physico-chemical properties

DnBP is a colourless or very faintly yellow oily liquid at room temperature. The vapor pressure is $9.7 \pm 3.3 \times 10^{-3}$ Pa at 25°C, the water solubility is 10 mg/l at 20°C and the octanol-water partition coefficient (log K_{ow}) is 4.57 (EU RAR, 2004; ECHA, 2014). Further physico-chemical properties are summarised in Table 1.

Table 9: Physico-chemical data on di-n-butyl phthalate (DnBP)

Molecular formula	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ O ₄
Molar mass	278.348 g/mol
State at room temperature	Colourless to faint-yellow oily liquid
Melting point	-69°C
Boiling point	340°C at 1 013 hPa
Relative density	1.049 g/cm ³ at 20°C*
Vapor pressure	$9.7 \pm 3.3 \times 10^{-3}$ Pa at 25°C
Partition coefficient log K _{ow}	4.57 at 20°C
Water solubility	10 mg/l at 20°C

*<https://www.echa.europa.eu/web/guest/registration-dossier/-/registered-dossier/14862/4/5>

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 61

4.3 Uses

DnBP is used as a plasticiser for polyvinyl chloride (PVC), polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) and rubber as well as a solvent and a fixative in paints.

DnBP is essentially used for its viscosity reducing properties and compatibility with non-PVC mixtures (lacquers, printing inks, sealants, adhesives) or as processing aid for PVC (plasticisers, compounds) (ECHA, 2013; SCOEL, 2017).

Its soft PVC uses include flooring, packaging material, shoes, home furnishing, and clothing (ECPI 2015; ECHA 2016).

DnBP is also used in enteric-coated pharmaceuticals. However, from June 2018, medicines should only exceptionally contain DnBP (EMA, 2014)¹⁰.

According to ECHA's information¹¹, DnBP is currently manufactured and/or imported in the EU Economic Area in 1 000 - 10 000 tons per year.

4.4 EU Harmonised Classification and Labelling

According to the Classification, Labelling and Packaging (CLP) Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008, DnBP may damage the unborn child and is suspected of damaging fertility (Hazard statement code H360Df). It is classified as toxic for reproduction, cat. 1B.

International Chemical Identification	EC. no	CAS no.	Classification		Labelling	
			Hazard Class & Category Code(s)	Hazard statement code(s)	Pictogram Signal Word Code(s)	Hazard statement code(s)
Di-n-butyl phthalate (DnBP)	201-557-4	84-74-2	Repr.1B Aquatic Acute 1	H360Df H400	GHS09 GHS08 Dgr	H360Df H400

4.5 EU regulations

Since 21st of February 2015, DnBP has been subject to the REACH authorisation process, being identified as Substance of Very High Concern (SVHC) for its reprotoxic properties. In July 2017 then, DnBP was identified as SVHC due to its endocrine disrupting (ED) properties for human health, in accordance with Article 57(f) of REACH (ECHA, 2017).

Also in 2017, EU member states voted unanimously in favour of a proposal to amend Annex XVII to Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council concerning the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH) and to further restrict the phthalates DEHP, DnBP, BBzP and DiBP to a concentration equal to or below 0.1% by weight individually or in any combination in any plasticised material in articles used by consumers or those used in indoor areas. The proposal was approved at the REACH Committee meeting on 11 July 2018. It takes into account the cumulative effects and combined exposure to the four phthalates from different articles¹². After being examined by the EU Parliament and the Council of

¹⁰ Veterinary medicines seem not to be covered and potentially may contribute to human exposure via the food chain (ECHA, 2016)

¹¹ <https://echa.europa.eu/fr/substance-information/-/substanceinfo/100.001.416>

¹² <https://chemicalwatch.com/68660/member-states-back-eu-phthalates-restriction-proposal>

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 62

Ministers, the EU Commission adopted the decision to amend the REACH regulation and to restrict the use of the phthalates DEHP, BBzP, DnBP and DiBP in consumer products on the EU market. The restriction (COMMISSION REGULATION (EU) 2018/2005 of 17 December 2018) is published in the EU Official Journal¹³ and will come into effect as of June 2020.

Based on the 2005 *European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) safety assessment of DnBP (and of several other phthalates)*, the EU Commission transformed during their risk-management procedure the tolerable daily intake (TDI) of DnBP established by EFSA into a legislative limit, also taking other sources of exposure in consideration (EU Commission 2007).

Since 2007, the use of DnBP has not been permitted in materials intended to come into contact with food (Directive 2007/19/EC). In some cases, however, phthalates used in food contact materials are regulated by compositional limits as Quantum Maximum (Qms) and/or Specific Migration Limits (SML). Table 2 summarises the legislative limits for DnBP in the plastics regulation EU 10/2011. DnBP used in Food Contact Materials (FCMs) is thereby regulated by a SML of 0.3 mg/kg food simulant (Petersen & Jensen, 2010).

Table 10: Legislative limits for DnBP in the plastics regulation (EU 10/2011) (Jensen & Petersen, 2015)

Substance	SML (mg/kg food simulant)	Qm (% in the plastic)	Parameter to control in single use FCM			Parameter to control in repeated use FCM		
			Fatty food	Infant food	Non-fatty food	Fatty food	Infant food	Non-fatty food
DnBP	0.3	0.05	Qm			Qm	SML	

SML: Specific Migration Limit; Qm: Quantum Maximum; FCM: Food Contact Material

In 2014, a joint Nordic control campaign was performed about the quality of Declarations of Compliance for Food Contact Materials, including analytical control of phthalates, including DnBP. The investigation focused on drinking equipment sold from a Norwegian retail shop. It appeared that all the samples of drinking equipment showed non-compliance with the legislative limits for phthalates in plastics for food contact. Only some single items from the inhomogeneous batches of samples were compliant (with respect to phthalates) (Jensen et al., 2015).

In July 2017, EFSA received a mandate from the EU Commission to update its 2005 opinions on the safety assessment of three phthalates DnBP, BBzP and DEHP currently authorised for use in plastic FCM. The new opinion is scheduled for completion in 2018/2019 and will be used by the EU Commission to help inform their decision-making on these substances¹⁴.

Since 2004, the use of DnBP has not been permitted in cosmetics (Directive 2004/93/EC). The placing on the market of cosmetics containing DnBP is prohibited via EU regulation No 1223/2009¹⁵.

¹³ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32018R2005>

¹⁴ <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/topics/topic/food-contact-materials>

¹⁵ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32009R1223&from=FR>

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 63

Regarding the occupational field, DnBP is regulated under the EU Occupational Safety and Health (OSH) Chemical Agents Directive (CAD) 98/24/EC on the protection of the health and safety of workers from the risks related to chemical agents at work¹⁶.

Also, the EU legislation obliges employers to ensure that the work environment is safe for the reproductive health of the workers, pregnant workers, and offspring. The EU Directive 92/85/EEC requires employers to assess the health and safety risks to pregnant and breastfeeding workers, and if needed, to change working conditions or offer suitable alternative work¹⁷. The prevention or reduction of exposure of workers can be done in several ways in accordance with the widely recognised hierarchy of control, e.g.:

- Eliminating or substituting hazardous chemicals for safe alternatives,
- Improving the work environment by collective protection measures, such as the enclosure of the emitting process, local exhaust ventilation, general ventilation, changing work tasks and habits into safe procedures
- Use of personal protective equipment
- Moving the pregnant worker to another job
- Granting leave to the pregnant worker in accordance with national legislation, if none of the above measures is feasible.

Both the employer and workers should be informed about risk assessment results identified for the workplace in terms of agents harmful to reproductive health and the health of the offspring. Women and men workers should be informed beforehand, for example during the pre-employment medical examination, of any potentially harmful occupational exposures and protective measures to prevent any adverse reproductive effects. Women should be advised to contact health services immediately after becoming pregnant or when planning to become pregnant¹⁸.

¹⁶ <https://osha.europa.eu/en/legislation/directives/75>

¹⁷ <https://osha.europa.eu/en/legislation/directives/10>

¹⁸ https://oshwiki.eu/wiki/Reproductive_effects_caused_by_chemical_and_biological_agents

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 64

4.6 Human exposure

4.6.1 General population

The evaluation of the routes and sources of the EU population exposure to DnBP performed by Wormuth et al. (2006) (via a scenario-based approach) indicates that the principle route of exposure for individuals from the general population is through trace levels in foods (either due to migration from food contact materials containing DnBP or due to its widespread presence as an environmental contaminant).

Exposure via inhalation pathways (indoor air, dust) is also occurring due to its presence e.g. as a result of release from industrial and residential sources (SCOEL, 2017).

Dermal contact with plastics, or other materials containing DnBP can also occur (ECHA, 2009).

4.6.2 Occupationally exposed adults

Workers may be exposed to DnBP during the production of DnBP, in the polymer industry and in the paint and printing industry (SCOEL, 2017).

According to the EU RAR (2004), the production of DnBP usually takes place in closed systems. However, both inhalation and dermal exposure may occur during the production of DnBP. Such exposures may occur from "breathing" of the system at elevated temperatures, during system leaks, filling of road and rail tankers, drumming, cleaning of tanks, during service and maintenance, transfer, and process sampling.

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 65

5 General toxicological profile

5.1 Toxicokinetics and metabolism

According to ECHA's Risk Assessment Committee (RAC), absorption fractions for the calculation of internal doses starting from external doses are 100% for the oral path (experimental animals and humans), 10% for the dermal path (humans, all ages) and 100% for inhalation (humans, all ages) (ECHA, 2012).

DnBP is rapidly absorbed and excreted after oral administration, as was demonstrated in laboratory animals as well as human volunteer's studies (ECHA, 2012).

Information on the quantitative distribution in human organs is not available.

Both in humans and in rodents, the major part of DnBP is hydrolysed to mono-n-butyl phthalate (MnBP) and its corresponding alcohol prior to absorption by the small intestine. Hydrolysis can also occur in liver and kidneys (ECHA, 2012). In human serum, the major part of MnBP is present as glucuronide whereas 25-30 % is present as free MnBP (Silva et al., 2003).

MnBP is mainly excreted in urine in its free or glucuronide-conjugated form (Silva et al., 2007a, Figure 2). According to Seckin et al. (2009), conjugated MnBP accounts for 94% of the urinary total MnBP in humans. Zhu et al. (2016) observed a higher ratio of the free form of MnBP over the total MnBP (free + conjugated) measured in pregnant women, compared to non-pregnant women. The authors are thereby assuming a potentially reduced capacity of phthalates glucuronidation during pregnancy, consistent with that of one animal study, which had shown a decrease in capacity of phthalates glucuronidation during gestation in female rats (Clewell et al., 2008).

MnBP can also be metabolised via oxidation (Clewell et al., 2008), even if this pathway is likely to be less relevant for the metabolism of DnBP than for other phthalates (e.g. DEHP). Oxidation of MnBP occurs primarily through ω and $\omega-1$ sidechain cleavage and leads to mono-3-hydroxy-n-butyl phthalate (MHBP), mono-3-oxo-n-butyl phthalate (MOBP) and mono-3-carboxypropyl phthalate (MCPP). These 3 oxidative metabolites of MnBP have been detected in urine of rats dosed with DnBP (Tanaka et al., 1978; Fennell et al., 2004; Silva et al., 2007a). MnBP, MHBP and MCPP were also detected in human urine (Silva et al., 2007a)

Figure 4: Proposed metabolism of DnBP in rats and humans, according to Silva et al., 2007a

The metabolism of DnBP was investigated in a male human volunteer after a single oral exposure of approximately 60 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ of D⁴-DnBP (about 50 times higher than the typical background adult exposures of 1-5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ a day for DnBP (Wormuth et al., 2006). The majority of the DnBP dose was excreted in the urine in the first 24 hours (92.2 % of DnBP) and <1 % was excreted on day 2 (Koch

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 66

et al., 2012). The simple monoester MnBP was the major metabolite of DnBP detected (84%). Approximately 8 % was excreted as various side chain oxidised metabolites of DnBP. MnBP reached peak concentrations 2-4 hours post exposure and its elimination half-life was 2.6 hours. Oxidised metabolites had a longer elimination half-time of 2.9-6.9 hours.

Anderson et al. (2001) conducted also an experimental study on human volunteers to describe the urinary elimination of metabolites of DnBP following oral administration. ¹³C-labelled DnBP was administered to a group of 8 individuals at a low (255 µg) and a high dose (510 µg). 24-h urine samples were collected on the day of administration, the next day, and on day 6. Assuming that the volunteers had bodyweights of approximately 70 kg, the doses were corresponding to 3.6 and 7.3 µg/kg/day. Excreted DnBP monoester were measured by LC-MS following hydrolysis of conjugates. No labelled DnBP derivative was found in samples collected after the 1st day, confirming the rapid metabolism and elimination of this substance in urine, also confirming that the excretion fraction measured accounted for the full-administrated dose. According to Anderson et al. (2001), the main metabolite MnBP is thus only detectable in the urine within 24 hours after the end of exposure. In this space of 24 hours, 69% as molar excretion fraction of the ingested DnBP (64% and 73% respectively according to the administered doses of 255 and 510 µg) was excreted in the urine as total MnBP (free and conjugated forms).

5.2 Toxicity

Although phthalates (including DnBP) cause a wide range of toxicities, the most sensitive and most extensively studied is male developmental toxicity in the rat (CHAP, 2014). Specifically, exposing pregnant dams to certain phthalates¹⁹ causes a syndrome indicative of androgen deficiency, referred to as the “phthalate syndrome” in rats. The phthalate syndrome is characterised by malformations of the epididymis, vas deferens, seminal vesicles, prostate, external genitalia (hypospadias), and by cryptorchidism (undescended testes) as well as by retention of nipples/areolae (sexually dimorphic structures in rodents) and demasculinisation of the perineum, resulting in reduced anogenital distance (AGD). The phthalate syndrome in rats bears a resemblance to the “testicular dysgenesis syndrome” (TDS) in humans, which includes poor semen quality, testis cancer, cryptorchidism, and hypospadias (either observed at birth or in childhood), and which is hypothesised to have its origin in diminished androgen action during fetal life (Sharpe and Skakkebaek, 2008).

The report at hand will focus primarily on the reproductive and developmental toxicity of DnBP. DnBP inhibits fetal testosterone production, reduces male AGD, decreases gene expression related to steroid biosynthesis, increases permanent nipple retention in male offspring, increases incidence of genital malformations (hypospadias and cryptorchidism), delays puberty onset, reduces semen quality and causes testicular changes including decreased testes and epididymis weight, tubular atrophy and Leydig cell hyperplasia in rats (ECHA, 2016). The current scientific evidence in male animals and epidemiological studies shows that these effects are relevant in male humans (ECHA, 2014; ECHA, 2016). They form the basis for the N(L)OAEs and Derived No-Effect Levels (DNELs) identified for the combined risk assessment of phthalates including DnBP in the ECHA’s 2016 restriction report (ECHA, 2016).

Other adverse effects caused by DnBP in animals and humans were reviewed in the following reports: EU RAR, 2004; NICNAS, 2013; ANSES, 2017; SCOEL, 2017.

¹⁹ Phthalates with 3 to 7 (or 8) carbon atoms in the backbone of the alkyl side chain (CHAP, 2014)

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 67

5.2.1 Human toxicity studies

Human health effects related to the environmental exposure to phthalates in human populations are a very active area of research, with 65 studies published in 2014-2016 related to effects on reproduction and development alone, as reported by Rice (2017). A review of all recently published epidemiological studies regarding DnBP was not performed. Conclusions that were drawn in recent reports regarding available epidemiological evidence on DnBP are reported in the present document (ANSES, 2017; ECHA, 2012, 2014, 2016; CHAP 2014).

As indicated by ECHA, a number of epidemiological studies are available showing associations with developmental effects on male reproduction, such as congenital malformations of the male reproductive organs, reduced semen quality, reduced male reproductive hormone levels, and changes in pubertal timing (ECHA, 2016). Epidemiological studies are generally associated with considerable uncertainties and it is therefore difficult to draw exact conclusions on these studies. However, they contribute to the overall evidence that effects seen in rats from exposure to specific phthalates are relevant in humans at exposure levels seen in the population.

An overview of some epidemiological studies in which DnBP exposure has been related to health effects is given in Table 3. The results of these studies in men and boys point to reprotoxic effects of DnBP, but do not allow to define a critical concentration of MnBP. It should be noted that four publications (Hauser et al., 2006; Duty et al., 2003; 2004; and 2005) refer to a cross-sectional study (consultation for infertility in the same clinic) that appears to have been reproduced several times using the results of the previous study each time (thus increasing the population size with each publication), but thus not showing independent results (ANSES, 2015).

Table 11: Epidemiological studies in which urinary concentrations of MnBP have been related to reproductive or developmental health effects (ANSES, 2015)

Reference	Population and size	Urinary concentrations of MnBP Median (95 th percentile)			Reproduction parameter	Levels of exposure associated with significant effect ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$)
		$\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$		$\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\text{ cr}$		
		Without adjustment	Adjusted to urinary density ²⁰			
Axelsson et al., 2015a	314 Swedish men entering military service				Decrease in sperm concentration and motility	
Duty et al., 2003	143 men, infertile couples	15.9 (73.1)	16.2 (58.5)	-	Decrease in sperm motility	20.16 - 433.93 (adjusted for specific gravity)
Duty et al., 2004	220 men, infertile couples	17.8 (90)	18.0 (73.9)	-	Decrease in sperm motility	-
Duty et al., 2005	295 men, infertile couples	14.3 (75.4)	16.2 (69.9)	-	Increase in the level of inhibin B (hormone)	-

²⁰ 1.024 as reference value

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 68

Reference	Population and size	Urinary concentrations of MnBP Median (95 th percentile)			Reproduction parameter	Levels of exposure associated with significant effect ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$)
		$\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$		$\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\text{ cr}$		
		Without adjustment	Adjusted to urinary density ²⁰			
Hauser et al., 2006	463 men, infertile couples	-	17.7 (69.9)	-	Decrease in sperm concentration and motility	31.7 – 14,459 (adjusted for specific gravity)
Jönsson et al., 2005	234 Swedish men (military service)	78 (330)	-	47 (159)	No association with sperm counts or hormones	-
Swan et al., 2005	85* mothers	13.5 (75 th p 30.9)	-	-	Decreased AGD in boys	7.2 - 30.9
Frederiksen	725 healthy Danish girls (aged 5.6–19.1 years)	MnBP, 95 th p: 153 MiBP, 95 th p: 241			Association at high exposure (MnBP(i+n)) with significantly delayed pubarche	
Mouritsen et al., 2013	84 girls from Denmark	GM: 122 (23-904)			Negative association with adrenal androgen levels in girls	
	84 boys from Denmark	GM: 118 (23-676)			Association at high exposure with earlier age at pubarche in boys	
Zhang et al., 2015	430 children (222 boys and 208 girls) aged 9.7 ± 2.2 years	GM: boys 22.32, girls 21.41 (adjusted for specific gravity)			Association with delayed pubic hair development in boys, and with breast onset in girls	
Pan et al., 2006	63 unexposed controls	-	-	113.5 (434.5)	Significant correlation with reduction in FT in exposed workers	-
	74 exposed workers (PVC)	-	-	548.4 (8781.2)		-
Weuve et al., 2010	1,227(1,221) women 20–54 years of age (NHANES, 1999–2004)	GM (SE): 26.2 (0.9)			Prevalence of uterine diseases (pooled cases of endometriosis and uterine leiomyomata (fibroids))	

* The article does not clearly state if the population size is 85 or fewer newborn boys

IQR = interquartile range increase; FT = free testosterone; DFI = DNA fragmentation index

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 69

Hauser et al. (2006) assessed 463 subjects and showed a dose-response relationship between increased urinary concentrations of MnBP and decreased sperm motility. This study (unlike that of Duty et al., 2003) also revealed a dose-response relationship between increased urinary concentrations of MnBP and lower sperm concentration.

On the other hand, Jönsson et al. (2005) did not show any changes in sperm parameters or hormone levels in men (around the age of 20 years) whose median urinary MnBP concentration was 78 µg/L (95th percentile concentration at 330 µg/L).

Swan et al. (2005) showed an increased frequency of decreased AGD in newborns, statistically associated with an increase in maternal urinary concentrations of MnBP (also of monoethyl phthalate (MEP), mono(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (MEHP), mono(2-ethyl-5-hydroxyhexyl) phthalate (MEHHP) and mono(2-ethyl-5-oxohexyl) phthalate (MEOHP), considered separately or with an overall exposure score). The highest odds ratios are those obtained with MnBP, with no adjustment for concentrations of other metabolites.

Other studies did not find any association between urinary MnBP concentrations and shortened AGD (CHAP, 2014 according to Huang et al., 2009; Suzuki et al., 2012).

The data on pubertal development of children and adolescents are inconsistent. Frederiksen et al. (2012) found that a high urinary phthalate concentration (MnBP_(i+n)) was associated with significantly delayed pubarche in healthy girls, in contrast, phthalate exposure was not associated with age at breast development in girls. Mouritsen et al. (2013) investigated whether urinary phthalate metabolite levels are associated with circulating adrenal androgen levels and age at puberty. In girls in puberty (13 years of age), lower serum levels of two adrenal androgens (dehydroepiandrosterone sulfate and andione) were retrieved in those who excreted the highest amount of MnBP. The same trend was observed at 10 years of age, albeit not statistically significant. No associations between phthalate exposure and age at pubertal milestones were observed. A lower age at pubarche was observed in boys with excretion of MnBP above the geometric group mean (11.0 vs 12.3 years, $p = 0.005$). Findings of Zhang et al. (2015) suggest subtle effects of phthalate metabolites associated with pubertal onset and progression. MnBP exposure may be associated with delayed pubic hair development in boys, while MnBP, MMP, MEP, and MEHP exposures may be associated with breast onset in girls. The odds of girls' breast onset were 4 to 10 times higher in the high MnBP, MMP, MEP or MEHP exposure group than in the low exposure group.

In workers, Pan et al. (2006) observed a modest and significant reduction of serum free testosterone with higher levels of urinary MnBP and MEHP compared with unexposed workers.

The study performed by Weuve et al. (2010) with over 1,200 women showed a dose-response relationship between increased urinary concentrations of MnBP and the prevalence of uterine diseases (pooled cases of endometriosis and uterine leiomyomata²¹ (fibroids)). However, no significant dose-response relationship was retrieved when considering separate data of endometriosis and leiomyomata. Furthermore, the results of Itoh et al. (2009), investigating infertile Japanese women, do not support the hypothesis that higher urinary concentrations of phthalate metabolites are associated with an increased risk of endometriosis.

Associations of MnBP with neurodevelopmental effects could not be substantiated unequivocally (CHAP, 2014).

²¹ Uterine leiomyomata are benign neoplasms composed of smooth muscle cells, growing within or around the myometrium

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 70

In terms of adverse effects of phthalate exposure on the immune system, it was found that children from homes with high concentrations of phthalates (DEHP, BBzP and DnBP) in dust had high incidences of allergy, asthma, rhinitis or eczema (Bornehag et al., 2004; Hsu et al., 2012; Kolarik et al., 2008; Braun et al., 2013). These studies however do not clarify possible causative relationships (ECHA, 2016).

It has to be mentioned that unfortunately, up to present, most of the epidemiological studies observing the health outcomes of DnBP together with biomonitoring data have used the total urinary MnBP concentration (free and glucuronidated forms). However, studies with rats and hamsters suggest that a higher concentration of free MnBP in urine in relation to the total urinary MnBP concentration may be associated with more testicular damage after oral treatment with either DnBP or MnBP (Foster et al., 1983). Furthermore, placental transfer of glucuronidated xenobiotics is typically inefficient (Saillenfait et al., 1998), and both animal and human studies have found that the free phthalate metabolites were predominant in amniotic fluid (Calafat et al., 2006; Saillenfait et al., 1998; Tranfo et al., 2014). Thus, the free form phthalate metabolite may be more bioactive and a better proxy for the effective exposure levels *in utero*.

5.2.2 Animal studies

Animal reproductive and developmental toxicity studies cover a broad range of species and methods, and clearly support the overall conclusion that DnBP has anti-androgenic properties (CHAP, 2014). The adverse outcome following gestational exposure of rats to DnBP is known as the rat phthalate syndrome. As already mentioned, it is well understood, that this syndrome with diverse effects on male offspring like reduced semen quality, testicular injury, decreased AGD, increased nipple retention, increased incidence of hypospadias, increased incidence of cryptorchidism, delayed puberty onset and changes in germ cell differentiation is caused by fetal androgen suppression (Kortenkamp and Faust, 2010; CHAP, 2014; Health Canada, 2015)

In a study by Lee et al. (2004), maternal rats were given DnBP at dietary concentrations of 0, 20, 200, 2000 and 10000 mg/kg (corresponding to 0, 2, 20, 200 and 1000 mg/kg bw/day) from late gestation (gestational day (GD) 15) to the end of lactation on postnatal day 21 (PND 21). Reduction of testicular spermatocyte development and mammary gland changes at low incidence in both sexes of offspring were seen at PND 21 at the lowest dose tested of 20 mg/kg (1.5-3.0 mg/kg bw/day) and above, with dose-dependent increased incidence or/and severity. Loss of germ cell development was no longer present at 20 mg/kg at postnatal week 11, but was still present with dose-dependency from 200 mg/kg (14-28 mg/kg bw/day) to 10000 mg/kg (712-1372 mg/kg bw/day). A significant increase in scattered foci of aggregated Leydig cells was observed at 2000 mg/kg and 10000 mg/kg. In the epididymis, significantly decreased ductular cross sections, indicating reduced coiling, were observed at 2000 and 10000 mg/kg. Non-dose-related, but statistically significant effects on the mammary gland persisted to postnatal week 11 in males at all doses, but by postnatal week 20, significant effects were only seen from 200 mg/kg and above.

DnBP administered to gestating rats inhibits the steroidogenic activity of fetal testicles in various strains of rats. The consequences of inhibited fetal testosterone production have been clearly identified (e.g. decreased AGD, retention of mammary areola or nipples in males, reduced penile length, lower prostate weight and increase in hypospadias and cryptorchidism) (INSERM, 2011).

Most of the effects of *in utero* exposure in animals involve foetal testicles and have been observed in gavage studies. These studies report effects on the three main types of testicular cells: Leydig cells, Sertoli cells and germ cells (INSERM, 2011). Leydig cell dysgenesis seems to occur in connection with other reproductive developmental effects in rodents (Barlow and Foster, 2003; Barlow et al., 2004). Also, unusual clusters of undifferentiated germ cells and multinucleated germ

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 71

cells have been observed in animal studies (Skakkebaek et al., 2016). Further research is necessary to elucidate the role of Leydig cell dysgenesis and multinucleated gonocytes observed in animal studies in relation to the human TDS and human testicular cancer.

A study to estimate the relative toxicity of different phthalates was performed by Howdeshell et al. (2008). In this study pregnant Sprague-Dawley rats were exposed to 33, 50, 100, 300, or 600 mg/kg bw/day of DnBP from GD 8 to GD 18 by gavage in corn oil (n=3 to 4 dams per group). Testicular testosterone production ex vivo was assessed by incubation of testes of 18 days old fetuses for 3 hours and testosterone measurement in the media. Dose-related decreases in testosterone production was seen for DnBP from 300 mg/kg bw/day and above.

Lehmann et al. (2004) explored the effects of DnBP on steroidogenesis in fetal testes. Thereby, pregnant Sprague-Dawley rats received DnBP by gavage with corn oil at doses of 0.1; 1.0; 10; 50; 100 or 500 mg/kg bw/day (5 animals per DnBP-dosed group) from GD 12 until GD 19. Male foetus testes were isolated on day 19 and gene expression changes were quantitatively assessed by real-time PCR. Fetal testicular testosterone concentration was measured by radioimmunoassay. The results showed a dose-dependent reduction in the expression of key genes and proteins involved in cholesterol transport and in steroidogenesis accompanied by a reduction of testosterone in fetal testes after maternal exposure from 50 mg/kg bw/day, which is lower than levels at which adverse effects are detected on developing male reproductive organs as e.g. in Mylchreest et al. (2000). Observed changes (gene and protein expression) can serve as early indicators of testicular response to DnBP.

The effects on the development of the male reproductive system linked with the anti-androgenic activity of DnBP are both histological and functional and there is good consistency for the DnBP reprotoxic effects in animals and humans. These effects are relevant to be taken into account for the derivation of HBM-GVs (ANSES, 2015).

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 72

6 Selected biomarker(s) for the HBM-GV proposal and analytical method

6.1 Choice of biomarkers of exposure

Three metabolites of DnBP can be detected in human urine: MnBP, MCPP and MHBP.

Due to a lack of data on urinary concentrations of MHBP in the general population and in occupationally exposed adults, this biomarker was not selected. MCPP can also be a metabolite of di-n-octylphthalate and is therefore not specific to DnBP exposure. MCPP was thus also not retained as biomarker for DnBP.

The biomarker of exposure identified as relevant for the biological monitoring of exposed humans (from the general population or as workers) is the total urinary MnBP. This biomarker is indeed the main metabolite of DnBP (69% to 84% of the absorbed DnBP dose according to Anderson et al. (2001) respectively Koch et al. (2012)). Urinary MnBP is also associated with effects on sperm parameters and decrease of AGD in male newborns (ANSES, 2015). However, urinary MnBP is not specific to DnBP exposure, as it is also a known metabolite of BBzP. But, in case of BBzP exposure, MnBP is seldom detected or not detected at all even at high exposures according to Anderson et al. (2001).

6.2 Analytical method

Total MnBP is measured in the urines by on-line high-performance liquid chromatography and tandem mass spectrometry (HPLC-MS/MS) using internal isotope-labelled standards (Silva et al., 2007a; Kasper-Sonnenberg et al., 2012; Koch et al., 2012; Koch et al., 2017). Deliverable D9.2 “Prioritised list of biomarkers, matrices and analytical methods for the 1st prioritisation round of substances” produced within HBM4EU is providing more details.

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 73

7 Choice of HBM-GVs derivation method

7.1 Derivation of HBM-GVs for the general population

7.1.1 Method for the HBM-GV_{GenPop} derivation

The epidemiological (or human volunteer) studies having measured urinary MnBP and explored adverse health effects in humans do not allow for the identification of a dose-relationship.

A review of the existing toxicity reference values (TRVs) was therefore performed, in accordance with the HBM-GVs derivation methodology (Apel et al., 2020).

A relevant TRV was selected and was used as a basis for calculating the internal concentration of urinary MnBP that is consistent with this external threshold value.

7.1.2 Review of relevant toxicity reference values and selection of a TRV

Agency	Key study	Endpoint	Point of departure	Assessment factors	TRV
EFSA (2005)	Lee et al. (2004)	Reduction of testicular spermatocyte development (loss of germ cell development) and mammary gland changes (vacuolar degeneration and alveolar atrophy) in adult male offspring	LOAEL 2 mg/kg bw/d	On the whole: 200 - 10 for intraspecies differences - 2.5 for interspecies differences - 4 as allometric scaling factor - 2 for LOAEL to NOAEL extrapolation	TDI 0.01 mg/kg bw
ECHA (2012, 2016)	Lee et al. (2004)	Reduction of testicular spermatocyte development (loss of germ cell development) and mammary gland changes (vacuolar degeneration and alveolar atrophy) in adult male offspring	LOAEL 2 mg/kg bw/d	On the whole: 300 - 10 for intraspecies differences - 10 for interspecies differences - 3 for LOAEL to NOAEL extrapolation	DNEL 0.0067 mg/kg bw
CHAP report (2014)	Mylchreest et al. (2000) Zhang et al. (2004)	Increased nipple retention in male pups Increased male AGD	NOAEL 50 mg/kg bw/day	-	-
OEHHA 2007	Lee et al. (2004)	Histopathological changes in the testis and mammary glands in adult male offspring	LOAEL 1.5 mg/kg bw/d)	10000 - 10 for LOAEL to NOAEL extrapolation - 1000 for animal to human extrapolation	MADL_{adults} 8.7 µg/day (based on a human female bw of 58 kg)

DNEL: Derived No-Effect level; N(L)OAEL: No (Lowest) Observed Adverse Effect Level; MADL: Maximum Allowable Dose Level; TDI: Tolerable Daily Intake

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 74

7.1.2.1 EFSA

The developmental rat toxicity study by Lee et al. (2004) was selected by EFSA as key study for the derivation of the TDI value for DnBP in 2005. A LOAEL based on the loss of germ cell development and mammary gland changes at 20 mg/kg in the diet was identified.

Given the reversibility of the effects at all dose levels and especially at the LOAEL (20 mg/kg feed, which corresponds to 1.5 to 3 mg/kg bw/day) and also given that in several reproductive toxicity studies with longer exposure periods approximately 30-fold higher NOAELs or LOAELs had been determined, a global assessment factor (AF) of 200 (10 for intraspecies differences, 10 for interspecies differences and 2 for the LOAEL to NOAEL extrapolation) was considered sufficient to derive a TDI for DnBP.

7.1.2.2 ECHA

With regard to the Annex XV dossier proposing restrictions on four phthalates, RAC also selected the LOAEL of 2 mg/kg bw/day from the Lee et al. (2004) study as point of departure. RAC further decided to apply an overall AF of 300 (10 for intraspecies differences, 10 for interspecies differences and 3 for the LOAEL to NOAEL extrapolation) to derive a DNEL of 0.0067 mg/kg bw for DnBP (ECHA, 2012, 2016).

Since the derived DNEL is based on a LOAEL for developmental reproductive effects, the DNEL is most relevant to assess the risk for pregnant women and may not be relevant for assessing the risks for children, as the critical period of exposure in the studies is prenatal and early postnatal which does not mimic the direct exposure of children. Given however that phthalates exert the most effect during the developmental phase, and pregnant women (and thus fetuses) and very small children are the main target groups to protect, it was concluded that the derived DNEL could also be used for evaluating risks for toddlers (recognising though that even toddlers are not completely comparable to very small children) (ECHA, 2012).

7.1.2.3 CHAP

The Chronic Hazard Advisory Panel (CHAP) was established by the U.S. Consumer Product Safety Commission to study the effects of all phthalates and phthalate alternatives used in children's toys and childcare articles (CHAP, 2014). The study of Lee et al. (2004) was not selected as key study by the authors of the CHAP report, because less than 20 animals per dose were used. The CHAP committee focused instead on the studies of Mylchreest et al. (2000) and Zhang et al. (2004). For both studies, multiple doses and approximately 20 animals per dose were used. In the absence of maternal toxicity, Mylchreest reported an increase in nipple retention in male pups at 100 mg/kg bw/day, whereas Zhang et al. reported increased male AGD at 250 mg/kg bw/day. For each study, a NOAEL of 50 mg/kg bw/day has been established. A NOAEL of 50 mg/kg bw/day is also supported by the study of Mahood et al. (2007), which indicates a LOAEL of 100 mg/kg bw/day for decreased fetal testosterone production after exposure to DnBP (CHAP, 2014). However, the report of the CHAP does not indicate a TRV related to this POD, as a combined risk of similar acting phthalates (including DEHP, DnBP, DiBP and BBzP) via the concept of dose addition through a Hazard Index approach was performed.

7.1.2.4 Selection of a TRV

Under HBM4EU, the DNEL of 0.0067 mg/kg bw/day derived by ECHA (2012) is retained as external TRV to derive the HBM-GV_{GenPop}. The decision of EFSA (2005) to use an AF of 2 for the LOAEL-NOAEL extrapolation due to "the reversibility of the observed effects and due to results of other studies with higher NOAELs/LOAELs" is not supported. Instead, ECHA's method to apply an AF of 3 for the LOAEL-NOAEL extrapolation is supported. Indeed, this is the minimum value recommended in the ECHA guidance R8 for taking into account the uncertainty in the dose-

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 75

relationship when the LOAEL represents the lower boundary of the exposure range in which the effect is observed.

The DNEL value is rounded to 0.007 mg/kg bw/d for further calculations.

7.1.3 Calculation of the HBM-GV_{GenPop}

The fractional urinary excretion coefficient (F_{ue}) of the biomarker, i.e. the share of orally absorbed DnBP that is excreted in form of urinary MnBP, is 69 % according to the human toxicokinetic study of Anderson et al. (2001). This molar excretion fraction of ingested DnBP was selected instead of the 84% retrieved by Koch et al. (2012). Indeed, the Koch et al. (2012) study was conducted in only one human volunteer, whereas eight volunteers were involved in the Anderson et al. (2001) study.

The HBM-GV_{GenPop} for urinary MnBP is calculated with the following mass balance equation, assuming steady-state conditions of exposure:

$$\text{HBM-GV}_{\text{GenPop (U-MnBP)}} = \frac{\text{DNEL(ECHA,2016)} \cdot \left(\frac{\text{MW(MnBP)}}{\text{MW(DnBP)}}\right) \cdot F_{ue}}{\text{Daily urine volume adjusted to the bodyweight}} \quad (\text{with MW} = \text{molecular weight})$$

The following daily urine volumes adjusted to the bodyweight are assumed according to the HBM4EU concept document: 0.03 L/kg bw/day for children and 0.02 l/kg bw/day for adults.

- **HBM-GV_{GenPop (U-MnBP), children}** = $\frac{0.007 \text{ mg/kg bw/day} \cdot \left(\frac{222.24}{278.34}\right) \cdot 0.69}{0.03 \text{ L/kg bw/day}} = 0.12 \text{ mg/L}$
- **HBM-GV_{GenPop (U-MnBP), adults}** = $\frac{0.007 \text{ mg/kg bw/day} \cdot \left(\frac{222.24}{278.34}\right) \cdot 0.69}{0.02 \text{ L/kg bw/day}} = 0.19 \text{ mg/L}$

7.2 Derivation of an HBM-GV_{Worker} for the occupational population

7.2.1 Method for the HBM-GV_{Worker} derivation

Epidemiological studies and field studies do not allow for quantifying a dose-response relationship between DnBP effects and MnBP urinary levels.

The calculation of the urinary MnBP concentration at any recommended 8-hour occupational exposure limit (8h-OEL) value is also not possible, because there are no workplace studies reporting both urinary concentrations of MnBP and atmospheric concentrations of DnBP (ANSES, 2015, 2017). Available OEL values are mentioned for information only in the Annex.

Therefore, the last option for deriving the HBM-GV_{Worker} is to select a POD related to the critical effect (i.e. reprotoxicity) from an animal key study and to extrapolate this POD into a human urinary MnBP level.

Pregnant women are much likely to be occupationally exposed to DnBP in the 1st trimester of pregnancy, before knowing their pregnancy status and thus before being able to inform their employer in order to be removed from their workstation if exposed to DnBP.

According to the DnBP toxicological profile, the selected critical effect concerns the development of the male reproductive system after *in utero* exposure. According to the data in the scientific

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 76

literature, the testicular differentiation takes place around GD 13.5 in rats²² and around GD 43 in humans (thus during the middle of the 1st trimester of pregnancy in humans) (Magre and Jost, 1991; Shepard, 1998; INSERM, 2011).

7.2.2 Choice of a POD value from a key study

From the available toxicity studies, it seems relevant to use data on the most susceptible animal species, i.e. male rats, and during what seems to be the most susceptible period, i.e. *in utero* exposure.

Workers are likely to be exposed to DnBP via inhalation mainly, therefore toxicity studies exploring the reprotoxicity of DnBP and having animals exposed *in utero* via inhalation of pregnant rats would be preferred as key study. However, none such study is available from the scientific literature. Thus, toxicity studies exploring the reprotoxicity in rats of DnBP via oral intake were assessed. The gastrointestinal absorption of DnBP is close to 100% in rodents (INSERM, 2011). In the absence of data, it is considered by default that DnBP absorption by inhalation is also 100% in rodents, as well as in humans.

The POD of 2 mg/kg bw/day (LOAEL) identified in the Lee et al. (2004) study was not selected because the exposure period lasted from GD 15 to the end of lactation on PND 21. The perinatal exposure conditions are not considered relevant for an occupational exposure scenario, as pregnant women (as soon as they become aware of their pregnancy, most often by the end of the 1st trimester) and breast-feeding mothers should not be exposed to DnBP (see section 4.5).

From the scientific literature review of all relevant animal studies on the reproductive and developmental toxicity of DnBP²³, the study from Lehmann et al. (2004) was identified as key study. A NOEL of 10 mg/kg bw/day regarding the decrease in concentration of testicular testosterone in the foetus in combination with the reduction in the expression of key genes encoding proteins involved in cholesterol transport and steroidogenesis following *in utero* exposure (GD 12 to GD 19) was identified as POD in this study.

7.2.3 Calculation of the HBM-GV_{Worker}

The method for deriving the HBM-GV_{Worker} is based on the calculation of the urinary MnBP level consistent with the human extrapolated NOEL identified in the study from Lehmann et al. (2004).

First, an extrapolation of the NOEL of 10 mg/kg bw/day from rats to humans taking into account the same route of exposure (oral) is performed, by applying an interspecies AF of 10, as for the HBM-GV_{GenPop} derivation. Regarding the exposure route extrapolation between oral and inhalation (inhalation being the most likely absorption pathway of DnBP at the workplace), it is assumed that the bioavailability of DnBP for both exposure routes is 100% (see section 5.1) and that the retrieved urinary total MnBP concentrations would be the same between both routes.

An AF_H of 10 accounting for intra-species differences is further applied to the human adjusted NOEL. Usually, a default value of 5 is applied when accounting for intraspecies differences in the working population for systemic effects, instead of 10 for the general population as the occupational population is considered a more homogeneous population group, as it does not include infants, children, seniors and very sick individuals. However, the selected critical endpoints

²² For rat: at the stage of 13.5 days after fertilization, the first Sertoli cells differentiate. A continuous basal lamina delineating the seminiferous cords begins to appear on GD 14.5 and becomes widespread on GD 15.5 (Magre and Jost., 1991)

²³ Criteria for selecting relevant studies were: 1) Animal / human consistency of the effect considered, 2) Sensitivity of the effect: only studies showing the lowest reference dose (NOAEL or LOAEL) were retained and 3) Plausibility of the exposure scenario with regard to occupational exposure.

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 77

are related to the effects on the offspring after *in utero* exposure. In this case, as no sensitivity and toxicokinetic differences following exposure can be assumed between foetuses carried by women from the general population and foetuses carried by working women, a default AF of 10 for the intra-species differences was applied to the respective PODs. Thus a 'TRV-like value' of 0.1 mg/kg bw/day is obtained.

Within 24h, a share of 69 % (F_{ue}) of DnBP orally absorbed is excreted in the urine in form of total MnBP, according to Anderson et al. (2001).

The bodyweight-related urine excretion of 0.02 l/kg bw/day for adults is used for the HBM-GV_{Worker} calculation.

$$\text{HBM-GV}_{\text{Worker (U-MnBP)}} = \frac{0.1 \text{ mg/kg bw/day} \cdot \left(\frac{222.24}{278.34}\right) \cdot 0.69}{0.02 \text{ L/kg bw/day}} \sim 3 \text{ mg/l}$$

In the occupational field, moments of sampling are part of the biological monitoring strategy and are based on the toxicokinetic properties of the biomarker of exposure. MnBP has an estimated urinary half-life of 2.6 hours (Koch et al., 2012). Therefore, the time for sampling urinary MnBP in occupationally exposed adults allowing the occupational physician to investigate the workers exposure with regards to the HBM-GV_{Workers} of 3 mg/l is at the end of the shift, on any day of the working week.

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 78

8 Level of confidence attributed to the derived HBM-GVs

As mentioned in the HBM4EU concept document to derive HBM-GVs, it is suggested to attribute a level of confidence (low, medium or high) to each calculated HBM-GV. The level of confidence should reflect the uncertainties identified during the elaboration of the value and could constitute a good incentive to revise later on values with estimated 'lower' level of confidence.

However, it should be specified that the levels of confidence proposed in this document are not determined according to an established recognised methodology, but rather rely on expert judgment regarding the reliability of the data and the calculation method used to derive the HBM-GVs.

The levels of confidence attributed to the HBM-GVs for the general population and for occupationally exposed adults are set to **medium**. Please, refer to the n°2 note of the factsheets presented below for explanation on this level of confidence appreciation.

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 79

9 Discussion

For evaluating the exposure to DnBP in the general population it is recommended to determine MnBP in urine (HBM4EU, Deliverable 9.2 Prioritised list of biomarkers, matrices and analytical methods) and to compare the analytical results with the HBM-GVs for the general population derived here above (general population, children: 0.12 mg/l, adults: 0.19 mg/l). For assessing DnBP exposure in the occupational field, measurement of MnBP in urine as biomarker of exposure should be performed at the end of the workshift for comparison of the concentration with the suggested HBM-GV_{Worker} of 3 mg/l. The derivation of the HBM-GVs for the general population as well as for workers is based on the conversion of external doses to their estimated equivalent internal doses. The respective underlying animal studies were selected according to their relevance for the exposure scenario, which is the main reason for differences between the values for workers and adults of the general population aside from different AFs for intraspecies differences between workers and adults of the general population. The critical endpoints selected are based on anti-androgenic effects. Those effects have been shown in numerous studies, thus allowing for a high level of confidence.

For reducing the uncertainties towards the HBM-GVs hereby derived (global level of confidence is “medium” for the HBM-GV_{GenPop} as well as for the HBM-GV_{Worker}) one lead would be to have a validated PBPK or TK model for DnBP enabling the extrapolation of the selected animal POD value to the corresponding human POD value, thereby avoiding the default factor value for the interspecies differences applied to the animal PODs.

It has to be kept in mind that the toxicokinetic data on the urinary excretion of the metabolite comes solely from a single human study of controlled exposure (2 dose groups, 8 volunteers per dose group). The second study available does only report examination results of one volunteer. No information is available regarding the range of variability occurring in the general population due to age, sex, and other influencing factors. Thus, potential under- or over-estimations by taking a default F_{ue} cannot be excluded. Taking these uncertainties together and considering the likely variations in measured urinary concentrations resulting from the short biological half-life of the metabolite, the HBM-GVs for DnBP have their limitations on the individual level and should be interpreted carefully in terms of the likelihood of an adverse health effect in an individual case. The derived HBM-GV_{GenPop} are most appropriate as a screening tool to evaluate population-based biomonitoring data in the context of possibly necessary risk management on a regulatory level. In this connection it should also be thought about the fact that HBM-GV_{GenPop} are expected to be protective over a lifetime of exposure. Nevertheless, exceedances should serve as a hint to avoid exposure sources, thus allowing for risk minimisation.

Considering the high uncertainties related to the HBM-GV_{Worker} derivation, it is not recommended to use it for the effective control of the health risks related to DnBP in the practice of occupational health. The EU reference value for workers that will be established for DnBP under T10.4 of HBM4EU should be rather used to assess whether the exposure at the workplace is adequately controlled or not.

It should be taken into account that due to the short half-life of excretion of the mono-ester more reliable evaluations of the extent of exposure could be made based on 24h urine collections rather than spot samples. Moreover, a current publication by Casas et al. (2018) quantifying the variability of biomarker measurements of many non-persistent chemicals during several time windows shows that for many of these compounds a few dozen samples are required to accurately assess exposure over periods encompassing several trimesters or months. Exposure misclassification in epidemiological studies is expected to be high.

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 80

10 Factsheets

10.1 Factsheet on the HBM-GV for the general population

Compound: Dibutyl phthalate (DnBP)			Factsheet General Population
Parameter	Note	Value / descriptor	Comments
HBM-GV_{GenPop} and status			
HBM-GV _{GenPop}	1	Urinary total MnBP Children: 0.12 mg/l Adults: 0.19 mg/l	
Level of confidence	2	Medium	
HBM-GV _{GenPop} status	3	Provisional	
HBM-GV _{GenPop} year of issue	4	2019	
General Information			
CLP-INDEX-Nr.	5	607-318-00-4	
EC-Nr.	6	201-557-4	
CAS-Nr.	7	84-74-2	
Harmonised CLP classification	8	- Repr. Cat. 1B - H360Df (may damage the unborn child; suspected of damaging fertility) - Aquatic acute Cat. 1 - H400 (very toxic to aquatic life)	
Molar mass	9	278.34 g/mol	
Biomarker(s)			
Identification	10	Urinary MnBP	
Molar mass of biomarker(s)	11	222.24 g/mol	
Toxicokinetic data			
Key study for TK data, authors, year	12	Anderson et al. (2001): A biomarker approach to measuring human dietary exposure to certain phthalate diesters	
Type of study	13	Human	8 volunteers/dose group
Route of exposure	14	Oral single dose: 255 or 510 µg	
Half-life of biomarker(s)	15	Elimination half-time of MnBP is 2.6 hr	Koch et al. (2012)
Factor for metabolic conversion (F _{ue})	16	F _{ue} = 0.69 (urinary MnBP)	Anderson et al. (2001)
Derivation method			
Derivation method	17	Based on a DNEL	ECHA (2016)
DNEL	18	0.007 mg/kg bw/d	Key study: Lee et al. (2004): Developmental toxicity study Critical endpoints: delayed germ cell

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 81

			development and male mammary gland changes after exposure from GD15 to PND21 POD: LOAEL= 2 mg/kg bw/d Total AF = 300
Calculation of HBM-GV_{GenPop}			
Calculated HBM-GV _{GenPop}	19	<p>Children: $\text{HBM-GV}_{\text{GenPop}} (\text{MnBP}) = [0.007 \text{ mg/kg bw/d} \cdot (222.24/278.34) \cdot 0.69] / 0.03 \text{ l/kg bw/d}$ = 0.12 mg/l</p> <p>Adults: $\text{HBM-GV}_{\text{GenPop}} (\text{MnBP}) = [0.007 \text{ mg/kg bw/d} \cdot (222.24/278.34) \cdot 0.69] / 0.02 \text{ l/kg bw/d}$ = 0.19 mg/l</p>	$\text{HBM-GV}_{\text{GenPop}} = [\text{DNEL} \cdot (\text{MW}_{\text{MnBP}} / \text{MW}_{\text{DnBP}}) \cdot \text{F}_{\text{ue}}] / \text{urine volume}$ Calculated with the following urine volumes: Children (6-13y) = 0.03 l/kg bw/d Adults = 0.02 l/kg bw/d

Explanation of notes:

1) HBM-GV_{GenPop}: numerical value of the HBM-GV_{GenPop} in mg/l

2) Level of confidence of the HBM-GV_{GenPop}: reflects the reliability of the proposed HBM-GV. The level of confidence takes into account the various uncertainties underlying the derivation of the HBM-GV (e.g. reliability of the key study used to derive the TDI or TDI like value, uncertainties related to the toxicokinetic data on the substance of interest, to the extrapolations and calculation of the final HBM-GV). Attribution of a global level of confidence for the proposed HBM-GV_{GenPop} is suggested, considering:

- the nature and quality of the toxicological and epidemiological data: epidemiological and field studies are available but associated with considerable uncertainties, making it difficult to draw exact conclusions; numerous toxicological studies on different animal species exist; the determination of the factor for metabolic conversion (F_{ue}) is based on one study with 8 volunteers/dose group only (see note 12); data gaps exist to compare adults and children: data are missing to ensure that metabolism and sensitivity are similar in adults and children → **medium**
- the choice of the critical endpoint and mode of action: There is high confidence in the critical effect (delayed germ cell development and mammary gland changes). The evidence of the anti-androgenic effects of DnBP is based on numerous animal studies. Evidence for these effects in humans is available from the scientific literature → **high**
- the selected key study for the derivation of a DNEL: The animal toxicity study selected as key study was conducted not according to OECD guidelines but evaluated by ECHA, 2014 as reliable. The best case for deducing HBM-GVs would have been the availability of human data. → **medium**
- the selected POD: The selected POD is the DNEL based on a LOAEL. No NOAEL could be derived for DnBP and thus uncertainty regarding the no-effect level exists for DnBP. → **low**
- the extrapolations of the POD value for the DNEL calculation: the LOAEL from the key study is being extrapolated using default AFs: across species (AF_A = 10) and according to intra-individual variability (AF_H = 10). Using a validated PBPK model or TK model for extrapolating from animal to human could increase the level of confidence. → **low**

Altogether the global level of confidence for the DnBP HBM-GV_{GenPop} is set to '**medium**'.

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 82

3) HBM-GV_{GenPop} status: the status value is fixed to 'provisional', thereby reflecting that this value could be revised later on in the project, if uncertainties underlying the data could be reduced. For example, the uncertainties of the TK data could be reduced by means of a validated PBPK model for DnBP. A higher level of confidence attributed to the value would lead to a 'confirmed' value status.

4) HBM-GV_{GenPop} year of issue: year of setting the HBM-GV_{GenPop} in the HBM4EU workframe.

5) CLP Number: according to Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 on classification, labelling and packaging (CLP) of substances and mixtures, implementing the globally harmonised system of chemical classification or GHS
http://guidance.echa.europa.eu/docs/guidance_document/clp_introduutory_en.pdf

6) EC Number: under European Inventory of Existing Commercial chemical Substances (EINECS), ELINCS (European List of Notified Chemical Substances) in support of Directive 92/32/EEC, the 7th amendment to Directive 67/548/EEC, NLP (No-Longer Polymers), see: ESIS: European chemical Substances Information System:
<https://web.archive.org/web/20131106181548if/http://esis.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>

7) CAS Number: collection of disclosed chemical compound information by Chemical Abstracts Service. Almost all molecule databases can be searched by CAS Registry Number.

8) Harmonised CLP classification: CLP classification including CMR and other health relevant effects. In the case that classification is not harmonised, this should be stated. For self-classifications by industry the ECHA- CLP inventory can be searched at: <http://echa.europa.eu/web/guest/information-on-chemicals/cl-inventory-database>

9) Molar mass: mass of DnBP per amount of this substance expressed in g/mol

10) Biomarker(s) identification: the biomarker identified as valid for a diagnosis of exposure to DnBP is the monoester MnBP (Anderson et al., 2001) which should be taken into consideration for the HBM-GV derivation.

11) Molar mass of the biomarker(s): mass of the selected biomarker(s) (expressed in g/mol)

12) Study for TK data, Authors, Year: Anderson et al. (2001) examined the metabolism of DnBP in humans. The metabolites and the elimination kinetics were determined by means of chromatographic-mass spectrometric methods (LC-MS) following hydrolysis of conjugates. ¹³C-labelled DnBP was administered to a group of 8 individuals at a low (255 µg) and a high dose (510 µg). 24-h urine samples were collected on the day of administration, the next day, and day 6. Assuming that the volunteers had bodyweights of approximately 70 kg, the doses were corresponding to 3.6 and 7.3 µg/kg/day. No labelled DnBP derivative was found in samples collected after the 1st day, confirming the rapid metabolism and elimination of this substance in urine.

13) Type of study: human oral study

14) Route of exposure: oral single administration

15) Half-life of biomarker: estimated elimination half-lives for the DnBP metabolite

16) Factor for metabolic conversion (F_{ue}): fractional urinary excretion ratio of biomarker relative to the oral dose of DnBP taken up. For DnBP, 64% and 73% on a molar basis of the low, and high dose respectively was excreted as monobutyl phthalate. No labelled DnBP derivative was found in samples collected after the 1st day, confirming the rapid metabolism and elimination of this substance in urine, also confirming that the excretion fraction measured accounted for the full administrated dose.

17) Derivation method: the existing data base on DnBP does not allow for the derivation of health-based guidance values from human data, based on internal concentration and health effects relationship. Therefore, a derivation method based on a TRV, i.e. a DNEL in this case, is used.

18) DNEL: A LOAEL of 2 mg/kg bw/day was selected from the developmental study performed by Lee et al. (2004) referring to the observed delayed germ cell development and persistent male mammary gland changes.

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 83

Assessment factors (AF): 3 for LOAEL - NOAEL-extrapolation, 10 for intraspecies differences, 10 for interspecies differences

19) HBM-GVs: Ideally, the HBM-GVs should refer to a complete 24-hour urine sample, stating the quantity of a substance in µg/d, especially if the monitored substance has a short half-life of excretion. For reasons of simplification, in accordance with the approach described in the concept document, the excretion is referred to a body weight-related urine excretion of 30 ml/kg bw/day for children and 20 ml/kg bw/d for the remaining subgroups of the population.

The resulting HBM-GV_{GenPop} for MnBP in urine are as follows:

Children: 0.12 mg/l

Adults including adolescents and women in child-bearing age: 0.19 mg/l

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 84

10.2 Factsheet on the HBM-GV for workers

Compound: Dibutyl phthalate (DnBP)		Target population: occupational exposed adults	
Parameter	Note	Value / descriptor	Comments
HBM-GV_{Worker} and Status			
HBM-GV _{Worker}	1	Urinary total MnBP = 3 mg/l	Based on reprotoxic effects
Level of confidence	2	Medium	See note for explanation
HBM-GV _{Worker} status	3	Provisional	See note for explanation
HBM-GV _{Worker} year of issue	4	2019	
General Information			
CLP-INDEX-Nr.	5	607-318-00-4	
EC-Nr.	6	201-557-4	
CAS-Nr.	7	84-74-2	
Harmonised CLP classification	8	- Repr. Cat.1B - H360Df (may damage the unborn child; suspected of damaging fertility) - Aquatic Acute Cat. 1 - H400 (very toxic to aquatic life)	
Molar mass	9	278.34 g/mol	
Biomarker(s)			
Identification	10	Urinary MnBP	
Molar mass of biomarker(s)	11	222.24 g/mol	
Toxicokinetic data			
Key study for TK data, authors, year	12	Anderson et al. (2001): A biomarker approach to measuring human dietary exposure to certain phthalate diesters	
Type of study	13	Human	8 volunteers/dose group
Route of exposure	14	Oral single dose: 255 or 510 µg	
Half-life of biomarker(s) (second phase)	15	Excretion halftime of MnBP is 2.6 hr	Koch et al. (2012)
Factor for metabolic conversion (F _{ue})	16	F _{ue} = 0.69 (urinary MnBP)	Anderson et al. (2001)
Derivation method and calculation			
Derivation method	17	Based on an animal POD	
Animal POD	18	Oral NOEL 10 mg/kg bw/day	<u>Key study:</u> Lehmann et al. (2004), Developmental toxicity study <u>Critical effect:</u> Reduction of testosterone concentrations in fetal testes

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 85

			in combination with the reduction in the expression of key genes encoding proteins involved in cholesterol transport and steroidogenesis after <i>in utero</i> exposure from GD12 to GD19
TRV-like value	19	0.1 mg/kg bw/day	Global AF of 100 (AF for interspecies differences of 10; AF for intraspecies differences of 10)
Calculation of HBM-GV_{Worker}			
HBM-GV _{Worker}	20	Urinary MnBP = [0.1 mg/kg bw/d · (222.24/278.34) · 0.69] / 0.02 l/kg bw/d = 3 mg/l	HBM-GV _{Worker} (MnBP) = [TRV-like value · (MW _{MnBP} /MW _{DnBP}) · F _{ue}] / adult bodyweight-related urine excretion
Comment: Sampling should be done at the end of the work-shift.			

Explanation of notes:

1) HBM-GV_{Worker}: numerical value of the HBM-GV in mg/L

2) Level of confidence of the HBM-GV_{Worker}: reflects the reliability of the proposed HBM-GV. The level of confidence takes into account the various uncertainties underlying the derivation of the HBM-GV (e.g. reliability of the key study used, uncertainties related to the toxicokinetic data on the substance of interest, to the extrapolations and calculation of the final HBM-GV). Attribution of a global level of confidence for the proposed DnBP HBM-GV_{Worker} is suggested, considering the level of confidence in:

- the nature and quality of the toxicological and epidemiological data: epidemiological and field studies are available but associated with considerable uncertainties, making it difficult to draw exact conclusions; numerous toxicological studies on different animal species. The determination of the factor for metabolic conversion (F_{ue}) is based on one study with 8 volunteers/dose group only (see note 12) → **medium**
- the choice of the critical endpoint and mode of action: the evidence of the anti-androgenic effects of DnBP is based on numerous animal studies. Evidence for these effects in humans is available from the scientific literature. Medium confidence in critical effects (reduction of testosterone concentration in foetal testes in combination with the reduction in the expression of key genes encoding proteins involved in cholesterol transport and steroidogenesis) as there is no clear consensus about the quantity of testosterone reduction that will lead to subsequent adverse effects → **medium**
- the selected key study: The selected key study is an oral animal study; a human study would have been preferred; an inhalation toxicity study would have been preferred; methodological shortcomings according OECD guidelines 414 (Prenatal Developmental Toxicity Study)²⁴, however regarded as reliable by ECHA²⁵ → **medium**
- the selected POD: NOAEL was chosen as POD determined in animal oral toxicity study. BMDL approach would have been preferred over a NOAEL/LOAEL pair. → **medium**

²⁴ See: [http://www.oecd.org/officialdocuments/publicdisplaydocumentpdf/?cote=ENV/JM/MONO\(2018\)18&doclanguage=en](http://www.oecd.org/officialdocuments/publicdisplaydocumentpdf/?cote=ENV/JM/MONO(2018)18&doclanguage=en)

²⁵ European Chemicals Agency (ECHA), ECHA, 2014. Support document to the opinion of the member state committee for identification of diisobutyl phthalate (DIBP)

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 86

- the inter- and intra-species extrapolations: the NOEL identified from the key toxicity study is being extrapolated to humans by an allometric adjustment and a default AF for the TD differences. The adjustment for the intraindividual variability was done by applying a default AF_H of 10. Using a validated PBPK model or TK model for extrapolating from animal to human could increase the level of confidence. → **low**

Altogether the global level of confidence for the DnBP HBM-GV_{worker} is set to '**medium**'.

3) HBM-GV_{Worker} status: the status value is fixed to 'provisional', thereby reflecting that this value could be revised later on in the project, if uncertainties underlying the data could be reduced. For example, the uncertainties of the TK data could be reduced by means of a validated PBPK model for DnBP. A higher level of confidence attributed to the value would lead to a 'confirmed' value status.

4) HBM-GV_{Worker} year of issue: year of setting the HBM-GV_{Worker} in the HBM4EU workframe.

5) CLP Number: according to Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 on classification, labelling and packaging (CLP) of substances and mixtures, implementing the globally harmonised system of chemical classification or GHS
http://guidance.echa.europa.eu/docs/guidance_document/clp_introduutory_en.pdf

6) EC Number: under European Inventory of Existing Commercial chemical Substances (EINECS), ELINCS (European List of Notified Chemical Substances) in support of Directive 92/32/EEC, the 7th amendment to Directive 67/548/EEC, NLP (No-Longer Polymers), see: ESIS: European chemical Substances Information System:
https://web.archive.org/web/20131106181548if_/http://esis.jrc.ec.europa.eu/

7) CAS Number: collection of disclosed chemical compound information by Chemical Abstracts Service.

8) Harmonised CLP classification: CLP classification including CMR and other health relevant effects.

9) Molar mass: mass of DnBP per amount of this substance (g/mol)

10) Biomarker(s) identification: selected biomarker of exposure for DnBP is the monoester MnBP in the urine

11) Molar mass of the biomarker(s): mass of the selected biomarkers (expressed in g/mol)

12) Study for TK data, Authors, Year: Anderson et al. (2001) examined the metabolism of DnBP in humans. The metabolites and the elimination kinetics were determined by means of chromatographic-mass spectrometric methods (LC-MS) following hydrolysis of conjugates. ¹³C-labelled DnBP was administered to a group of 8 individuals at a low (255 µg) and a high dose (510 µg). 24-h urine samples were collected on the day of administration, the next day, and day 6. Assuming that the volunteers had bodyweights of approximately 70 kg, the doses were corresponding to 3.6 and 7.3 µg/kg/day. No labelled DnBP derivative was found in samples collected after the 1st day, confirming the rapid metabolism and elimination of this substance in urine.

13) Type of study: human oral study

14) Route of exposure: oral single administration

15) Half-life of biomarker: estimated elimination half-lives for the DnBP metabolite

16) Factor for metabolic conversion (F_{ue}): fractional urinary excretion ratio of biomarker relative to the oral dose of DnBP taken up. For DnBP, 64% and 73% on a molar basis of the low, and high dose respectively was excreted as MnBP. No labelled DnBP derivative was found in samples collected after the 1st day, confirming the rapid metabolism and elimination of this substance in urine, also confirming that the excretion fraction measured accounted for the full administrated dose.

17) Derivation method: the existing database on DnBP does not allow for the derivation of an HBM-GV_{Worker} from human data. Calculation of an HBM-GV_{Worker} based on the MnBP urinary concentration consistent with an OEL is also not possible, as no correlation was demonstrated between atmospheric levels of DnBP and urinary concentrations of MnBP. Therefore, the derivation method starts from an animal POD.

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 87

18) Selected animal POD: a NOEL of 10 mg/kg bw/day referring to reduction of testosterone concentrations in combination with the reduction in the expression of key genes encoding proteins involved in cholesterol transport and steroidogenesis in rat fetal testes was selected from the Lehmann et al. (2004) oral study.

19) TRV-like value: an AF of 10 for interspecies differences and an AF of 10 for the intra-individual differences among the working population is applied to the POD, resulting in a TRV-like value of 0.1 mg/kg bw/day

20) HBM-GV_{Worker}: resulting HBM-GV_{Worker} for urinary MnBP calculated on the basis of a mass balance equation and the body weight-related urine excretion for adults including women of child-bearing age (20 ml/kg bw/day).

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 88

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D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 89

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D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 90

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D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 91

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D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 92

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D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 93

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D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 94

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D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 95

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12 Annex

Table 12: Available OELs for DnBP

Country		Key study	Critical effect	Point of departure	Assessment factors	TWA 8-hours
SCOEL, 2017 (Europe)		Gamer et al., 2000	Irritation of the upper respiratory tract	LOAEC 1.2 mg.m⁻³ (DnBP aerosol)		0.58 mg.m⁻³
ANSES, 2017 (France)		Lehmann et al., 2004	Reduction of testosterone concentrations in foetal testes	NO(A)EL 10 mg.kg ⁻¹ .d ⁻¹ NO(A)EL_{inhalated} HEC 17,6 mg.m⁻³	6 - 3 for interspecies differences - 3 for intraspecies differences	2 mg.m⁻³
DFG, 2014 (Germany)		Gamer et al., 2000	Irritation of the upper respiratory tract			0,58 mg.m⁻³ (as inhalable fraction and vapor)

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 97

Part III

Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GVs) for DiBP (Diisobutyl phthalate, CAS no. 84-69-5) referring to the general population and to workers

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 98

Table of contents

1	Authors and acknowledgements	100
2	Glossary.....	101
3	Introduction	102
4	General information and properties of Diisobutyl phthalate (DiBP)	103
4.1	Identification of the substance	103
4.2	Physico-chemical properties	103
4.3	Area of application.....	103
4.4	Classification	104
4.5	EU legislation and regulation	104
4.6	Human exposure	104
4.6.1	General population	104
4.6.2	Workers	105
5	General toxicological profile	106
5.1	Human toxicokinetics and metabolism.....	106
5.2	Toxicity	108
5.2.1	Human health effects.....	108
5.2.2	Animal studies	109
6	Selected biomarker for the HBM-GV proposal and analytical method	114
6.1	Choice of biomarker	114
6.1.1	For HBM measurements in the general population	114
6.1.2	For HBM measurements in the occupational field.....	114
6.2	Analytical method	114
7	Choice of the HBM-GVs derivation method.....	115
7.1	Options to derive HBM-GVs for the general population based on results from studies with experimental animals - calculation of HBM-GVs using ECHA's DNEL.....	115
7.1.1	Calculation of HBM-GVs for the general population	116
7.2	Derivation of an HBM-GV for the occupational field based on an animal POD derived by read across to DnBP	117
8	Level of confidence attributed to the derived HBM-GVs	118
9	Discussion	119
10	Fact sheets	121
10.1	Factsheet on the HBM-GV for the general population.....	121
10.2	Factsheet on the HBM-GV for workers	124
11	References	127

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 99

12	Annex.....	133
12.1	Annex 1	133
12.2	Annex 2: PROAST BMD modelling report.....	141
12.2.1	Data Description	141
12.2.2	Selection of the BMR	141
12.2.3	Software Used	141
12.2.4	Results	141
12.2.5	Estimated Model Parameters.....	142
12.2.6	Weights for Model Averaging.....	142
12.2.7	Final BMD Values	142
12.3	Annex 3: Lehmann et al. 2004 study.....	144

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 100

1 Authors and acknowledgements

Lead author

Petra Apel

Contributors

Eva Ougier, ANSES, France

Rosa Lange, UBA, Germany

Matthieu Meslin, ANSES, France

Christophe Rousselle, ANSES, France

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Entity	Contributing expert
NH Finland	FIOH
NH Germany	Holger M. Koch
NH Netherlands	Wieneke, Bil (RIVM)
NH Netherlands	Marjolijn Woutersen (RIVM)
NH Portugal	Teresa Borges (DGS)
NH Portugal	Susana Viegas (ESTeSL)
NH Switzerland	Rex Fitzgerald (SCAHT)
EU Policy Board	Hans Verhagen (EFSA)

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 101

2 Glossary

ADI	Acceptable Daily Intake
ADME	Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism, and Excretion
AF	Assessment Factor
AF _A	Assessment factor for interspecies differences
AF _H	Assessment factor accounting for intraspecies differences
ANSES	French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety
BGV	Biological Guidance Value
BLV	Biological Limit Value
BMD	Benchmark Dose
BMDL	Benchmark Dose Lower confidence Limit
Bw	Body weight
CLP	Classification, Labelling and Packaging
DEHP	Bis(2-ethylhexyl)phthalate
DiBP	Diisobutylphthalate
DNEL	Derived No-Effect Level
ECHA	European Chemicals Agency
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
EU	European Union
FPS	Fetal Phthalate Screen
Fue	Urinary excretion factor (factor for metabolic conversion)
HBM-GV	HBM-Guidance Value (developed under the project HBM4EU)
HBM	Human Biomonitoring
HBM4EU	European Biomonitoring Initiative
HED	Human Equivalent Dose
MAK Commission	German Permanent Senate Commission for the Investigation of Health Hazards of Chemical Compounds in the Work Area
MiBP	Mono-iso-butylphthalate
MOE	Margin of Exposure
NO(A)EL	No Observed (Adverse) Effect Level
OEL	Occupational Exposure Limit
PBPK/PBTK	Physiologically Based Pharmacokinetic/Toxicokinetic

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 102

3 Introduction

Within the framework of task 5.2 of HBM4EU, Human Biomonitoring guidance values (HBM-GVs) are derived for HBM4EU priority substances. From the group of phthalates HBM-GVs are derived for DEHP, DPHP, DnBP, DiBP and BBzP. The methodology applied to derive these values is described in the concept paper previously released in the HBM4EU task 5.2 workframe (Apel et al., 2020). For the time being, HBM-GVs to be derived shall be agreed on at HBM4EU project level, further adoption of derived HBM-GVs at EU level has to be discussed among partners and the EU Commission.

In the current report, general population HBM-GVs ($\text{HBM-GV}_{\text{GenPop}}$) and an occupational HBM-GV ($\text{HBM-GV}_{\text{Worker}}$) are derived and discussed for Diisobutyl phthalate (DiBP).

Effects of DiBP on male reproductive organs observed in rats following gestational exposure are seen as critical effects.

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 103

4 General information and properties of Diisobutyl phthalate (DiBP)

4.1 Identification of the substance

Name	Diisobutyl phthalate (DiBP)
IUPAC Name	1,2-bis(2-methylpropyl) benzene-1,2-dicarboxylate
CAS Number	84-69-5
EC Number	201-553-2
Molecular weight	278.348 g/mol
Molecular formula	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ O ₄
Structural formula	<p>Figure 5: Structural formula of DiBP (Source: PubChem, https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov)</p>

4.2 Physico-chemical properties

DiBP is a colourless liquid with a slight ester odour; it has excellent heat and light stability.

The calculation factor for the gaseous phase is at 1013 mbar and 20 °C: 1 ml/m³ = 11.6 mg/m³.

Table 13: Physico-chemical data of DiBP (ILO-ICSC)

State at room temperature	liquid
Melting point	-37°C
Boiling point	320°C
Relative density at 25°C	1.04 g/cm ³
Vapour pressure at 20°C	0.01 Pa
Partition coefficient log K _{OW}	4.11
Water solubility at 20°C	1 mg/l

4.3 Area of application

DiBP is manufactured and/or imported in the European Economic Area in 1 - 10 tonnes per year. This substance is applied in articles, in formulation or re-packing, at industrial sites and in

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 104

manufacturing. The substance is used for example in coatings, fillers, putties, plasters, modelling clay, polymers, adhesives, sealants and paints (ECHA brief profile).

4.4 Classification

As per harmonised classification and labelling approved by the European Union, DiBP is classified as reprotoxic cat.1B (Hazard Statement Code H360 Df: may damage the unborn child and suspected of damaging fertility).

4.5 EU legislation and regulation

DiBP is a substance of very high concern (SVHC) and requires since 21 February 2015 authorisation before it can be used or placed on the market for use in the EU (Annex XIV of REACH). As substance which is classified as H360 Df DiBP is also forbidden in cosmetics.

According to COMMISSION REGULATION (EU) 2018/2005 of 17 December 2018 amending Annex XVII to Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council DiBP shall not be used as substance or in mixtures, individually or in any combination with DEHP, DnBP, or BBzP in a concentration equal to or greater than 0.1 % by weight of the plasticized material, in toys and childcare articles. In addition, DiBP shall not be placed on the market after 7 July 2020 in articles (including toys and childcare articles), individually or in any combination with the three phthalates DEHP, DnBP, and BBzP, in a concentration equal to or greater than 0.1 % by weight of the plasticized material in the article.

In the case of articles exclusively for industrial and agricultural use, or for open air use, the restriction should only apply to those articles containing plasticized material that comes into contact with human mucous membranes or into prolonged contact with the skin, because such contacts lead to exposure which poses risk to human health. The restriction does not apply i.e. to articles regulated by other Union legislation, such as materials and articles intended to come into contact with food within the scope of Regulation (EC) No 1935/2004 of the European Parliament and of the Council and Commission Regulation (EU) No 10/2011, medical devices within the scope of Council Directives 90/385/EEC or 93/42/EEC, or Directive 98/79/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council, or components for such devices, electrical and electronic equipment within the scope of Directive 2011/65/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council or the immediate packaging of medicinal products within the scope of Regulation (EC) No 726/2004 of the European Parliament and of the Council or of Directives 2001/82/EC or 2001/83/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council. The proposed restriction should also not apply to measuring devices for laboratory use or articles that form part of such devices.

4.6 Human exposure

4.6.1 General population

Because of its manifold uses (including household products) people have been exposed to DiBP via food and indoor environments. Based on a scenario-based approach, Wormuth et al. (2006) showed food to be the major source of DiBP exposure in all consumer groups (60% in infants and toddlers, >95% in teenagers and adults). In infants and toddlers, dust (30%) and contaminated indoor air (>8%) contributed also significantly to DiBP exposure.

In contrast, Koch et al. (2013) suggest with their fasting study an equal or even major contribution of other sources than diet to total DiBP exposure in adults. "There does not appear to be any relationship to diary recorded behaviours with metabolite concentrations. There are rises and

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 105

declines within each individual, but patterns are not similar between individuals. This suggests ongoing exposures throughout the fast although for most of the phthalates studied, the diary information provided few clues as to where this exposure may be coming from."

In the German Environmental Survey on children, significant correlations between phthalates in house dust and their metabolites in urine were found for DnBP, DiBP and BBzP (Kolossa-Gehring et al., 2011).

Also, CPSC CHAP has modelled DiBP exposures in 2014. Their external exposure models indicate to almost 10 times higher average DiBP exposures of toddlers compared to adults, and 6 times higher in the upper bound. Furthermore, comparisons of the external exposure models with intake calculations based on HBM data indicated that external exposure models might underestimate actual, overall body burdens measured by HBM. The full report and appendices are available at: <https://www.cpsc.gov/chap>.

Lorber et al (2017) used the data from chamber experiments with DnBP performed by Weschler et al. (2015, see below) for a modelling exercise linking dose models for inhalation and transdermal permeation with a simple pharmacokinetic model that predicted timing and mass of metabolite excretions. Their demonstration of the linked model designed to characterise general population exposures to typical airborne indoor concentrations of DnBP in the United States suggests that the combined pathways of inhalation and dermal uptake of airborne DnBP contribute a substantial fraction of exposure to DnBP in the general US population.

4.6.2 Workers

Information on occupational exposure to DiBP is scarce. Uses by professional workers, as described in the REACH registration dossier are the following: formulation of mixtures, use in coatings, polymer processing through low energy manipulations. DiBP is for example used by companies manufacturing rubber products (e.g. rubber gaskets for aerosol cans, inhalers and bottles) (Hines et al., 2009). In rubber processing, phthalate exposure could occur during compounding, mixing, milling, calendaring and curing (or vulcanising). Probably waste management (plastic waste sorting and plastic re-use) can also be an occupational setting where exposure can occur.

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 106

5 General toxicological profile

5.1 Human toxicokinetics and metabolism

The human toxicokinetics database for DiBP is very limited, especially for the dermal and inhalation route of exposure. Given the resemblances between DnBP and DiBP, it is assumed that the absorption fractions for both substances are similar. According to ECHA (2012) 100% absorption can be assumed for the oral and inhalatory path. For the dermal path newer studies with DnBP suggest 43-57% absorption (Doan et al., 2010, Hopf et al., 2014).

Weschler et al. (2015) investigated transdermal uptake, directly from air, of diethyl phthalate (DEP) and di(n-butyl) phthalate (DnBP) in humans and showed that dermal uptake directly from air can be a meaningful exposure pathway for DEP and DnBP. They performed chamber experiments at which in two 6 h sessions six males clad only in shorts were exposed either only dermally to DnBP while breathing clean air from a hood, or both dermally and via inhalation when exposed without a hood. Full urine samples were taken before, during, and for 48 h after leaving the chamber and measured for key DnBP metabolites. The data demonstrated high levels of DnBP metabolite excretions while in the chamber and during the first 24 h once leaving the chamber under both conditions. For DnBP, the median dermal uptake from air was 3.1 µg/(µg/m³ in air) compared with an inhalation intake of 3.9 µg/(µg/m³ in air).

Morrison et al. (2016) assessed the role of clothing in both accelerating and impeding dermal absorption. For this purpose, they performed chamber experiments with selected airborne phthalates, using a breathing hood to isolate dermal from inhalation uptake, followed by measurements of the urinary excretion of the relevant metabolites for an individual wearing clean clothes or air-exposed clothes and compared these results with dermal uptake for bare-skinned individuals. When compared against the average results for bare-skinned participants, clean clothes were protective, whereas exposed clothes increased dermal uptake for DEP and DnBP by factors of 3.3 and 6.5, respectively. This means even for non-occupational environments, wearing clothing that has adsorbed/absorbed indoor air pollutants can increase dermal uptake of SVOCs by substantial amounts relative to bare skin.

On the basis of previous experience in human phthalate metabolism, Koch et al. (2012) postulated and confirmed, for oral intake of DiBP, ester cleavage to mono-iso-butylphthalate (MIBP) and further oxidation at the side chain to 3OH-MIBP and 2OH-MIBP (see figure 2).

The study from Koch et al. (2012) provides basic data on human metabolism and toxicokinetics of DiBP. It comprised the ingestion of approximately 60 µg/kg bw of D4-DiBP (5.001 mg total) by an individual male (36 years, 87 kg body weight). The dose was taken up orally during breakfast, with DiBP dissolved in decaffeinated coffee served in an edible cup to ensure that the complete dose was ingested. The intake dose of 60 µg/kg bw was according to the authors about 50 times higher than the typical background adult exposure at that time. Urine samples were collected at 20 time points up to 48 h following the dosing of DiBP. Analysis of DiBP and its metabolites followed the method described by Koch et al. (2007b) with minor modifications according to Schütze et al. (2012), including enzymatic cleavage of the glucuronic acid conjugates and quantitative analysis with LC-MS/MS. The limit of quantification (LOQ; defined as a signal-to-noise ratio of six) was estimated to be 0.25 µg/L for the labelled analytes. The majority of the dose was excreted in the first 24 h (90.3 % of DiBP), while only < 1 % of the dose was excreted in urine on day 2. The simple monoester was the major metabolite (MIBP, 71 % of the dose applied), approximately 20 % was excreted as the oxidised side chain metabolite 2OH-MIBP.

Figure 6: Proposed human metabolism of DiBP (according to Koch et al., 2012)

All urinary DiBP metabolites reached peak concentrations between 2 and 4 h post-exposure, followed by a monotonic decline. For DiBP metabolites, MiBP had the shortest half-life (3.9 h), and the oxidised metabolites had somewhat longer half-lives (4.1 and 4.2 h).

Table 14: Maximum urinary concentration (C_{max}), time of maximum concentration (t_{max}) and estimated elimination half-lives for DiBP metabolites (Koch et al., 2012)

Parent compound	Metabolite	Maximum urinary concentration		Estimated half-life (h)
		C_{max} ($\mu\text{g/g}$ creatinine)	t_{max} (h)	
DiBP	MiBP	8,585	2.83	3.9
	2OH-MiBP	2,053	2.83	4.2
	3OH-MiBP ^a	76.2	2.83	4.1
	MCiPP	Not detected	Not detected	Not detected

^a Half-life is estimated based on samples with concentrations above the LOQ of 0.25 $\mu\text{g/l}$

The fractions of the DiBP metabolites excreted in urine (F_{ue}), as the molar fraction of the parent compound eliminated in urine following exposure, is given in table 3 for the initial 24 h and full 48 h following exposure.

Table 15: Estimated F_{ue} for DiBP metabolites (Koch et al., 2012)

Parent compound	Metabolite	Estimated F_{ue} (%)	
		0–24 h	0–48 h (total)
DiBP	MiBP	70.30	70.68
	2OH-MiBP	19.28	19.46
	3OH-MiBP	0.69	0.70
	MCiPP	Not detected	Not detected
	Σ DiBP metabolites	90.27	90.84

Albeit determined only on one volunteer, the conversion factor for DiBP/MiBP agrees well with the conversion factor of DnBP/MnBP established in the same study, and with conversion factors for DnBP/MnBP established in previous studies for DnBP (Anderson et al. 2001). There, based on 6-7 volunteers, and 2 dose levels (^{13}C -DnBP, 255 and 510 $\mu\text{g abs}$, being 10 times lower than in Koch et al., 2012) they report an F_{ue} for MnBP of 64-73% (mean 69%) with an RSD of 28-29%.

Evidence is given that DiBP and MiBP can be transferred to human breast milk (Fromme et al., 2011; Latini et al., 2009) and cross the placental barrier (Wittassek et al., 2009) similar to DnBP. Calafat et al. (2006) examined amniotic fluid and maternal urine concentrations of the di(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (DEHP) metabolite mono(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (MEHP) and the di-n-butyl phthalate (DnBP) metabolite monobutyl phthalate (MnBP) after administration of DEHP and DnBP during pregnancy. In the second study, DnBP was administered by oral gavage to pregnant Sprague-Dawley rats at doses of 0, 100, or 250 mg/kg/day starting on GD 13. Maternal urine and amniotic fluid were collected and analysed to determine the free and glucuronidated levels of MnBP. In urine, MnBP was mostly glucuronidated. By contrast, free MnBP predominated in amniotic fluid. Statistically significant differences were found in amniotic MnBP levels between animals within the same DnBP dose treatment group ($p < 0.0001$) and between animals in different dose treatment groups ($p < 0.0001$). Amniotic fluid MnBP levels increased with increasing DnBP doses, and high variability in maternal urinary levels of MnBP between rats was observed.

5.2 Toxicity

5.2.1 Human health effects

Radke et al. (2018) performed a systematic review of the epidemiology literature to identify the male reproductive effects associated with phthalate exposure. For each outcome, studies were evaluated using criteria defined a priori for risk of bias and sensitivity by two reviewers using a domain-based approach. For DiBP, the literature basis was limited and the exposure levels were often low which decreased the ability to observe an effect. As a result, there is only slight evidence of an association of DiBP exposure with time to pregnancy (referring to male exposure; Buck Louis et al., 2014), reduced anogenital distance (AGD) and semen parameters. The association with decreased testosterone levels is estimated to be moderate (see below).

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 109

However, all of these approaches are hampered by the transient nature of phthalate / DiBP exposure, often only single exposure measures, a very short window of utmost susceptibility (in humans end of 1st trimester), combined exposures (to other phthalates and other chemicals) and effects that often manifest only in much later life stages. Considering these circumstances, robust associations are hardly to expect.

There is some evidence that increased exposure to DiBP is associated with increased time to pregnancy, but the results are not statistically significant, and this evidence is considered slight (Radke et al., 2018). Three studies were described and evaluated that examined the association between DiBP (measured by MIBP) and AGD (Radke et al., 2018): Swan (2008), assessed by Radke et al., 2018 as low confidence study (details see there), and Swan et al. (2015) (assessed as medium confidence study) reported inverse associations, however not statistically significant and with a small effect size in the latter study. The study of Jensen et al. 2016, a medium confidence study with higher exposure levels, reported no association. Associations between MIBP exposure and one or more positive results for decreased semen quality are supported by two medium confidence studies (Bloom et al., 2015 (MIBP median: 4.4 ng/mL); Pan et al., 2015/2016 (MIBP median: 48 ng/mL)). But two other studies, the medium confidence study of Thurston et al. (2016) and the low confidence study of Den Hond et al. (2015), reported no association. Thus, there is only slight evidence for an association with the outcome “semen quality”. Regarding reduced testosterone levels after DiBP exposure, consistency in the results is observed from the studies by e.g. Chang et al. (2015), Pan et al. (2015) and Meeker and Ferguson (2014), which found decreased testosterone levels with increasing DiBP exposure (measured by MIBP), whereby the results in the first two studies were statistically significant. Only one low confidence study by Den Hond et al. (2015) reported no association, despite having higher exposure levels for MIBP than other studies in this assessment. Altogether, the evidence is considered moderate for the outcome “reduced testosterone level”.

Overall, the evaluation of Radke et al. (2018) allows the conclusion that there are hints of male reproductive effects associated with DiBP exposure, but the current knowledge based on human exposure to DiBP is not adequate to derive HBM-GVs directly based on human data, be it for the general population or for the workers.

Because of this, HBM-GVs are derived based on effects observed in animal studies.

5.2.2 Animal studies

In toxicity studies with repeated oral dose of DiBP, the male reproductive system was the main target and most work performed to clarify the mode of action of DiBP has been carried out in experimental tests studying developing male rats (ECHA, 2009). Therefore, this endpoint will be discussed in more detail below.

The adverse outcome following gestational exposure of rats to certain phthalates is known as the rat phthalate syndrome. It is well understood that this syndrome consisting in diverse effects on male offspring like reduced semen quality, testicular injury, decreased AGD, increased nipple retention, increased incidence of hypospadias, increased incidence of cryptorchidism, delayed puberty onset and changes in germ cell differentiation is caused by fetal androgen deficiency (Kortenkamp and Faust, 2010; CPSC, 2014; Health Canada, 2015a). It is highly plausible that interference with steroid hormone synthesis in fetal testis is responsible for the anti-androgenic effects. Most of the effects observed in experimental animals are considered to be biologically relevant to humans. According to the National Research Council (US) Committee on the Health Risks of Phthalates (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK215030/>;) “there is a remarkable overlap in response between the phthalate syndrome and the hypothesised human testicular

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 110

dysgenesis syndrome, except for responses for which rats are sexually dimorphic (retention of nipples)“.

The DiBP toxicity on male reproductive organs is described in the “Support document for identification of diisobutyl phthalate as SVHC because of its CMR properties” (ECHA, 2009). This document also emphasises that the monoester metabolite MiBP is considered as the active metabolite of DiBP (similar to all other active phthalates). A comprehensive literature search and assessment of the toxicity of DiBP was also performed by the U.S. CPSC (2014), Health Canada (2015b) and the Danish Environmental Protection Agency/ECHA with the ANNEX XV RESTRICTION REPORT – FOUR PHTHALATES (2016). Recently, the US-EPA (Yost et al. 2019) performed a systematic literature review gathering all available toxicity studies for DiBP/MiBP. A total of 19 studies are available exposing laboratory animals during gestation or postnatally, via gavage or food. Ten studies are prenatal developmental toxicity studies in rats (9) or in mice (1) (BASF 2007; Borch et al. 2006; Saillenfait et al. 2006; Saillenfait et al. 2008; Howdeshell et al. 2008; Hannas et al. 2011; Hannas et al. 2012; Furr et al. 2014; Saillenfait et al. 2017; Wang et al. 2017). The 9 other studies are postnatal developmental toxicity studies in rats (7) or in mice (2) (University of Rochester 1953; 1954; Oishi and Higara 1980b; 1980c; Foster et al. 1981/1982; Zhu et al. 2010; Sedha et al. 2015; Oishi and Higara 1980a; 1980d). An overview of all available studies and their summaries is provided in Annex I.

The authors identified and characterised outcomes following exposure of nonhuman mammalian animals to DiBP or the primary metabolite mono-iso-butyl phthalate (MiBP) within six broad hazard categories (male reproduction, female reproduction, development, liver toxicity, kidney toxicity, and cancer). They hereby confirmed and amended prior analyses. The studies were evaluated using criteria defined a priori for reporting quality, risk of bias, and sensitivity using a domain-based approach. Results were summarised according to outcome and life stage of exposure. The strength of evidence was grouped into robust, moderate, slight, indeterminate, or 'compelling evidence of no effect'. Most of the 19 toxicity studies in rats or mice which met the inclusion criteria reported data on multiple hazards.

The results of this systematic review provide *“robust evidence that DiBP causes male reproductive toxicity: Male rats and mice exposed to DiBP during gestation had decreased testosterone and adverse effects on sperm or testicular histology, with additional phthalate syndrome effects observed in male rats. There was also evidence of androgen-dependent and -independent male reproductive effects in rats and mice following peripubertal or young adult exposure to DiBP or MiBP, but confidence was reduced because of concerns over risk of bias and sensitivity in the available studies. There was also robust evidence that DiBP increased post-implantation loss and decreased pre- and postnatal growth. For other hazards, evidence was limited by the small number of studies, experimental designs that were suboptimal for evaluating outcomes, and study evaluation concerns such as incomplete reporting of methods and results. There was slight evidence for female reproductive toxicity and effects on liver, and indeterminate evidence for effects on kidney and cancer.”* Data gaps are seen in terms of studies on male reproductive effects following postnatal and adult exposure, and studies to characterise potential hormonal mechanisms in females.

As can be seen from table 4 “Evidence profile table for male reproductive effects of DiBP or MiBP” taken from Yost et al. (2019), the study of Saillenfait et al. (2008) was rated of high confidence for the outcomes male morphological development, reproductive organ weight, and testicular histology or sperm evaluation in F1 postnatal and adult male rats exposed during the gestational period. The outcomes testicular testosterone decrease and male morphological development observed in rat studies (oral exposure during gestational period) conducted by Borch et al. (2006), Saillenfait et al.

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 111

(2006), Howdeshell et al. (2008), Hannas et al. (2011), Hannas et al. (2012), Furr et al. (2014) and Saillenfait et al. (2017) were also considered as highly reliable.

Table 16: Evidence profile table for male reproductive effects of DiBP or MiBP (*indicates MiBP study) taken from Yost et al. (2019)

Outcome	Available studies	Factors that increase confidence	Factors that decrease confidence	Confidence judgement for outcome	Confidence judgement for overall hazard
Gestational (F1) Exposure	<p>High confidence: Borch et al., 2006 Furr et al., 2014 Hannas et al., 2011 Hannas et al., 2012 Howdeshell et al., 2008 Saillenfait et al., 2017</p> <p>Medium confidence: Wang et al., 2017</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consistency • Dose-response gradient • Effect size • Biological plausibility (support from mechanistic evidence) • Minimal concerns for bias and sensitivity 		<p>⊕⊕⊕ ROBUST</p> <p>A dose-related decrease in testicular T levels or production (up to -96% compared to control) was observed in all studies in rats and mice that evaluated this outcome. Several of these studies also demonstrated decreased testicular expression of genes and proteins in the steroidogenesis pathway in both rats and mice, which provides support for biological plausibility.</p>	<p>⊕⊕⊕ ROBUST</p> <p>Supported by consistency and coherence across outcomes, with mechanistic evidence (e.g. decreased testicular expression of steroidogenic enzymes and INSL3 in F1 males) providing support for biological plausibility. The greatest weight of evidence came from gestational exposure studies, whereas postnatal exposure studies were limited by risk of bias and sensitivity concerns.</p>
Male morphological development	<p>High confidence: Borch et al., 2006 Saillenfait et al., 2006 Saillenfait et al., 2008 Saillenfait et al., 2017</p> <p>Medium confidence: Wang et al., 2017</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consistency within rat studies • Dose-response gradient • Effect size • Biological plausibility • Minimal concerns for bias and sensitivity 		<p>⊕⊕⊕ ROBUST</p> <p>All rat studies observed a dose-related increase in effects consistent with decreased T and INSL3, including increased time to puberty, decreased AGD, nipple retention, cryptorchidism, non-scrotal testis, hypospadias, and exposed os penis. No effects on AGD were observed in mice (Wang et al., 2017).</p>	
Reproductive organ weight	<p>High confidence: Saillenfait et al., 2008</p> <p>Medium confidence: Wang et al., 2017</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dose-response gradient and minimal concern for bias and sensitivity in the study by Saillenfait et al., 2008 • Biological plausibility • Coherence with postnatal exposure studies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Few studies 	<p>⊕⊕○ MODERATE</p> <p>Decreased reproductive organ weights were observed in rats (Saillenfait et al., 2008), whereas a consistent trend in testis weight was not observed in mice (Wang et al., 2017); it is not clear whether this is related to differences in species or study designs. This effect is consistent with decreased T.</p>	
Testicular histology or sperm evaluation	<p>High confidence: Saillenfait et al., 2008</p> <p>Medium confidence: Borch et al., 2006 Wang et al., 2017</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consistency • Dose-response gradient • Effect size • Biological plausibility 		<p>⊕⊕⊕ ROBUST</p> <p>Adverse effects on the testis and/or sperm were observed in rats and mice, including a dose-related increased incidence of pathological lesions of the testis (Borch et al., 2006, Saillenfait et al., 2008), epididymal oligo- or azoospermia</p> <p>(Saillenfait et al., 2008), and decreased sperm concentration and motility (Wang et al., 2017).</p>	

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 112

Postnatal (Weanling or Peripubertal) Exposure	Testosterone	<p>Medium confidence: Oishi and Hiraga, 1980a Oishi and Hiraga, 1980c* Oishi and Hiraga, 1980d*</p> <p>Low confidence: Oishi and Hiraga, 1980b</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biological plausibility • Concerns for bias and sensitivity in some studies • Unexplained inconsistency 	<p>○○○ INDETERMINATE</p> <p>A dose-related increase in androgen levels was observed in two rat studies (Oishi and Hiraga, 1980b, c), whereas androgen levels were decreased or not changed in two mouse studies (Oishi and Hiraga, 1980a, d).</p>
	Reproductive organ weight	<p>Medium confidence: Oishi and Hiraga, 1980b Oishi and Hiraga, 1980c* U. Rochester, 1954</p> <p>Low confidence: Oishi and Hiraga, 1980a Oishi and Hiraga, 1980d* Foster et al., 1981* Zhu et al., 2010</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consistency within rat studies • Biological plausibility • Coherence with gestational exposure studies • Concerns for bias and sensitivity in some studies 	<p>⊕⊕⊕ ROBUST</p> <p>In rats, a dose-related decrease in absolute testis weight was consistently observed (Oishi and Hiraga, 1980b, c; Foster et al., 1981; University of Rochester, 1954). In weanling mice, Zhu et al. (2010) observed decreased absolute testis weight in the highest dose group. In peripubertal mice, Oishi and Hiraga (1980a, d) observed increased relative testis weight, which is considered a less reliable metric compared to absolute testis weight.</p>
	Testicular histology/sperm evaluation	<p>Low confidence: Oishi and Hiraga, 1980b Foster et al., 1981*</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consistency • Biological plausibility • Coherence with gestational exposure studies • Concerns for bias and sensitivity • Few studies 	<p>⊕⊕○ MODERATE</p> <p>Rats were found to have increased testicular atrophy (Foster et al., 1981) and decreased spermatocytes and spermatogonia (Oishi and Hiraga, 1980a).</p>

Thus, the database includes several high confidence gestational exposure studies (studies in both rats and mice) that assessed similar outcomes, including multi-dose studies in multiple rat strains. From Annex I follows that four studies (Saillenfait et al., 2006 and 2008; Howdeshell et al., 2008; Hannas et al., 2011) could in principle be considered relevant for the derivation of a point of departure (POD). Of these, the two studies in rats from Saillenfait et al. (2006 and 2008) both included multiple doses, conducted the exposure during the appropriate stage of gestation, and employed relatively large numbers of animals per dose (20-22 and 11-14). Because the study from Saillenfait et al. (2008) included more sensitive endpoints compared to the study published in 2006, it should be preferred. An overview of the relevant findings in Saillenfait et al. (2008) is provided in Table 5. The ECHA Risk Assessment Committee (RAC) initially agreed upon a LOAEL of 125 mg/kg bw/d as POD for the DNEL derivation based on the increased incidence of epididymis with azoospermia and the increased incidence of males with tubular degeneration-atrophy/hypoplasia of the testes, both observed at the lowest administered dose (125 mg/kg bw/d) and above (ECHA, 2012). However, these histopathological lesions arose according to Saillenfait et al. (2008) from the same litter, and should be interpreted with caution. In 2016 then, the authors of the Annex XV restriction report (ECHA, 2016) re-assessed the data base, and decided to disregard the Saillenfait et al. (2008) study because the lowest dose applied was considered too high for the derivation of a POD. Instead, the POD was chosen based on a read-across with DnBP. This option for use in the HBM-GV derivation is discussed below.

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 113

Table 17: Incidences of histological changes in testes, nipple retention, AGD reduction and age at preputial separation (Saillenfait et al. (2008), taken from the Annex XV restriction report, 2016)

Dose level (mg/kg bw/d)	DiBP					DnBP
	0	125	250	500	625	500
Incidences of tubular degeneration - atrophy/hypoplasia at PNW 11-12 (adult)	2/24 (8.3%)	2/20 (10.0%) But higher grade than control	7/28 (25.0%)	16/22 (72.7%)	20/20 (100.0%)	Not reported
Oligospermia + azoospermia	0/24 (0.0%)	2/20 (10.0%)	6/28 (21.4%)	12/22 (54.5%)	19/20 (95.0%)	Not reported
Incidences of nipple retention on PND 12-14	0/76 (0.0%)	0/78 (0.0%)	8/96 (8.3%)	47/79 (59.5%)	56/76 (73.7%)	44/59 (74.6%)
Incidences of nipple retention at PNW 11-12 (adult)	0/46 (0.0%)	0/40 (0.0%)	4/55 (7.3%)	24/44 (54.5%)	29/38 (76.3%)	29/39 (74.4%)
Male AGD PND 1 [mm] Difference compared with control (%)	2.55 ±0.17	2.44 ±0.15 (-4%)	2.28 ±0.30* (-11%)	2.02 ±0.13** (-21%)	1.98 ±0.16** (-22%)	1.94 ±0.17** (-24%)
Age at preputial separation[days]	46.9 ±1.5	45.1 ±1.6*	46.3 ±1.8	51.5 ±3.1**	49.8 ±3.2*	50.1 ±3.1**

AGD: anogenital distance; PNW: postnatal week; PND: postnatal day

* significantly different from control group, p<0.05

** significantly different from control group, p<0.01

The studies of Howdeshell et al. (2008), as well as Hannas et al. (2011) are particularly relevant as they describe dose-related decreases in fetal testosterone production in Sprague-Dawley rats thereby focusing on the event which is central for the effects observed for anti-androgenic phthalates. Decreases in fetal testosterone production were observed at doses from 300 mg/kg bw/d after gestational exposure by gavage respectively from GD 8 to 18 or GD 14 to 18. Gene expression studies in testes at GD 18 were carried out accompanying the study by Hannas et al. (2011). They showed that the expression of a number of steroidogenesis-related genes was downregulated by DiBP: StAR, Cyp11a1, 3bhsd, Cyp17a1, Scarb1, Insl3, Cyp11b1 and Rxrg. In addition, DiBP led to upregulation of the expression of Amhr2 and Sox9 (Hannas et al., 2011 and 2012). These data were applied for potency ranking of phthalates and Hannas et al. (2012) concluded that several phthalates including DiBP are affecting the same biological pathways. Due to the larger scope the study by Hannas et al. (2011) is preferred over the study by Howdeshell et al. (2008), a shortcoming of both studies is the small sample size together with the large intra-species variation of fetal testosterone production.

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 114

6 Selected biomarker for the HBM-GV proposal and analytical method

6.1 Choice of biomarker

6.1.1 For HBM measurements in the general population

Data on DiBP metabolism and excretion in humans are available (see chapter 2.1), although the data come from an investigation of only one male volunteer. The simple monoester MiBP and the oxidised side chain metabolite 2OH-MiBP are the main metabolites measured. Both have similar elimination half-lives. However, the simple monoester MiBP is by far the major metabolite retrieved in urine (70.3 % of the dose applied after 24 h, 70.68 % after 48 h, whereas approximately 20 % (19.28 % after 24 h) is allotted to 2OH-MiBP.

In addition, MiBP is specific to DiBP exposure and seems to be the metabolite responsible for the biological impacts of DiBP (ECHA, 2014). For those reasons, MiBP in urine is chosen as biomarker of exposure for biomonitoring of the general population.

6.1.2 For HBM measurements in the occupational field

Studies in the workplace reporting levels of metabolites in biological matrices are rare (Hines et al., 2009). The simple monoester MiBP is also proposed as biomarker to determine DiBP exposure in the occupational field.

6.2 Analytical method

The analytical method to quantify DiBP metabolites specifically is described by Koch et al. (2012 and 2017). It includes enzymatic hydrolysis with (arylsulfatase free) beta-glucuronidase followed by on-line high-performance liquid chromatography coupled to tandem mass spectrometry (HPLC–MS/MS). Internal isotope-labelled standards are used.

According to the deliverable D 9.2 of the EU project HBM4EU „Prioritised list of biomarkers, matrices and analytical methods for the 1st prioritisation round of substances”, MiBP is the metabolite of choice. All laboratories (N=10) participating in an inter-laboratory comparison were able to measure it, but strict internal and external contamination control is warranted (<https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/>). The limit of quantification for MiBP is 1 µg/l (Koch et al., 2017). Various other, rather similar analytical methodologies exist (e.g. from the CDC, Atlanta, or other trusted labs in the EU). Please check the method inventory referred to in the deliverable D 9.2.

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 115

7 Choice of the HBM-GVs derivation method

The existing database on biomonitoring data on DiBP does not allow for the derivation of HBM-GVs for the general population or for workers based on a relationship between human internal concentrations (parent compound or biomarker(s)) and health effects. Regarding workers, there is also neither evidence of a relationship between the atmospheric concentration of DiBP at the workplace and the urinary concentration of the biomarker of exposure, nor an OEL available. Thus, it has been investigated if HBM-GVs could be derived on the basis of other toxicologically relevant values derived from experimental studies with animals.

Factsheets summarising the data which are relevant to perform the derivation of the HBM-GVs, as described here below, are provided in section 10 of this report: section 10.1 summarises the information used for the HBM-GV derivation for the general population, and section 10.2 summarises the information used for the workers HBM-GV derivation.

7.1 Options to derive HBM-GVs for the general population based on results from studies with experimental animals - calculation of HBM-GVs using ECHA's DNEL

There is more than one option to decide on a POD/TRV from experimental animal studies for the derivation of HBM-GVs for DiBP, each of them with individual disadvantages:

1. Saillenfait et al. (2008) determined reduced male neonatal AGD, increased incidence of areolas/nipples retention in males and histopathologic testicular lesions as sensitive endpoints. The most sensitive endpoint is the testicular degeneration with oligospermia and azoospermia reported at all doses tested. A BMD modelling for this finding was performed by ANSES, but judged as inadequate. The PROAST report on this BMD modelling is presented in Annex II. Thus, for this endpoint there is only the possibility left to derive the TRV from the LOAEL (ECHA, 2012): $125 \text{ mg/kg bw/d} : 300 = 0.42 \text{ mg/kg bw/d}$ (AF 3 for LOAEL-NOAEL-, AF 10 for inter- and AF 10 for intra-species-extrapolation)

A further BMD analysis with the AGD dataset from this study conducted by ANSES (EFSA web-tool for BMD analysis, PROAST version 66.24) resulted in a BMD5%L90% of 37.6 mg/kg/d (model averaging approach). Extrapolation with a factor of 100 for inter- and intra-species differences lead to a comparable TRV-like value of 0.38 mg/kg bw/d.

2. The authors of the Annex XV restriction report (ECHA, 2016) however, decided to disregard the Saillenfait et al. (2008) study because the lowest dose applied was considered too high for the derivation of a POD. Instead, they performed a read across from the key toxicity study for the risk assessment of DnBP (Lee et al., 2004) arguing that DiBP has similar potency to DnBP for effects on decreasing fetal testosterone production which is central for the effects observed for antiandrogenic phthalates, and thus that the LOAEL of 125 mg/kg bw/day used previously as the starting point for DNEL derivation for DiBP does not seem to appropriately reflect this potency. A markedly lower LOAEL for DnBP (2 mg/kg bw/d) was used which refers to delayed germ cell development and persistent male mammary gland changes in rats (Lee et al., 2004). Because no studies on prepubertal spermatogenesis or adult mammary histology have been published for DiBP, the authors of the Annex XV restriction report reasoned that a LOAEL for DiBP of 2.5 mg/kg bw/d should be adequate as POD for DNEL setting, taking the slight potency difference of 25% between DnBP and DiBP into account (ECHA, 2016). In this argumentation it has to be considered, that the potency differences were determined at significantly higher doses (500 and 625 mg/kg bw/d), thus making the read across uncertain. If one used the read across POD, the relevant TRV would be 0.0083 mg/kg bw/d or 8.3 µg/kg

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 116

bw/d after applying a total assessment factor of 300 (accounting for LOAEL-NOAEL extrapolation as well as for inter- and intraspecies differences).

- Due to the critical role that testosterone plays during sexual differentiation of the male foetus in all mammals, suppression of fetal testicular testosterone production as measured by Hannas et al. (2011) was selected by Kortenkamp and Koch (2019) as the critical endpoint for mixture risk assessment of selected phthalates. Furthermore, they proposed to rely as much as possible on benchmark doses to overcome inexactly defined effect sizes associated with NOAELs and LOAELs. As a result, they calculated with the dataset from Hannas et al. (2011) a BMD5%L of 10.9 mg/kg/d (PROAST tool version 66.39) as POD for phthalate mixture risk assessment referring to male reproductive toxicity. By further application of an overall assessment factor of 100 for animal – human extrapolation, they derived a RfD AA of 100 µg/kg bw/d = 0.1 mg/kg bw/d. Being aware of the high intra- and interspecies variability of the fetal testosterone production, the BMR of 5% referring to this effect has its weaknesses, because it is difficult to assess which extent of decrease may actually lead to effects on fertility regarded as adverse.

Taking together on the one hand the approaches with their limitations mentioned above, on the other hand the comments received, it has been decided to choose the most conservative and therefore most protective approach to derive the HBM-GVs for the general population. This approach refers to the DNEL derived by ECHA (2016) by means of read across to DnBP and is assumed to cover a variety of effects associated with the phthalate syndrome in rats which have not all been addressed in experimental animal studies with DiBP.

7.1.1 Calculation of HBM-GVs for the general population

HBM-GVs are given for the single metabolite MiBP. Input parameters for the calculation are the molecular weights of DiBP and its measured metabolite MiBP, the F_{ue} of the measured metabolite after 24 h and the daily urine volume adjusted to the body weight (Kommission Human-Biomonitoring, 2007b). The 24 h values for excretion are preferred because a large proportion of DiBP is excreted in urine within 24 h (minimal difference to the 48h value) and the mass conservation equation was established considering an excretion during 24 h. This way the calculation for the general population and workers is consistent at this point. However, in principle, for dose extrapolations the total F_{ue} has to be used. This necessity becomes apparent for chemicals with longer elimination half times, but should generally be applied for general population monitoring (assuming constant exposure).

$$HBM - GV_{GenPop} = \frac{TRV \cdot \frac{MW(\text{Metabolite}) \cdot F_{ue}(\text{Metabolite})}{MW(\text{Substance})}}{\text{Daily urine volume adjusted to the bw}}$$

TRV = Toxicity Reference Value (here DNEL (ECHA, 2016): 0.0083 mg/kg bw/d); MW = Molecular Weight; F_{ue} = proportional urinary excretion factor; bw = body weight

DiBP has a molecular weight of 278.34 g/mol; the molecular weight of MiBP is 222.24 g/mol. The F_{ue} (24 h) for MiBP is 0.703 (see Table 3). The daily urine volume adjusted to the body weight is according to the current state of knowledge 0.03 l/kg bw/d for children and 0.02 l/kg bw/d for adults.

a) Bodyweight-related urine excretion rate adjustment (0.02 l/kg bw/d for adults):

$$HBM - GV_{GenPop} = \frac{0.0083 \text{ mg/kg bw/d} \cdot \left[\frac{222.24 \text{ g/mol(MiBP)} \cdot 0.7}{278.34 \text{ g/mol(DiBP)}} \right]}{0.02 \text{ l/kg bw/d}} = 0.23 \text{ mg/l (with } F_{ue} \text{ (48h): } 0.23 \text{ mg/l)}$$

The HBM-GV_{GenPop} referring to MiBP in human urine is therefore for adults: 0.23 mg/l

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 117

b) Bodyweight-related urine excretion rate adjustment (0.03 l/kg bw/d for children):

The HBM-GV_{GenPop} referring to MiBP in human urine is for children: 0.16 mg/l

7.2 Derivation of an HBM-GV for the occupational field based on an animal POD derived by read across to DnBP

A good reliable toxicity study performed via inhalation to examine the most representative exposure route to phthalates under occupational settings is not available. Thus, a relevant oral study had to be chosen for the derivation of an HBM-GV_{Worker}.

Following from the analysis by ECHA in 2016 the study from Lehmann et al. (2004) could be identified as key study for the derivation of an HBM-GV_{Worker} for DiBP by making use of a read across to DnBP²⁶ (Description of the Lehmann et al., 2004 study in Annex III). A NOEL of 10 mg/kg bw/d regarding the decrease in concentration of testicular testosterone in the foetus in combination with the reduction in the expression of key genes encoding proteins involved in cholesterol transport and steroidogenesis following *in utero* exposure (GD 12 to GD 19) was identified as POD from this study. Applying the estimated 25% potency difference factor between DnBP and DiBP (ECHA, 2016), a POD of 12.5 mg/kg bw/d for DiBP is obtained. Extrapolation of this POD of 12.5 mg/kg bw/d from rats to humans is performed by applying an interspecies AF of 10 taking into account the same route of exposure (oral intake). It is assumed that the bioavailability of DiBP, as for DnBP, is 100% after oral intake or inhalation and that the retrieved urinary total MiBP concentration does not differ according to the two exposure routes. An additional time scaling is not necessary, as a critical window of exposure is crucial for triggering the effects (the critical window of male sexual differentiation is approximately between GDs 14-18 in rats (Furr et al., 2014; Hannas et al., 2011, 2012) and around GD 43 for testicular differentiation in humans (i.e. during the middle of the 1st trimester of pregnancy in humans) (Magre and Jost, 1991; Shepard, 1998; INSERM, 2011)). The AF accounting for intraspecies differences (AF_H) is set to 10 and not 5 as usually done by default. The reason is that the unborn child has to be protected and there is no scientific reason to assume a difference between the unborn child of a working mother compared to the unborn child of a mother from the general population.

A "TRV-like" value of 0.125 mg/kg bw/d is derived by applying the overall AF of 100 to the POD of 12.5 mg/kg bw/d.

Bodyweight-related urine excretion rate adjustment (0.02 l/kg bw/d for adults):

$$\text{HBM - GV}_{\text{Worker}} = \frac{0.125 \text{ mg/kg bw/d} \cdot \left[\frac{222.24 \text{ g/mol (MiBP)} \cdot 0.7}{278.34 \text{ g/mol (DiBP)}} \right]}{0.02 \text{ l/kg bw/d}} = 3.5 \text{ mg/l}$$

²⁶ Criteria for selecting relevant studies: 1) Animal / human consistency of the effect considered, 2) Sensitivity of the effect: only studies showing the lowest reference dose (NOAEL or LOAEL) were retained and 3) Plausibility of the exposure scenario with regard to occupational exposure: mid or end of pregnancy, as well as perinatal condition of exposure to a classified reprotoxic substance at the workplace are not considered relevant to set the HBM-GV_{worker}, as EU Directive 92/85/EEC requires employers to assess the health and safety risks to pregnant and breastfeeding workers, and to change working conditions or offer suitable alternative work if needed. It is considered that pregnant women, as soon as they are aware of their pregnancy status, should be removed from their workstation if exposed to classified reprotoxic substances, as DiBP or DnBP. However, exposure during the 1st trimester of pregnancy is much likely to occur and, if relevant regarding occurrence of the critical effect, is considered for setting the HBM-GV_{worker}.

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 118

8 Level of confidence attributed to the derived HBM-GV_s

As mentioned in the HBM4EU concept paper to derive HBM-GVs, it is suggested to attribute a level of confidence (low, medium or high) to each calculated HBM-GV. The level of confidence should reflect the uncertainties identified during the elaboration of the value and could constitute a good incentive to revise later on values with estimated 'lower' level of confidence.

However, it should be specified that the levels of confidence proposed in this document are not determined according to an established recognised methodology, but rather rely on expert judgment regarding the reliability of the data and the calculation method used to derive the HBM-GV values.

The levels of confidence attributed to the HBM-GV_{GenPop} are set to '**low**'. Please, refer to the n°2 note of the factsheet presented in section 10.1 for explanation on this level of confidence appreciation.

The levels of confidence attributed to the HBM-GV_{worker} is set to '**low**'. Please, refer to the n° 2 note of the factsheet presented in section 10.2 for explanation on this level of confidence appreciation. Considering the high uncertainties related to the proposed HBM-GV_{worker}, it is not recommended to use it for the effective control of the health risks related to DiBP in the practice of occupational health. The EU reference value for workers that will be established for DiBP under T10.4 of HBM4EU should be rather used to assess whether the exposure at the workplace is adequately controlled or not²⁷.

²⁷ If a biomonitoring result is greater than an EU reference value for workers, it does not necessarily mean that ill health will occur, but it does indicate that control of exposure may not be adequate. Under these circumstances, employers will need to look at current work practices to see how they can be improved to reduce exposure.

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 119

9 Discussion

The derivation of the HBM-GVs is based on a read across approach to DnBP referring to known and relevant endpoints associated with the rat's phthalate syndrome. Essentially, the HBM-GVs were obtained by transforming the external DNEL for the general population and an adequate TRV-like value for workers into the internal metabolite doses, with the aim of more easily identifying from HBM data sets where exceedances occur.

The difference between the value for the adults of the general population and for workers is due to different exposure scenarios to be considered, thus determining the selection of the relevant study (see section 7.2, footnote 1).

One interesting option for refining the values in future might be a more accurate re-analyses of the Saillenfait et al. (2008) data, aggregated over the overall phthalate syndrome endpoints and evaluated over the different doses, thus reducing uncertainties inherent to the individual (morphological) endpoints. The NRC Phthalates and Cumulative Risk Assessment Report (NRC, 2008; App D) conducted such an analysis in which several continuous endpoints (all within the Phthalate syndrome) were modelled together. This approach goes beyond the possibilities of this project.

A PBPK or TK model for DnBP/DiBP enabling the extrapolation of the selected animal POD value to the corresponding human POD value, could also be helpful, thereby avoiding the default factor for the interspecies differences applied to the animal PODs.

For evaluating internal exposures to DiBP of the general population as well as of workers it is recommended to determine the metabolite MiBP in urine and to compare the analytical results with the HBM-GVs derived here above: 0.16 mg/l for children, 0.23 mg/l for adults of the general population, and 3.5 mg/l for workers.

Considering the uncertainties of the value's derivation and the likely variations in measured urinary concentrations resulting from the short biological half-lives of the metabolites, the HBM-GVs for DiBP have their limitations on the individual level and should be interpreted carefully in terms of the likelihood of an adverse health effect in an individual case. The derived HBM-GVs are most appropriate as a screening tool to evaluate population-based or workplace biomonitoring data in the context of possibly necessary risk management. Thus, exceedances should serve as a hint to avoid exposure sources in order to minimise possible risks.

It should be taken into account that due to the short half-life of excretion of the monoester metabolites, more reliable evaluations of the extent of exposure could be made based on morning or 24-h urine collections rather than spot samples. Moreover, a publication by Casas et al. (2018) quantifying the variability of biomarker measurements of many non-persistent chemicals during several time windows shows that for many of these compounds a few dozen samples are required to accurately assess exposure over periods encompassing several trimesters or months. Therefore, exposure misclassification is expected to be high.

On the other hand, on a population basis, spot and 24-h samples produce rather comparable results, e.g. see: Christensen et al. (2012) "Overall, spot urinary concentrations of DEHP metabolites and BPA have variability roughly comparable with corresponding 24-h average concentrations obtained from a comparable population, suggesting that spot samples can be used to characterise population distributions of intakes. However, the analysis also suggests that caution should be exercised when interpreting the high end of spot sample data sets."

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 120

For evaluating DiBP exposure in the occupational field, measurement of the biomarker of exposure MiBP at the end of the work shift should be performed. In addition, a measurement could be recommended prior to the work shift in order to assess non-occupational DiBP exposure (i.e. from food consumption) and therefore, better estimate the exposure resulting from occupational activities.

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 121

10 Factsheets

10.1 Factsheet on the HBM-GV for the general population

Compound: DiBP (Diisobutyl phthalate)			Factsheet General population
Parameter	Note	Value / descriptor	Comments
HBM-GV_{GenPop} and status			
HBM-GV _{GenPop}	1	MiBP in the urine: Children: 0.16 mg/l Adults: 0.23 mg/l	
Level of confidence	2	low	See note for explanation
HBM-GV _{GenPop} status	3	Provisional	See note for explanation
HBM-GV _{GenPop} year of issue	4	2019	
General Information			
CLP-INDEX-Nr.	5	607-623-00-2	
EC-Nr.	6	201-553-2	
CAS-Nr.	7	84-69-5	
Harmonised CLP classification	8	Category 1B reproductive toxicant - H360Df (May damage the unborn child; suspected of damaging fertility)	
Molar mass	9	278.34 g/mol	
Biomarker(s)			
Identification	10	Urinary MiBP	
Molar mass of biomarker	11	222.24 g/mol	
Toxicokinetic data			
Key study for TK data	12	Koch et al., 2012	
Type of study	13	Human	1 volunteer, 1 dose
Route of exposure	14	Oral single dose: 60 µg/kg bw (in total 50 mg)	
Half-life of selected biomarker(s)	15	MiBP = 3.9 h	Koch et al., 2012
Factor for metabolic conversion (F _{ue})	16	F _{ue} (24 h) = 0.7 (urinary MiBP)	Koch et al., 2012
Derivation method and calculation			
Derivation method	17	Based on a DNEL	ECHA, 2016
Establishment DNEL	18/19		Key study: Lee et al., 2004 Total AF = 300, read across 25 % potency difference
HBM-GV_{GenPop}			
Calculated HBM-GV _{GenPop}	20	Children:	Calculated with the following urine volumes: Children (6 to 13 years):

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 122

	$\frac{0.0083 \text{ mg/kg bw/d} \cdot \left[\frac{222.24 \text{ g/mol(MiBP)} \cdot (0.7)}{278.34 \text{ g/mol(DiBP)}} \right]}{0.03 \text{ l/kg bw/d}}$ <p>= 0.16 mg/l</p> <p>Adults:</p> $\frac{0.0083 \text{ mg/kg bw/d} \cdot \left[\frac{222.24 \text{ g/mol(MiBP)} \cdot (0.7)}{278.34 \text{ g/mol(DiBP)}} \right]}{0.02 \text{ l/kg bw/d}}$ <p>= 0.23 mg/l</p>	0.03 l/kg bw/d Adults: 0.02 l/kg bw/d
Additional Comments		

Explanation of notes:

1) HBM-GV_{GenPop}: rounded numerical value of the HBM-GV_{GenPop} in mg/l

2) Level of confidence of the HBM-GV_{GenPop}: reflects the reliability of the proposed HBM-GV. The level of confidence takes into account the various uncertainties underlying the derivation of the HBM-GV (e.g. reliability of the key study used to derive the toxicity reference value (TRV), uncertainties related to the calculation of the TRV, to toxicokinetic data on the substance of interest, to the extrapolations and calculation of the final HBM-GV). Attribution of a global level of confidence for the proposed DiBP HBM-GV_{GenPop} is suggested, considering:

- the nature and quality of the DiBP epidemiological and toxicological data: DiBP database on human studies is very limited, database on animal studies is more extended but however limited to oral rodent studies; high degree of uncertainty regarding NOAEL/LOAEL identification for DiBP, especially because no tests with an exposure scenario relevant for the general population have been performed with concentrations below 100 mg/kg bw/d; determination of the factor for metabolic conversion (F_{ue}) is based on a study with 1 volunteer and 1 dose (see note 12) and steady-state is assumed by using a mass-balance equation, data are missing to ensure that metabolism and sensitivity is similar in adults and children → **low**

- the critical endpoint and mode of action: the evidence of DiBP anti-androgenic effects is acknowledged and based on numerous animal studies. Evidence for these effects in humans is available from the scientific literature; however, read-across approach from DnBP was used as no test with doses below 100 mg/kg bw/d for DiBP were available → **medium**

- the selected key study: Lee et al. study is an animal toxicity study; unclear whether conducted according to OECD guidelines, but was evaluated by ECHA as reliable without restriction → **medium**

- **the chosen POD**: a LOAEL for DnBP was identified from Lee et al (2004), and based on a read across approach, a potency difference factor of 25% was applied to obtain a LOAEL for DiBP → **low**

- the extrapolation for DNEL setting: the LOEAL-NOAEL-, inter- and intra-species extrapolations: the estimated NOAEL for DiBP is extrapolated from a LOEAL (AF = 3), across species (AF_A = 10) and according to intra individual variability (AF_H = 5) → **low**

Altogether the global level of confidence for the DiBP HBM-GVs in the general population is set to '**low**'.

3) HBM-GV_{GenPop} status: the status value is fixed to 'provisional', thereby reflecting that this value could be revised later on in the project, if uncertainties underlying the data could be reduced. For example, the uncertainties of the TK data could be reduced by means of a validated PBPK model for DiBP. A higher level of confidence attributed to the value would lead to a 'confirmed' value status.

4) HBM-GV_{GenPop} year of issue: year of setting the HBM-GV_{GenPop} in the HBM4EU workframe.

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 123

5) CLP Number: according to Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 on classification, labelling and packaging (CLP) of substances and mixtures, implementing the globally harmonised system of chemical classification or GHS
http://guidance.echa.europa.eu/docs/guidance_document/clp_introduutory_en.pdf

6) EC Number: under European Inventory of Existing Commercial chemical Substances (EINECS), ELINCS (European List of Notified Chemical Substances) in support of Directive 92/32/EEC, the 7th amendment to Directive 67/548/EEC, NLP (No-Longer Polymers), see: ESIS: European chemical Substances Information System:
https://web.archive.org/web/20131106181548if_/http://esis.jrc.ec.europa.eu/

7) CAS Number: collection of disclosed chemical compound information by Chemical Abstracts Service. Almost all molecule databases can be searched by CAS Registry Number.

8) Harmonised CLP classification: CLP classification including CMR and other health relevant effects. In the case that classification is not harmonised, this should be stated. For self-classifications by industry the ECHA- CLP inventory can be searched at: <http://echa.europa.eu/web/guest/information-on-chemicals/cl-inventory-database>

9) Molar mass: mass of DiBP per amount of this substance expressed in g/mol

10) Biomarker identification: the biomarker identified as appropriate for a diagnosis of exposure to DiBP is the monoester MiBP (Koch et al., 2012), it has been taken into consideration for the HBM GV derivation.

11) Molar mass of the biomarker: mass of the selected biomarker (expressed in g/mol)

12) Study for TK data: Koch et al., 2012. Di-n-butyl phthalate (DnBP) and diisobutyl phthalate (DiBP) metabolism in a human volunteer after single oral doses. Arch Toxicol 86:1829–1839.

13) Type of study: human oral study

14) Route of exposure: oral single administration

15) Half-life of biomarker: estimated elimination half-live for MiBP

16) Factor for metabolic conversion (F_{ue}): fractional urinary excretion ratio of biomarker relative to the oral dose of DiBP taken up.

17) Derivation method: the existing database on DiBP does not allow for the derivation of HBM-GVs from human data (i.e. based on a relationship between concentration of a DiBP biomarker and health effects). Therefore, a derivation method based on an established DNEL is used.

18/19) DNEL development: A LOAEL of 2 mg/kg bw/d for DnBP was selected from the developmental study performed by Lee et al. (2004) referring to the observed delayed germ cell development and persistent male mammary gland changes. 25 % potency difference for DiBP were taken from Saillenfait et al., 2008.

Assessment factors (AF): 3 for LOAEL - NOAEL-extrapolation, 10 for intraspecies differences, 10 for interspecies differences

20) HBM-GVs: Ideally, the HBM-GVs should refer to a complete 24-hour urine sample, stating the quantity of a substance in µg/d, especially if the monitored substance has a short half-life of excretion. For reasons of simplification, in accordance with the approach described in the concept document, the excretion is referred to a body weight-related urine excretion of 30 ml/kg bw/d for children and 20 ml/kg bw/d for the remaining subgroups of the population.

The resulting HBM-GV_{GenPop} for MiBP in urine are as follows:

Children: 0.16 mg/l,

Adults including adolescents and women in child-bearing age: 0.23 mg/l

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 124

10.2 Factsheet on the HBM-GV for workers

Compound : DiBP (Diisobutyl phthalate)			Factsheet Workers
Parameter	Note	Value / descriptor	Comments
HBM-GV_{Worker} and status			
HBM-GV _{Worker}	1	MiBP in the urine, at the end of the working shift: 3.5 mg/l	
Level of confidence	2	low	See note for explanation
HBM-GV _{Worker} status	3	Provisional	See note for explanation
HBM-GV _{Worker} year of issue	4	2019	
General Information			
CLP-INDEX-Nr.	5	607-623-00-2	
EC-Nr.	6	201-553-2	
CAS-Nr.	7	84-69-5	
Harmonised CLP classification	8	Category 1B reproductive toxicant - H360Df (May damage the unborn child; suspected of damaging fertility)	
Molar mass	9	278.34 g/mol	
Biomarker(s)			
Identification	10	Urinary MiBP	
Molar mass of biomarker	11	222.24 g/mol	
Toxicokinetic data			
Key study for TK data	12	Koch et al., 2012	
Type of study	13	Human	1 volunteer, 1 dose
Route of exposure	14	Oral single dose: 60 µg/kg bw (in total 50 mg)	
Half-life of selected biomarker(s)	15	MiBP: 3.9 h	Koch et al., 2012
Factor for metabolic conversion (F _{ue})	16	F _{ue} (24 h) = 0.7 (urinary MiBP)	Koch et al., 2012
Derivation method and calculation			
Derivation method	17	Based on an animal POD and read across approach to DnBP	Annex XV restriction report (ECHA, 2016)
Read-across approach on animal POD	18	Oral NOEL for DnBP = 10 mg/kg bw/d Application of potency difference of 25% (as set by ECHA (2016), based on results from the Saillenfait et al. (2008) study) -> oral animal POD for DiBP = 12.5 mg/kg/d	Key study for POD setting: Lehmann et al., 2004 (Developmental toxicity study) Critical endpoint: Reduction of testosterone concentrations in fetal rat testes in combination with the reduction in the expression of key genes encoding proteins involved in cholesterol transport and steroidogenesis after <i>in</i>

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 125

			<i>utero</i> exposure from GD12 to GD19
TRV-like value	19	0.125 mg/kg bw/d	Global AF of 100 (AF _A for interspecies differences: 10; AF _H for intraspecies differences: 10)
HBM-GV_{Worker}			
Calculated HBM-GV_{Worker}	20	Worker $\frac{0.125 \text{ mg/kg bw/d} \cdot \left[\frac{222.24 \text{ g/mol(MiBP)} \cdot 0.7}{278.348 \text{ g/mol(DiBP)}} \right]}{0.02 \text{ l/kg bw/d}}$ = 3.5 mg/l	Calculated with the following urine volume: Adults: 0.02 l/kg bw/d
Additional Comments: sampling at the end of the working shift			

Explanation of notes:

1) HBM-GV_{Worker}: rounded numerical value of the HBM-GV_{Worker} in mg/l

2) Level of confidence of the HBM-GV_{Worker}: reflects the reliability of the proposed HBM-GV. The level of confidence takes into account the various uncertainties underlying the derivation of the HBM-GV (e.g. reliability of the key study used to derive the toxicity reference value (TRV), uncertainties related to the calculation of the TRV, to toxicokinetic data on the substance of interest, to the extrapolations and calculation of the final HBM-GV). Attribution of a global level of confidence for the proposed DiBP HBM-GV_{Worker} is suggested, considering:

- the nature and quality of the DiBP epidemiological and toxicological data: DiBP database on human studies is very limited, database on animal studies is more extended but however limited to oral rodent studies; high degree of uncertainty regarding a NOEL/LOAEL identification for DiBP, especially because no tests with concentrations below 100 mg/kg bw/d have been performed; the determination of the factor for metabolic conversion (F_{ue}) is based on a study with 1 volunteer and 1 dose (see note 12) and steady-state is assumed by using a mass-balance equation → **low**
- the critical endpoint and mode of action: the evidence of DiBP anti-androgenic effects is acknowledged and based on numerous animal studies, however the critical effect selected refers to DnBP read across. Evidence for anti-androgenic effects in humans is available from the scientific literature → **medium**
- the selected key study: the study by Lehmann et al. 2014 is an oral animal toxicity study; an inhalation study would have been preferred; the key study has some methodological shortcomings according OECD guidelines 414 (Prenatal Developmental Toxicity Study)²⁸, however was regarded as reliable by ECHA, 2014²⁹ → **medium**
- the selected POD: a NOEL for DnBP was identified from Lehmann et al (2004) and based on a read across approach, a potency difference factor of 25% was applied to obtain a NOEL for DiBP → **low**
- the route-to-route, inter- and intra-species extrapolations: due to lack of data, it is assumed that oral intake is generating the same amount of the selected biomarker than inhalation (the most likely exposure route for workers); the estimated NOEL for DiBP is extrapolated across species (AF_A = 10) and according to intra individual variability (AF_H = 5) → **low**

Altogether the global level of confidence for the DiBP HBM-GVs in the occupational field is set to '**low**'.

3) HBM-GV_{Worker} status: the status value is fixed to 'provisional', thereby reflecting that this value could be revised later on in the project, if uncertainties underlying the data could be reduced. For example, the uncertainties of the TK data

²⁸ See: [http://www.oecd.org/officialdocuments/publicdisplaydocumentpdf/?cote=ENV/JM/MONO\(2018\)18&doclanguage=en](http://www.oecd.org/officialdocuments/publicdisplaydocumentpdf/?cote=ENV/JM/MONO(2018)18&doclanguage=en)

²⁹ European Chemicals Agency (ECHA), ECHA, 2014. Support document to the opinion of the member state committee for identification of diisobutyl phthalate (DIBP)

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 126

could be reduced by means of a validated PBPK model for DiBP. A higher level of confidence attributed to the value would lead to a 'confirmed' value status.

- 4) HBM-GV_{Worker} year of issue: year of setting the HBM-GV_{Worker} in the HBM4EU workframe.
- 5) CLP Number: according to Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 on classification, labelling and packaging (CLP) of substances and mixtures, implementing the globally harmonised system of chemical classification or GHS
http://guidance.echa.europa.eu/docs/guidance_document/clp_introduutory_en.pdf
- 6) EC Number: under European Inventory of Existing Commercial chemical Substances (EINECS), ELINCS (European List of Notified Chemical Substances) in support of Directive 92/32/EEC, the 7th amendment to Directive 67/548/EEC, NLP (No-Longer Polymers), see: ESIS: European chemical Substances Information System:
https://web.archive.org/web/20131106181548if_/http://esis.jrc.ec.europa.eu/
- 7) CAS Number: collection of disclosed chemical compound information by Chemical Abstracts Service. Almost all molecule databases can be searched by CAS Registry Number.
- 8) Harmonised CLP classification: CLP classification including CMR and other health relevant effects. In the case that classification is not harmonised, this should be stated. For self-classifications by industry the ECHA- CLP inventory can be searched at: <http://echa.europa.eu/web/guest/information-on-chemicals/cl-inventory-database>
- 9) Molar mass: mass of DiBP per amount of this substance expressed in g/mol
- 10) Biomarker identification: the biomarker identified as relevant for interpreting exposures to DiBP through HBM measurement is the monoester MiBP retrieved in urine.
- 11) Molar mass of the biomarker: mass of the selected biomarker (expressed in g/mol)
- 12) Study for TK data: Koch et al., 2012. Di-n-butyl phthalate (DnBP) and diisobutyl phthalate (DiBP) metabolism in a human volunteer after single oral doses. Arch Toxicol 86:1829–1839.
- 13) Type of study: human oral study
- 14) Route of exposure: oral single administration
- 15) Half-life of biomarker: estimated elimination half-lives for MiBP
- 16) Factor for metabolic conversion (F_{ue}): fractional urinary excretion ratio of selected biomarker MiBP relative to the oral dose of DiBP taken up.
- 17) Derivation method: the existing database on DiBP does not allow for the derivation of HBM-GVs from human data (i.e. based on a relationship between concentration of a DiBP biomarker and health effects). Therefore, a derivation method based on extrapolating an animal POD is used. In addition, a read-across approach based on comparison of the DnBP and DiBP potency on reprotoxic endpoints is used.
- 18) Animal POD and read-across approach: A NOEL of 10 mg/kg bw/d for DnBP was selected from the developmental study of Lehmann et al. (2004, referring to the observed reduction of testosterone concentrations in rat fetal testes in combination with the reduction in the expression of key genes encoding proteins involved in cholesterol transport and steroidogenesis after *in utero* exposure from GD12 to GD19). The 25 % potency difference between DiBP and DnBP as assessed by ECHA, is based on the potency difference between these two phthalates observed in Saillenfait et al., 2008. The POD for DiBP obtained is 12.5 mg/kg bw/d.
- 19) TRV-like value calculation: a total AF of 100 is applied to the DiBP estimated NOEL (10 for intraspecies differences (workers), 10 for interspecies differences).
- 20) HBM-GV_{worker} calculation: a mass-balance equation is used to calculate the HBM-GV_{worker}, considering a body weight-related urine excretion of 0.02 l/kg bw/d for adults.

The resulting HBM-GV_{Worker} for MiBP in urine measured at the end of the working shift is **3.5 mg/l**.

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 127

11 References

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WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 128

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WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 129

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WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 131

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D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 132

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D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 133

12 Annex

12.1 Annex 1

Several studies on developmental toxicity of DiBP have been summarised in the SVHC dossier (Borch et al., 2006; Saillenfait et al., 2006 and 2008; Howdeshell et al., 2008; Hodge 1954; Oishi and Higara 1980a; 1980b; 1980c; 1980d; Foster et al., 1981). The underneath section providing summaries of the latter studies, shown in italics, is a direct copy of the SVHC report (ECHA 2009; Section 5.6 and 5.9), where an overview of the available studies on this end-point was provided. After the dossier, several new studies were published (Hannas et al., 2011; Hannas et al., 2012; Furr et al., 2014; Saillenfait et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2017; Sedha et al., 2015; Zhu et al., 2010). Study summaries for these studies were also provided, not in italics, for a complete overview of all available studies to date.

Effects on fertility

Whereas no fertility studies (one-, two- or multigeneration studies) could be identified in the current toxicological data base for DiBP, adverse effects on male reproductive organs (testicular toxicity) and on spermatogenesis had been observed during repeated dose toxicity studies with DiBP and with MiBP at relatively high dosages, indicating that the monoester MiBP to which DiBP is hydrolysed by human and rat hepatic esterases (Mentlein and Butte, 1989) should be considered an active metabolite.

Developmental toxicity

Prenatal developmental toxicity studies

In a study (Borch et al., 2006; cited in: Boberg et al., 2008) mated female Wistar rats (n=8/group) were gavaged from GD 7 until GD 19 or until GD 20/21 with either vehicle (corn oil) or 600 mg/kg bw/d of DiBP (purity 99%), when they were sacrificed and their male offspring evaluated. At sacrifice on GD 19 five dams from the control and six dams from the treated group provided litters and at sacrifice on GD 20/21 six dams from the treated group provided litters. Anogenital distance (AGD) was measured in all fetuses, fetuses were decapitated and their trunk blood collected, and from males testes removed for histopathology and for immunohistochemistry, for measurement of testosterone production ex vivo, respectively measurement of testosterone content. Administration of DiBP resulted in statistically significant reduction in AGD in male pups (and increased AGD in female pups) at GD 20/21 together with 10 % reduction in bodyweights of male and female fetuses and in a significant reduction in testicular testosterone production and testicular testosterone content in the male offspring at GD 20/21. Histopathological investigations revealed testes pathology as seen with other phthalates, in particular clustering of small Leydig cells on GD19 or GD20/21 and vacuolisation of Sertoli cells on GD 20/21.

Immunohistochemistry revealed reduced staining for StAR and P450scc, indicative for reduced expression of these two proteins and thereby reduced capacity of the testicular steroid synthesis. Further results from this study were reported by Boberg et al. (2008), who quantified levels of insulin, leptin, MCP1, IL-1B, PAI-active, IL6, and TNF α in pooled samples of plasma. In addition, livers, adrenals and testes tissue from the male fetuses and ovaries from the females had been used for gene expression (mRNA expression) analysis and for steroid hormone measurements (oestradiol, testosterone). Treatment with DiBP had resulted at GD 21 in statistically significant reduction of protein levels of insulin and of leptin, whereas no alterations were seen in plasma levels of MCP1, IL-1B, PAI-1 active, IL6 or TNF α . Gene expression analysis on genes involved in

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 134

steroid synthesis revealed reduced testicular mRNA levels of SR-B1, StAR, P450c17, P450scc and Insl-3 at GD 19 and GD 21. In addition, testicular SF-1 mRNA levels were reduced on GD 19, whereas no alterations were seen for testicular mRNA levels of aromatase or PBR. In the ovaries of DiBP treated animals an increase in mRNA levels of aromatase was revealed at GD 21. Gene expression analysis on PPAR α and on PPAR γ revealed significantly reduced mRNA levels of PPAR α in livers and testes of DiBP exposed males at GD 19 but not at GD 21. PPAR γ mRNA levels were very low in both testes as well as livers and appeared unaltered by DiBP treatment. In the ovaries of DiBP treated animals no alterations were seen in the expression of ER α , ER β , PPAR α , or PPAR γ . Besides reductions in mRNA levels there were also indications for reduced protein levels of P450c17 and of PPAR γ in the Leydig cells of DiBP treated animals at GD 19 and GD21 (evidenced from reduced immunostaining intensity).

The study by Borch et al. (2006) received an overall high confidence rating by Yost et al. (2019). However, for derivation of an HBM guidance value this study is considered of lower relevance due to the dosing regimen (one highly dosed group compared to controls).

In a guideline-conform prenatal toxicity study on Sprague-Dawley rats, DiBP was administered to pregnant animals (23-24 animals per treatment group) by gavage at doses of 0 (olive oil), 250, 500, 750 and 1000 mg/kg bw/d on GD 6-20 (**Saillenfait et al., 2006**). Endpoints included in addition were determination of the degree of transabdominal testicular migration (TTM). There were no maternal deaths. Signs of transient maternal toxicity were observed, as evidenced by reduction in body weight gain, at the beginning of treatment (GD 6-9) at 500 mg/kg bw/d and higher doses, however, overall weight gain corrected for gravid uterus was not different from controls at the end of gestation. No changes could be observed for maternal food consumption, pregnancy rate or number of implantations. The incidences of resorptions were statistically significantly increased to 28% at 750 mg/kg bw/d and to 59% at 1000 mg/kg bw/d. Mean fetal body weight was statistically significantly reduced at 500 mg/kg/d and higher doses amounting to a decrease of 24% -26% at 1000 mg/kg/d in comparison to controls. The incidence of total external malformations (neural tube closure defects, anophthalmia) and of total visceral malformations (urinary tract and vascular defects) was statistically increased at 750 and 1000 mg/kg bw/d. Skeletal evaluations revealed malformations primarily of the axial column with the incidences of fused sternebrae statistically significantly increased at 750 and 1000 mg/kg bw/d and variations (delayed ossification and supernumerary ribs) at 750 and 1000 mg/kg bw/d with supernumerary ribs in 95% of the foetuses of the 1000 mg/kg group. Visceral variations involved mainly the urinary tract with statistically significantly increased incidences of ureter variations in the 1000 mg/kg group and the male reproductive system. Unilateral or bilateral undescended testes occurred at 500 mg/kg/d and was significantly increased at 750 mg/kg/d (in 30/55 male foetuses and in 16/20 litters) and at 1000 mg/kg bw/d (in 30/34 male foetuses and in 16/17 litters). In addition, the degree of transabdominal descent was significantly impaired at 500 mg/kg/d with about two third of the testes located in the upper half of the abdominal cavity at the 1000 mg/kg dose group. Thus, it appeared that alterations of the male reproductive system occurred at lower doses than those producing structural malformations/variations and embryotoxicity. No evidence of embryo or fetal effects was found at the 250 mg/kg dose level. Therefore, a NOAEL/developmental toxicity of 250 mg/kg/d can be derived from the study.

The study by Saillenfait et al. (2006) received an overall high confidence rating by Yost et al. (2019). For derivation of an HBM guidance value this study may be suitable (high number of animals per dose group, four dosing groups compared to control).

In a study on Sprague-Dawley rats, which was performed to determine whether in utero exposure to DiBP would induce permanent and dose-responsive alterations of male reproductive

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 135

development, DiBP was administered to pregnant animals (11-13 animals per treatment group) by gavage at doses of 0 (olive oil), 125, 250, 500, and 650 mg/kg bw/d on GD 12-21 (**Saillenfait et al., 2008**). Doses were based on an unpublished preliminary study in which 625 mg DiBP /kg bw/d on GD 12-21 caused reproductive tract malformations in male offspring and had no effects on litter size or pup survival. Litters of the definite study were examined as soon as possible after birth to determine the number of viable and stillborn pups. Pup body weights were recorded on PND 1, 4, 7, 14 and 21.

AGD was measured on PND1 and litters culled to 10 pups on PND 4. All pups were examined for the presence of areola and/or nipples on the ventral surface of the thorax on PND 12-14. At weaning on PND 21 three to four male pups from each litter were randomly selected and retained and unselected pups sacrificed and submitted to internal examination. After weaning the dams were sacrificed and the number of implantations recorded from their uteri. All retained males were examined for preputial separation (PPS) and individual body weights recorded at acquisition. Adult males were necropsied on PND 76-86 (two males in each litter) or on PND 111-122 (the remaining males in each litter). They were examined for the presence of areolas and/or nipples on the ventral surface of the thorax, for gross abnormalities of external and internal genitalia, and for position of testes. Testes, epididymis, seminal vesicles (with the coagulating glands and seminal fluid), and prostate were weighed. Histopathology was conducted on testes and epididymis of all DiBP animals necropsied on PND 76-88. No differences in maternal body weight gain were observed between the controls and the treatment groups. All dams delivered live pups. Post-DiBP implantation loss, litter size, sex ratio, and pup survival to PND 4 and PND 21 were unaffected by treatment. AGD measured on PND 1 was dose-dependently significantly reduced in male pups from 250 mg DiBP/kg bw/d to the higher doses with or without adjustment for body weight. The decrease amounted to 11% at 250 mg DiBP/kg bw/d and 22% at 625 mg DiBP/kg bw/d, compared to controls. AGD of females was not affected at any dose. Pup body weight at PND 1 of both sexes was statistically significantly decreased at 625 mg DiBP/kg bw/d, and remained lower in comparison to controls in the male pups at weaning. During the post weaning period mean body weights of the offspring were lower than controls at 500 and 625 mg DiBP/kg bw/d (6-8% and 10-12%, respectively). On PND 12-14 or at adult necropsy retained areolas and/or nipples were apparent in males at 250 mg DiBP/kg bw/d and their incidence increased with dose. No such effects were observed in animals from vehicle controls or the 125 mg DiBP/kg bw/d treated group. Acquisition of PPS was delayed by approximately 4 days at 500 mg DiBP/ kg bw/d. Evaluation of PPS was precluded in half of the males at the high dose by presence of hypospadias. Mature males displayed severe malformations (hypospadias with exposed os penis in the more severely affected animals, and non-scrotal testis) at the two high doses. Non-descended testes were always located in the inguinal or supra-inguinal area; none were in the intra-abdominal position. Markedly underdeveloped (less than 10% of control weight) or absent testes and/or epididymis were seen in 2%, 16% (7 males from 5 litters), and 13% (5 males from 4 litters) of the animals in the 250, 500 and 625 mg/kg bw/d dose groups. At sacrifice (PND 76-86, resp. PND 111-122) organ weights of the testes, epididymis, seminal vesicles and prostate were significantly reduced (with or without body weight as covariate) at 500 and 625 mg DiBP/kg bw/d. These reductions amounted to 39-59% for the testes and the epididymis, and 28-33% for the seminal vesicles and the prostate. Histological examinations (see Table 5) revealed testicular damage in all DiBP treated groups with moderate or severe degeneration of seminiferous tubules (including Sertoli cell only tubules). The lesions were uni- or bilateral and associated with oligospermia or total azoospermia in the corresponding epididymis. Based on these observations a NOAEL/developmental toxicity could not be determined. Therefore, a LOAEL/developmental toxicity of 125 mg DiBP/kg bw/day can be derived from this study.

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 136

The study by Saillenfait et al. (2008) received an overall high confidence rating by Yost et al. (2019). For derivation of an HBM guidance value this study may be suitable (high number of animals per dose group, four dosing groups compared to control, sensitive parameters measured).

In a further study on Sprague-Dawley rats, which was designed to provide dose-response information on the effects of a series of individual phthalates on fetal testosterone production and on the use of the data obtained for the prediction of effects of phthalate mixtures on fetal testosterone production, DiBP was administered to pregnant animals (5-8 animals per treatment group) by gavage at doses of 0 (corn oil), 100, 300, 600, and 900 mg/kg bw/d on GD 8-18 (**Howdeshell et al., 2008**). Maternal body weights were taken on GD 8 and on GD 18 at sacrifice, when the uterus was removed and the number of foetuses (live and dead) and resorptions were counted and recorded. The total number of implantations was calculated by adding together the number of live and dead foetuses with the total number of resorptions. Fetal mortality was calculated by adding together the number of resorptions and dead foetuses then divided by the total number of implantations. Testes from three males/dose group (2 replicate determinations in individual testes) were used for investigation of ex vivo testis testosterone production. Maternal body weight gain was reduced from 73 g in controls to 48 and 43 g in the 600 and 900 mg/kg bw/d dose group. DiBP-induced complete litter loss in 1/5 dams at 900 mg/kg bw/d, and induced greater than 50% resorptions in 2/5 dams at 900 mg/kg bw/d and in 1/5 dams at 600 mg/kg bw/d resulting in increased percentages of fetal mortality of 17% at 600 mg/kg bw/d and of 59% at 900 mg/kg bw/d as compared to 1.3% in the controls. It is reported, that many of the testes collected from DiBP foetuses at dosages of 600 and 900 mg/kg bw/d were smaller, mucinilagous, and/or located higher in the abdominal cavity. The functional assay on testes ability for hormone production revealed that fetal testicular testosterone production was statistically significantly ($p < 0.001$) reduced at dosages of 300 mg/kg bw/d or higher. The overall results indicated that DiBP (as well as DnBP and BBP) was of equivalent potency to DEHP at reducing fetal testosterone production. Dosage levels reducing fetal testosterone production were about one-half to one-third of that required to increase fetal mortality, indicating changes in fetal testicular testosterone production to be a sensitive parameter. Based on statistically significantly lower fetal testosterone production at 300 mg/kg bw/d a NOAEL of 100 mg/kg bw/d can be derived from this study.

The study by Howdeshell et al. (2008) received a high confidence rating for evaluation of effects on testosterone production by Yost et al. (2019). For derivation of an HBM guidance value this study may be suitable (moderate number of animals per dose group, four dosing groups compared to control). However, a similar study with a higher number of animals per dose group would be preferred.

Hannas et al. (2011) describe a study in which pregnant Harlan Sprague-Dawley rats were exposed to 0, 100, 300, 600, or 900 mg/kg bw/d of DiBP from GD 14 to 18 by gavage (n=3 dams per group). This 5-day dosing regimen covers the critical programming window for male reproductive development (Welsh et al., 2008). Testicular testosterone production ex vivo was assessed by incubation of testes of 18-day old foetuses for 3 hours and testosterone measurement in the media. Dose-related decreases in testosterone production was seen for DiBP and the other tested phthalates (DEHP and DIHP (diisohexyl phthalate)) from 300 mg/kg bw/d and above (NOAEL: 100 mg/kg bw/day), and for DiNP from 500 mg/kg bw/d. (Annex to the Background document for the Annex XV dossier, slightly modified).

Aside from dose-response and potency information for fetal testicular T production, knowledge on gene expression was generated. Fetal testes from remaining males in the DEHP, DiBP, and DiNP experiments were prepared for RNA extraction. DiBP reduced fetal testis RNA expression levels

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 137

for StAR at dosage levels of 300 mg/kg/d and greater ($p < 0.05$) and Cyp11a levels at 100 mg/kg/day and greater ($p < 0.05$) (Hannas et al., 2011).

Hannas et al. (2012) describes gene expression studies in testes at GD 18 in the same study as described by Hannas et al. (2011). A number of steroidogenesis-related genes were downregulated at 300 mg/kg bw/d of DiBP and above and also by other phthalates examined (dihexyl-, diheptyl-, dipentyl-, and diisononyl phthalate), but not by diisodecyl phthalate. DiBP downregulated the expression of: StAR, Cyp11a1, HSD3b, Cyp17a1, Scarb1, Insl3, Cyp11b1 and Rxrg, and upregulated the expression of Amhr2 and Sox9. These data were applied for potency ranking of these phthalates and it was concluded that several phthalates including DiBP affected the same pathways (Annex to the Background document for the Annex XV dossier).

The studies by Hannas et al. (2011/2012) received a high confidence rating for evaluation of effects on testosterone production by Yost et al. (2019). For derivation of an HBM guidance value this study may be suitable (moderate number of animals per dose group, four dosing groups compared to control). However, a similar study with a higher number of animals per dose group would be preferred.

Furr et al. (2014) studied fetal testosterone production in several experiments with the aim to develop and validate the 'Fetal Phthalate Screen' assay. In the single dose experiment 27 substances were tested. Pregnant rats were dosed daily by oral gavage at 0 and 750 mg/kg bw/d from GD 14 to 18 ($n=3-4$ dams per group). At GD 18, fetal testes were removed and 3 testes were per litter were used to measure ex vivo testosterone production. The testosterone production was reduced to a level of about 20% of the control in the DiBP dosed animals and at about 12% for DEHP, DnBP and BBzP.

In the dose-response experiment 11 substances were tested. Pregnant Harlan Sprague Dawley rats were dosed daily by oral gavage at 0, 100, 200, 300, 500, 600, 750 and 900 mg/kg bw/d using the same protocol as for the single dose experiment. The ED50 was about 290 mg/kg bw/d with DiBP in Harlan SD rats (results for DiBP were partly taken from Hannas et al., 2011). The ED50 was about 160 and 320 mg/kg bw/d with DnBP (Harlan and Charles River SD rats respectively); 120 and 340 mg/kg bw/d with DEHP (Harlan SD and Charles River SD rats respectively); 170 mg/kg bw/d with BBzP in Harlan SD rats; and 750 mg/kg bw/d with DiNP in Harlan SD rats. Harlan SD rats appeared to be more sensitive than Charles River SD rats to reduction of fetal testosterone production from phthalate exposure. (Annex to the Background document for the Annex XV dossier)

The study by Furr et al. (2014) received a high confidence rating for evaluation of effects on testosterone production by Yost et al. (2019). For derivation of an HBM guidance value for DiBP it has to be referred to the study of Hannas et al. (2011) from which data were taken and combined.

Saillenfait et al. (2017) exposed pregnant Sprague-Dawley rats ($N = 15$; $N = 14$) to 250 mg DiBP/kg bw/d by gavage from GD 13 to 19. The first group of dams ($N = 15$) was used to study reproduction toxicity (reproductive organ weights, number of implantation sights, number of resorptions, and dead and live fetuses) and developmental toxicity effects in offspring (fetal weight, AGD, gene expression of fetal testes). The second group of dams ($N = 14$; 3 males per litter) was used to study ex vivo testal testosterone production in their male offspring. Results indicated that in male offspring the AGD relative to the cube root of body weight was decreased, other parameters were unaffected. Additionally, fetal testal testosterone and androstenedione production were significantly decreased up to 27% and 45% compared to control respectively. Furthermore, several genes (SR-B1; StAR; P450c17), responsible for proteins and enzymes

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 138

involved in cholesterol and steroid synthesis in the testes, were significantly reduced compared to control.

The study by Saillenfait et al. (2017) received a high confidence rating for evaluation of effects on testosterone production and morphological development by Yost et al. (2019). For derivation of an HBM guidance value this study may however be less suitable (only one, moderately high dose used).

Wang et al. (2017) administered DiBP to pregnant mice (N = 15) at 450 mg/kg bw/d via the diet from GD 0 to 21. Half of the pups were additionally exposed to DiBP until PND 21 via lactation, the other half of the group was unexposed from PND 0 to 21. Half of the offspring (exposed and unexposed during postnatal development) were sacrificed at PND 21, the other half of the group were fed normal diet until PND 80. Fetal gene expression was analysed in the testis of the offspring at PND21, reproductive organ weights and testosterone levels were examined in the offspring on PND 21 and PND 80 and in the latter group sperm quality was measured as well. Results indicated that testosterone levels in serum and testis significantly decreased from control following maternal exposure, and several genes related to steroid hormone synthesis and functioning were significantly lower expressed compared to control. Additionally, at PND80 the group that was exposed during postnatal development showed decreased epididymis sperm concentration and motility.

The study by Wang et al. (2017) received an overall moderate to low confidence rating by Yost et al. (2019). For derivation of HBM guidance value this study may be less suitable (only one high dose used).

Postnatal developmental toxicity studies

In albino rats (strain unknown), a feeding study over a period of four months is reported by Hodge (1954). Body weights and haematological parameters were measured. Organ weights were determined at autopsy. Livers and kidneys were examined histologically. Groups of rats (5/sex/group) were fed 0, 0.1, 1.0 and 5.0% DiBP in the diet. These dose levels were equivalent to 0 or to about 70, 700 and 3500 mg/kg bw/d in both sexes (calculated on an assumed daily food intake of 7% of the body weight). Retarded growth was observed at dosages of 1.0% and above DiBP in feed. Significantly decreased body weights were observed in both sexes at 5.0% (decrease up to 43% for males and 13% for females). The intake of 5.0% DiBP caused slight reduction in red blood cell counts in males and in haemoglobin values in both sexes. Both absolute and relative testes weights were considerably reduced in the 5.0% group. No statistical analyses were conducted but reductions were noted to approximately 30% and 50% of control values respectively. Absolute and relative liver weights were raised in the 5.0% groups of both sexes. For males, absolute weights were increased by 5%; relative weights by 80%. For females, absolute weights were increased by 40%; relative weights by 60%. Pathological examinations of liver and kidney were unremarkable.

The study by Hodge et al. (1954) received a moderate confidence rating for evaluation of reproductive organ weight by Yost et al. (2019). For derivation of an HBM guidance value, this study is considered of lower relevance due to the minimal information provided and the low number of animals per dose group.

To evaluate the effects of DiBP on the testes one week feeding toxicity studies in male rats and mice were performed, especially testosterone and zinc concentrations in the testes as an important role in the maintenance of testicular function were examined. (Oishi and Hiraga 1980c; 1980d). Feeding a diet containing 2.0% (approximately 1500 mg/kg bw/d, calculated on an assumed daily

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 139

food intake of 7% of the mean body weight of 108 g) of DiBP to 10 male rats (JCL: Wistar, 5 weeks old) resulted in significantly decreased zinc concentrations in the testes and liver. Testosterone concentrations in the testes were increased but appeared normal in the serum. The testes of DiBP-treated rats were reduced in size when compared to controls, and organ weight assessment revealed significantly ($p < 0.05$) decreased absolute and relative testicular weights in these rats. Microscopy indicated marked inhibition of spermatogenesis and desquamation of spermatocytes (Oishi and Hiraga, 1980c).

In a comparable study in male mice zinc and testosterone concentrations in tissues were determined, and body and organ weights of testes, liver and kidneys were evaluated, however microscopy was not performed. Administration of 2.0% (approximately 2000 mg/kg bw/d, calculated on an assumed daily food intake of 10% of the body weight) of DiBP in the diet to 10 young male mice (JCL: ICR) revealed significantly decreased zinc concentrations in the testes. The concentration of testosterone in the testes of DiBP-treated mice was not different from control values. The relative weights of the testes and liver of DiBP-treated mice were significantly higher, but the absolute testis weight was not different from control values (Oishi and Hiraga, 1980b).

The purpose of studies with MiBP was to discover whether phthalic acid monoesters including their metabolites have similar effects to their diesters regarding effects on the testes and alterations in zinc and testosterone concentrations.

Administration of 2.0% MiBP (corresponding to total intake of 2300 mg/kg bw/d) in the diet to 10 male rats (JCL: Wistar, 5 weeks old) for 7 days resulted in significantly suppressed food consumption throughout the experimental period, depressed body weight gains (69% of controls), and significantly decreased absolute and relative testes weights (60% of controls). Examination on the concentration of zinc in the testes, liver, kidneys and serum showed significantly decreased values in the testes and liver (60% and 90% of control values). Testosterone concentrations in the testes and serum were significantly increased by 260% and 160% of control values. Microscopy was not performed in this study (**Oishi & Hiraga, 1980d**).

In a mice study body weights and organ weights of testes, liver and kidneys were evaluated; and zinc concentration in testes, liver and kidneys was determined, and testosterone concentration in the testes. Feeding of 2.0% (approximately 2000 mg/kg bw/d, calculated on an assumed daily food intake of 10% of the body weight) MiBP in the diet to 10 male mice (JCL: ICR, 5 weeks old) for 7 days resulted in significantly increased relative liver and testes weights associated with decreased body weight, whereas the absolute weights did not differ from control values. The average zinc level in the testes of MiBP-treated mice was significantly lower than the control value and did not differ in liver and kidneys. Testosterone concentration in the testes was significantly decreased (**Oishi & Hiraga, 1980a**).

The studies by Oishi and Hiraga (1980a, b, c, and d) received a low to moderate confidence rating for effects on testosterone production, reproduction organ weights, and testicular histology and sperm. For derivation of an HBM guidance value, these studies are considered of lower relevance due to short exposure duration (7 days), and the availability of only one highly dosed group compared to control.

Liver, kidneys, testes and accessory sex organs were weighed, and testes and accessory sex organs were examined by light microscopy. Additionally, zinc metabolism was examined in 9 rats received $[^{65}\text{Zn}]\text{Cl}_2$ (50 $\mu\text{Ci}/\text{kg}$ body wt.) i.p. 48h prior to treatment with MiBP for 4 days. The ^{65}Zn content was determined in liver, kidney and testes. Urinary ^{65}Zn excretion was examined over a 24-h period following 4 days of treatment. Treated rats developed markedly reduced absolute and relative testes weights (73%, $P < 0.001$), and lowered seminal vesicle weights (not significant)

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 140

compared to control values. No differences were evident from prostate weights. Microscopy revealed in all six examined animals marked testicular atrophy of the majority of the seminiferous tubules with a diminution of both spermatocytes and spermatogonia. In all instances the lesions were bilateral in origin. No abnormalities were detected in sections of prostate or seminal vesicles. The zinc metabolism was adversely altered by significantly increasing urinary zinc excretion concomitant with decreased ⁶⁵Zn testicular content and elevated renal ⁶⁵Zn content (Foster et al., 1981).

The study by Foster et al. (1981) received a low confidence rating for reproductive organ weight and testicular histology and sperm by Yost et al. (2019). For derivation of an HBM guidance value, this study is considered of lower relevance due to short exposure duration (4 days), and the availability of one dosed group compared to control.

Zhu et al. (2010) investigated testicular toxicity of DiBP in 21-day-old Sprague-Dawley rats and C57BL/6N mice, using the in situ TUNEL method. For an acute exposure experiment, animals were once given DiBP at various concentrations by oral gavage. For a subchronic exposure experiment, they were daily given DiBP at various concentrations for consecutive 7 days. Controls were treated with corn oil under the same condition. For a recovery experiment, rats were once given DiBP (1000 mg/kg bw), and were sacrificed at day 1 to 8 after administration. Furthermore, the disorder of vimentin filaments in Sertoli cells after daily administration of DiBP (500 mg/kg bw) for consecutive 7 days in rats was also studied by immunohistochemistry using anti-vimentin antibody. As a result, the study demonstrated that DiBP can induce testicular atrophy in rats due to the increase of TUNEL-positive spermatogenic cells in both acute and subchronic exposure experiments. At the same time, the disorder of vimentin filaments in Sertoli cells was recognised. However, no such damages could be found in mouse testis. Referring to the recovery experiment, the testis weight and testicular morphology returned to normal at day 6 after administration.

The study by Zhu et al. (2010) received a low confidence rating for male reproductive organ weights by Yost et al. (2019). For derivation of an HBM guidance value this study is not further considered because of the methods and endpoints chosen.

Sedha et al. (2015) orally exposed immature female rats of the age of 20 days (N = 6) to DiBP at 250 or 1250 mg/kg bw/d either for 3 or 20 consecutive days. The study was designed to study the estrogenic effects of DiBP. The group exposed to DiBP for 3 days was analysed for body weight changes and reproductive organ weights. The second group was sacrificed at PND 41 and analysed for body weight changes and vaginal opening from PND 21 until sacrifice and reproductive organ weights at PND 41. Body weights were significantly changed from control in both groups, other parameters remained unaffected after treatment.

The study by Sedha et al. (2015) received a moderate confidence ranking for female reproductive morphological development. For derivation of an HBM guidance value this study is considered of low relevance due to the low sample sizes and the high doses tested.

12.2 Annex 2: PROAST BMD modelling report

12.2.1 Data Description

The endpoint to be analysed is: mean.

Data used for analysis:

Dose	Mean	SD	Number
0	2.55	0.17	13
125	2.44	0.15	11
250	2.28	0.30	14
500	2.02	0.13	12
625	1.98	0.16	11

12.2.2 Selection of the BMR

The BMR (benchmark response) used is a 5% change in mean response compared to the controls. The BMD (benchmark dose) is the dose corresponding with the BMR of interest.

A 90% confidence interval around the BMD will be estimated, the lower bound is reported by BMDL and the upper bound by BMDU.

12.2.3 Software Used

Results are obtained using the EFSA web-tool for BMD analysis, which uses the R-package PROAST, version 66.24, for the underlying calculations.

12.2.4 Results

Response variable: mean

Fitted Models

Model	Converged	Loglik	npar	AIC
full model	yes	64.95	6	-117.90
null model	yes	38.12	2	-72.24
Expon. m3-	yes	64.40	4	-120.80
Expon. m5-	yes	64.95	5	-119.90
Hill m3-	yes	64.40	4	-120.80
Hill m5-	yes	64.92	5	-119.84
Inv.Expon. m3-	yes	64.57	4	-121.14
Inv.Expon. m5-	yes	64.87	5	-119.74
LN m3-	yes	64.50	4	-121.00
LN m5-	yes	64.90	5	-119.80

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 142

12.2.5 Estimated Model Parameters

EXP

estimate for var- : 0.007087

estimate for a- : 2.555

estimate for CED- : 100.6

estimate for d- : 0.9131

HILL

estimate for var- : 0.007087

estimate for a- : 2.555

estimate for CED- : 100.7

estimate for d- : 0.915

INVEXP

estimate for var- : 0.007048

estimate for a- : 2.552

estimate for CED- : 112.3

estimate for d- : 0.1656

LOGN

estimate for var- : 0.007064

estimate for a- : 2.553

estimate for CED- : 107.5

estimate for d- : 0.3085

12.2.6 Weights for Model Averaging

EXP	HILL	INVEXP	LOGN
0.23	0.23	0.28	0.26

12.2.7 Final BMD Values

Endpoint	Subgroup	BMDL	BMDU
mean		37.6	222

Confidence intervals for the BMD are based on 200 bootstrap data sets.

Visualisation

bootstrap curves based on model averaging

12.3 Annex 3: Lehmann et al. 2004 study

Lehmann et al. (2004) explored the effects of DnBP on steroidogenesis in fetal testes. Thereby, pregnant Sprague-Dawley rats received DnBP by gavage with corn oil at doses of 0.1; 1.0; 10; 50; 100 or 500 mg/kg bw/day (5 animals per DnBP-dosed groups) from GD 12 until GD 19. Male foetus testes were isolated on day 19 and gene expression changes were quantitatively assessed by real-time PCR. Fetal testicular testosterone concentration was measured by radioimmunoassay. The results showed a dose-dependent reduction in the expression of key genes and proteins involved in cholesterol transport and in steroidogenesis accompanied by a reduction of testosterone in fetal testes after maternal exposure from 50 mg/kg bw/day, which is lower than levels at which adverse effects are detected on developing male reproductive organs as e.g. in Mylchreest et al. (2000). Observed changes (gene and protein expression) can serve as early indicators of testicular response to DnBP.

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 145

Part IV

Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GVs) for Butyl benzyl phthalate (BBzP, CAS-No.: 85-68-7) referring to the general population and to workers

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 146

Table of contents

1	Authors and acknowledgements	148
2	Glossary.....	149
3	Introduction	151
4	General properties of the substance	152
4.1	Identification of the substance	152
4.2	Physico-chemical properties.....	152
4.3	Uses of the substance	153
4.4	EU Harmonised Classification and Labelling	153
4.5	EU legislation and regulations	153
4.6	Human Exposure.....	154
4.6.1	General Population.....	154
4.6.2	Workers.....	155
5	General toxicological profile of the substance	156
5.1	Toxicokinetics and metabolism	156
5.1.1	Animal studies	156
5.1.2	Studies with human volunteers	157
5.2	Toxicity.....	158
5.2.1	Human health effects.....	158
5.2.2	Animal studies and <i>in vitro</i> tests.....	161
5.2.3	Conclusion and assessment of different bodies	169
6	Selected biomarker(s) for the HBM-GV proposal and analytical method	173
6.1	Choice of biomarkers of exposure	173
6.2	Choice of analytical method.....	173
7	Choice of the HBM-GVs derivation method.....	174
7.1	Derivation of an HBM-GV for the general population	174
7.1.1	Method for the HBM-GV _{GenPop} derivation.....	174
7.1.2	Derivation of an HBM-GV _{GenPop}	176
7.2	Derivation of an HBM-GV for the occupational population	177
7.2.1	Method for the HBM-GV _{worker} derivation.....	177
7.2.2	Derivation of an HBM-GV _{worker}	178
8	Level of confidence attributed to the derived HBM-GVs	179
9	Discussion	180
10	Factsheet.....	182
10.1	Factsheet for the general population.....	182

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 147

10.2 Factsheet for workers	186
11 References	190

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 148

1 Authors and acknowledgements

Authors

Rosa Lange, UBA, Germany

Petra Apel, UBA, Germany

Eva Ougier, ANSES, France

Christophe Rousselle, ANSES, France

Fatoumata Sissoko, ANSES, France

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Entity	Contributing experts
NH Austria	Maria Uhl (EAA)
NH Belgium	Kirsten Baken (VITO)
NH Germany	Holger M. Koch (IPA)
NH Switzerland	Nancy Hopf (Swiss Center for Applied Human Toxicology)
NH Portugal	Susana Viegas (ESTESL)
	Teresa Borges (FCT)

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 149

2 Glossary

AF	Assessment factor
AGD	Anogenital distance
BBzP	Butyl benzyl phthalate
CA	Chromosomal aberrations
CHAP Alternatives	Chronic Hazard Advisory Panel on Phthalates and Phthalate Alternatives
CLP	Classification, Labelling and Packaging
CMR	Carcinogenic, Mutagenic or Reprotoxic
DnBP	Di-n-butyl phthalate
DEHP	Bis(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate
DiBP	Diisobutyl phthalate
DNEL	Derived No-Effect Level
ECHA	European Chemicals Agency
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
EU RAR	European Union Risk Assessment Report
FSH	Follicle-stimulating hormone
GD	Gestational day
GM	Geometric mean
HED	Human equivalent dose
HPLC-MS/MS spectrometry	High-performance liquid chromatography with tandem mass spectrometry
LH	Luteinizing hormone
MAK Commission	German Permanent Senate Commission for the Investigation of Health Hazards of Chemical Compounds in the Work Area
MBzP	Monobenzyl phthalate
MnBP	Mono-n-butyl phthalate
NICNAS Scheme	National Industrial Chemical Notification and Assessment Scheme
N(L)OEL	No (Lowest) Observed Adverse Effect Level
OEL	Occupational Exposure Limit
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 150

PBPK/PBTK	Physiologically Based Pharmacokinetic/Toxicokinetic
PND	Postnatal day
POD	Point of departure
PVA	Polyvinyl alcohol
PVC	Polyvinyl chloride
RAC	Committee for Risk Assessment
SEAC	Committee for Socio-economic Analysis
SCE	Sister Chromatid Exchanges
SVHC	Substance of very high concern
T3	Triiodothyronine hormone
T4	Thyroxine hormone TDI
TDI	Tolerable daily intake
TDS	Testicular dysgenesis syndrome
TRV	Toxicity reference value

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 151

3 Introduction

Within the framework of task 5.2 of HBM4EU, Human Biomonitoring guidance values (HBM-GVs) are derived for HBM4EU priority substances. The methodology applied to derive these values is described in the concept paper previously released in the HBM4EU task 5.2 work frame (Apel et al., 2020). For the time being, HBM-GVs to be derived shall be agreed on at HBM4EU project level, further adoption of derived HBM-GVs at EU level has to be discussed among partners and the EU Commission.

In the current report, general population HBM-GVs (HBM-GV_{GenPop}) and an occupational HBM-GV (HBM-GV_{Worker}) are derived and discussed for butyl benzyl phthalate (BBzP) based on anti-androgenic effects on the male reproductive development observed in rats. This includes mainly changes in sperm motility and sperm count and suppression of foetal testosterone production and reduction in serum testosterone in adult offspring.

The state of epidemiological knowledge based on human exposure to BBzP on whether and how it might cause human health effects is not sufficient to derive HBM-GVs directly based on human data, be it for the general population or for workers. The derivation of HBM-GVs for the general population and for workers relies on an animal point of departure (POD) value identified from two key toxicity studies. The factsheets in section 10 of this document summarise the key input data allowing to derive HBM-GVs. Additionally, for selected criteria a level of confidence (LoC) is given separately and explained in detail in the footnotes of the factsheets. The single LoCs refer to the volume and quality of the respective database, and give an estimation of the uncertainties associated with the HBM-GV derivation. A global LOC, summarising the single LoCs is given for the derived HBM-GVs.

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 152

4 General properties of the substance

4.1 Identification of the substance

Name	Butyl benzyl phthalate
IUPAC Name	2-O-benzyl 1-O-butyl benzene-1,2-dicarboxylate
CAS Number	85-68-7
EC Number	201-622-7
Molecular weight	312.4 g/mol
Molecular formula	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₄
Structural formula	<p>Figure 7: Structural formula of BBzP (Source: PubChem Database accessed on July 17, 2019)</p>

4.2 Physico-chemical properties

Butyl benzyl phthalate, hereafter referred to as BBzP, is a benzyl ester that conforms to the formula C₁₉H₂₀O₄. It is a clear oily liquid at room temperature. The octanol-water partition coefficient (log K_{OW}) is 4.91 at 20 °C and the vapour pressure is 0.00112 Pa at 20°C. The water solubility ranges between 2.69 and 2.9 mg/L at 20 – 30 °C (ECB 2007, ECHA & Danish EPA 2016). The mean value of 2.8 mg/L at 20 °- 30° has been used in the table 1 below.

Table 18: Physico-chemical properties of Butyl benzyl phthalate (BBzP)

Molecular formula	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₄
Molar mass	312.4 g/mol
State at room temperature	Clear oily liquid
Melting point	< -35 °C
Boiling point	370 °C at 10.10 hPa
Relative density	1.116 g/cm ³ at 20 °C
Vapour pressure	0.00112 Pa at 20 °C
Partition coefficient log K _{OW}	4.91 at 20 °C
Water solubility	2.8 mg/L at 25 – 30 °C and pH 7

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 153

4.3 Uses of the substance

BBzP is mainly used as plasticiser for soft-polyvinyl chloride (PVC) but also in other polymer products. BBzP is formulated as component in preparations like adhesives, sealants, coatings and paints (ECHA & Danish EPA 2016). According to ECHA30, BBzP is manufactured and/or imported in the European Economic Area in the range of 1 - 10 tonnes per year. It is used in a wide range of articles together with other phthalates, such as plastic materials, fabrics, textiles and apparel, vehicles, electrical batteries and accumulators and rubber articles (German HBM Commission 2011, ECHA & Danish EPA 2016).

4.4 EU Harmonised Classification and Labelling

According to the Classification, Labelling and Packaging (CLP) Regulation ((EC) No 1272/2008), BBzP may damage the unborn child and is suspected of damaging fertility (H360Df) and is classified as toxic for reproduction, Cat. 1B. In addition, BBzP is very toxic to aquatic life and (H400) and is very toxic to aquatic life with long lasting effects (H401) and thereby classified as Aquatic Acute 1 and Aquatic Chronic 1.

International Chemical Identification	EC. no	CAS no.	Classification		Labelling	
			Hazard Class & Category Code(s)	Hazard statement code(s)	Pictogram Signal Word Code(s)	Hazard statement code(s)
Benzyl butyl phthalate (BBzP)	201-622-7	85-68-7	Repr.1B Aquatic Acute 1 Aquatic Chronic 1	H360Df H400 H410	GHS09 GHS08 Dgr	H360Df H410

4.5 EU legislation and regulations

BBzP is classified as a substance of very high concern (SVHC) in accordance with Article 57(c) of REACH regulation (ECHA 2008). In July 2017, BBzP was also identified as SVHC in accordance with Article 57(f) of REACH due to its endocrine disrupting properties for human health (ECHA 2017).

Together with three other reprotoxic phthalates (DEHP, DiBP, DnBP) it is subject to authorisation since 21 February 2015 (EC 2011). Exempted uses are uses in the immediate packaging of medicinal products covered under Regulation (EC) No 726/2004, Directive 2001/82/EC, and/or Directive 2001/83/EC.

BBzP is listed in Entry 51 of Annex XVII to Regulation EU No 1907/2006 (REACH), stating that BBzP together with DEHP, DiBP and DnBP is restricted in toys and childcare articles containing the four phthalates individually or in combination with a concentration limit of 0.1% (EC 2011).

In addition, BBzP is prohibited for use in cosmetics according to the Cosmetics Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009 (EC 2009).

³⁰ <https://echa.europa.eu/fr/brief-profile/-/briefprofile/100.001.475>

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 154

Medical devices containing BBzP or other CMR phthalates must be labelled as a device containing phthalates. If the intended use includes treatment of children, of nursing mothers or pregnant women, the manufacturer must provide a specific justification for the use of these substances according to the Medical Device Directive (93/42/EEC).

Regarding the food sector, BBzP is authorised for use as excipient or additive with a specific migration limit (SML) of 30 mg/kg foodstuff according to the legislation on food contact materials (Regulation No 10/2011). However, it can only be used for materials that come into contact with fatless food and cannot be used in infant formulas (EC 2011).

Regarding the occupational field, BBzP is regulated under the EU Occupational Safety and Health (OSH) Chemical Agents Directive (CAD) 98/24/EC on the protection of the health and safety of workers from the risks related to chemical agents at work³¹.

The EU legislation obliges employers to ensure that the work environment is safe for the reproductive health of the workers, pregnant workers, and offspring. The EU Directive 92/85/EEC requires employers to assess the health and safety risks to pregnant and breastfeeding workers, and if needed, to change working conditions or offer suitable alternative work³². The prevention or reduction of exposure of workers can be done in several ways in accordance with the widely recognised hierarchy of control, e.g.:

- Eliminating or substituting hazardous chemicals for safe alternatives,
- Improving the work environment by collective protection measures, such as the enclosure of the emitting process, local exhaust ventilation, general ventilation, changing work tasks and habits into safe procedures
- Use of personal protective equipment
- Moving the pregnant worker to another job
- Granting leave to the pregnant worker in accordance with national legislation, if none of the above measures is feasible.

Both, the employer and workers should be informed about risk assessment results of agents harmful to reproduction and development of the offspring that are identified at the workplace. Women and men workers should be informed beforehand, for example during the pre-employment medical examination, of any potentially harmful occupational exposures and protective measures to prevent any adverse reproductive effects. Women should be advised to contact health services immediately after becoming pregnant or when planning to become pregnant³³.

4.6 Human Exposure

4.6.1 General Population

The general population is exposed to BBzP via different routes through multiple sources. The exposure routes include ingestion, inhalation and dermal or mucous contact. Food is considered to be one source of exposure for BBzP, accounting for approximately 25 % of the total intake (ECHA & Danish EPA 2016). Also, the indoor environment through exposure via ingestion of dust and inhalation of air is considered a r source for BBzP exposure (Beko et al. 2013, Wormuth et al. 2006). The U.S. Chronic Hazard Advisory Panel estimated the exposure to BBzP based on

³¹ <https://osha.europa.eu/en/legislation/directives/75>

³² <https://osha.europa.eu/en/legislation/directives/10>

³³ https://oshwiki.eu/wiki/Reproductive_effects_caused_by_chemical_and_biological_agents

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 155

environmental data and found the main exposure sources to be diet and indoor sources (CPSC 2014). Also, exposure from articles can arise from contact between articles and the skin or mucous membrane, or with infants from mouthing articles (ECHA & Danish EPA 2016) as well as from inhalation of BBzP vapour and dust particles carrying BBzP molecules (ECB 2007).

Even though, studies show a widespread exposure to BBzP with a high percentage of samples tested above the LOD/LOQ (Den Hond et al. 2015, Giovanoulis et al. 2016, Hartmann et al. 2015), a recent study investigating the time trend of phthalate exposure demonstrated that the exposure to old, well-known and restricted phthalates (such as DEHP and DnBP) including, BBzP has considerably decreased (roughly by a factor of 10) over the last 25 years (Koch et al. 2017). When comparing DEMOCOPHES data to older studies, a significant decline in exposure was also seen for Germany and Denmark (ECHA & Danish EPA 2016).

4.6.2 Workers

In contrast to the general population who is exposed to BBzP via many routes, the main pathways of occupational exposure to BBzP is inhalation and dermal contact. In the EU risk assessment report the highest concentration of BBzP in the air during manufacture of butyl benzyl phthalate was estimated to be 1 mg/m³ as worst case value for drumming as exposure scenario with the highest exposure (ECB 2007). Estimations were done by using the EASE (Estimation and Assessment of Substance Exposure) model with the input value for saturated vapour pressure of 0.00112 Pa. Only a small number of exposure measurements for drumming were available. Data from a Monsanto Plant showed a high exposure of 2.6 mg/m³ in one measurement in a 15 minutes sample. Mean exposure value based on full shift samples (n=3) was 0.002 mg/m³. The measured value of 2.6 mg/m³ was regarded as short-term value and not representative for a full shift. In addition, aerosol formation was not thought to occur in this scenario, wherefore the reasonable worst-case exposure level was set to 1 mg/m³. This represents the highest exposure value calculated based on the vapour pressure at ambient temperatures as BBzP concentration in air is expected to be low owing to its very low vapour pressure. The highest dermal exposure is estimated to be 420 mg/day as no measurement data is available.

When looking at industrial use of BBzP-containing products the highest exposures for the inhalation pathway occur during calendering operation with worst case estimates of 3 mg/m³. This is reasonable as during calendering elevated temperatures up to 180 ° occur. For the dermal pathway, highest exposures were estimated for processing of PVC floats and sealants with 840 mg/day and with 420 mg/day for calendering processes. For professional end-use of BBzP-containing semi- and end products scenarios no measured exposure data is available. For dermal uptake EASE model estimated the highest exposures for use of polyurethane sealants/fillers/grouting agents with 84-840 mg/day. However, it is assumed that this scenario results in less dermal exposure than for the processing of PVC floats and due to its short duration actual exposures will be much lesser than estimated by EASE. Inhalation of BBzP aerosols can occur in these scenarios when techniques applied involve high temperatures as aerosols are generated. However, considered end uses do not include high temperatures and therefore inhalation exposure is considered negligible (ECB, 2007).

Recently, it became apparent that transdermal contact directly from air can be a relevant exposure pathway for semi-volatile compounds, such as phthalates. Indeed, Wechsler et al., 2014 showed that for DEP and DnBP, the median dermal uptake from air was comparable to the inhalation intake. However, the authors stated also that the contribution of this pathway to the overall uptake is assumed to decrease with increasing molecular weight (Weschler et al. 2015). However, studies for measuring if this applies to BBzP as well are still lacking.

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 156

5 General toxicological profile of the substance

5.1 Toxicokinetics and metabolism

5.1.1 Animal studies

In experimental studies with rats, BBzP was readily absorbed after oral administration of 150, 475 and 780 mg/kg bw/d in female rats with 54 %, 58%, 43% of the dose recovered as metabolites in urine within 24h. At the highest dose of 1500 mg/kg bw/d only 30 % could be recovered as metabolites within 24h (Nativelle et al. 1999). In male rats, orally given dosages of 2, 20 and 200 mg/kg BBzP were readily absorbed with 61-74% of the doses being recovered as metabolites in urine within 24 hours (Eigenberg et al. 1986). It was shown, that excretion rates were dose-dependent with higher doses being less excreted via the urine and more via the faeces (Eigenberg et al. 1986, Nativelle et al. 1999), apparently due to lower absorption at higher doses (2000 mg/kg bw/d) (Eigenberg et al. 1986) after oral administration. A study in four Beagle dogs, orally given 5000 mg/kg BBzP within 4h showed that 88% and 91% of the dose administered was recovered as unchanged BBzP in the faeces in male and female animals, respectively. Only 4% was excreted in urine as phthalic acid (ECB, 2007, NICNAS, 2015). In an in vitro study investigating species differences in the hydrolysis of BBzP demonstrated, that in mouse, rat and monkey liver microsomes BBzP was mainly hydrolysed to its monoester MnBP, followed by MBzP, whereas in dog and human liver microsomes it was the other way around (NICNAS, 2015, Hartwig 2018).

In another study with male rats, dermal absorption was estimated to be about 35% over 7 days with constant excretion of 3-6% of the applied dose (~ 8 mg/cm²) per day (Elsisi et al. 1989). No information related to absorption after inhalation was found in the literature (ECB 2007, NICNAS 2015).

Application of ¹⁴C-BBzP to the skin of male rats showed minimal and unspecific distribution of radioactivity in muscle (4,6%), in adipose tissue (0,17%), and in the brain, lung, liver, spleen, small intestine, kidney, testis, spinal cord and blood (< 0.5 % being the summation of dose found in these tissues), while 45 % were found in the area of application (Elsisi et al. 1989). Based on the results of this study, it cannot be excluded that BBzP is stored in the skin and that it might be released from the skin to enter systemic circulation. Orally given BBzP was mainly found in liver, kidneys and small intestine (Hartwig 2018). There is no reported tissue accumulation in the literature (ECHA & Danish EPA 2016). In animal studies, BBzP and its metabolites were found in breast milk, semen and foetal serum (NICNAS 2015). After absorption, BBzP is initially cleaved into its primary metabolites, the monoesters mono-n-butyl phthalate (MnBP) and benzylic alcohol as well as in monobenzyl phthalate (MBzP) and n-butanol by hydrolysis of esterases and lipases in the liver and in the intestinal lumen (Fig. 1) (NICNAS 2015, Hartwig 2018). In rats, the main metabolites formed were the butyl and benzyl monoesters representing respectively 29-34 % and 7-12 % of the total recovered metabolites in urine, and hippuric acid with 51-56 % (Nativelle et al. 1999). From both monoester metabolites, MnBP was found in a larger amount than MBzP with a ratio of 3:1 in adult and immature animals (ECB 2007, RAC & SEAC 2012). However, the amount of urinary excreted monoesters are higher in adult rats compared to immature rats (ECB 2007). Subsequently, mostly glucuronidation of the monoesters takes place (ECB 2007, Hartwig 2018). Both monoesters were found in the bile, and it can be assumed that BBzP undergoes enterohepatic circulation (Hartwig 2018, Nativelle et al. 1999). In an in-vitro study in liver microsomes, it was shown that BBzP was hydrolysed into MnBP to a larger extent in monkeys, rats and mice whereas in dogs more MBzP was formed (Takahara et al. 2014).

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 157

Figure 8: Metabolism of BBzP in female rats according to Nativelle, 1999 [Figure adapted from (Hartwig 2018)]. Percentage ranges given represent the amount for the respective metabolite of the total recovered metabolites. Doses tested were as follows: 150, 475, 780 and 1500 mg/kg bw/d

5.1.2 Studies with human volunteers

According to ECHA's Risk Assessment Committee (RAC), absorption fractions for the calculation of internal doses starting from external doses are 100% for the oral path (experimental animals and humans), 5% for the dermal path (human, all ages) and 100% for the inhalation path (human, all ages). These absorption fractions are default values (RAC & SEAC 2012). However, it needs to be noted that for the dermal pathway, studies in experimental animals indicate higher absorption fractions (see 5.1.1). Indeed, the dermal pathway for exposure to phthalates might have been underestimated (Hopf et al. 2014, Lorber et al. 2017, Salthammer et al. 2018, Weschler et al. 2015). However, human studies for the dermal absorption of BBzP are scarce and there is a need for further investigations.

Anderson et al. (2001) investigated the metabolism of BBzP in 7 human volunteers. The main urinary metabolite of BBzP in these volunteers after ingestion was mono-benzyl-phthalate (MBzP), representing 78% of the high dose (506 µg) and 67% of the low dose (253 µg) administered (molar basis) with relative standard deviations of 39% and 26% (n=7 volunteers). BBzP was also metabolised into mono-n-butyl phthalate (MnBP), but only 6% of the high dose administered were recovered in urine, whereas for the low dose no MnBP could be recovered in urine, probably due to an insufficient quantification (Anderson et al. 2001). The authors stated that the main urinary metabolite is MBzP, representing 73% of the oral dose, which is rapidly eliminated from the body (within 24 hours) and only little subsequent metabolism takes place (Anderson et al. 2001). Additionally, it was concluded that measuring urinary metabolites in any survey would only give a description of the exposure situation of the last 24h before sampling (Anderson et al. 2001)

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 158

assuming oral exposure. It has to be noted, that the authors did not mention the sex of the volunteers who participated in the study and that the reference for a detailed description of the study protocol given, was not accessible.

In humans, unlike in rats, it appears that conjugation with glucuronic acid is a significant and major metabolism pathway. Indeed, Silva et al., 2003, who investigated conjugation of several phthalates in urine samples of the US population,, demonstrated that MBzP is mainly (93%) present in its conjugated form in human urine (Silva et al. 2003), whereas in the metabolism study by Nativelle et al. (1999) on female rats, no glucuronides were found in the urine. This is in contrast to another study by Eigenberg et al. (1986), in which 2-21% of the dose was identified as glucuronides in the urine of male rats (Eigenberg et al. 1986). Nativelle et al. (1999) stated that sex differences can occur in the conjugation process by referring to a study by Mulder et al. (1986) .

Urinary excretion appears to be the major route in humans. According to the data of the study by Anderson et al. (2001), up to 84% of the administered dose of BBzP can be found in the urine as sum of the two metabolites MBzP and MnBP. This urinary excretion appears to occur quickly, since the majority of metabolites are found within 24 hours.

No other studies investigating the toxicokinetics of BBzP in human volunteers were found in the literature.

5.2 Toxicity

The toxicity of BBzP and its metabolites MBzP and MnBP has been extensively studied in animals and humans, however mostly after oral administration and this data has been assessed by various bodies. Therefore, this section does only provide a short summary of the toxicity data available and focuses on the outcomes relevant for the HBM-GV derivation. Details of the different studies can be found in several reviews and reports (ECB 2007, CPSC 2014, NICNAS 2015, Hartwig 2018, Radke et al. 2018).

5.2.1 Human health effects

BBzP is not thought to be acutely toxic to humans and shows no skin sensitisation. It is not expected to be an eye irritant and showed no skin irritation in humans (NICNAS 2015, Den Hond et al. 2015). Epidemiological studies in children and adults show equivocal results regarding BBzP exposure and asthma, asthma-like symptoms, rhinitis or eczemas. Due to the uncertainties presented by these studies, it is not possible to draw conclusions from them. However, BBzP is not expected to have a sensitisation potential (ECB 2007, NICNAS 2015, Hartwig 2018). Based on the results of animal studies, BBzP is considered not to be genotoxic for humans. The observed carcinogenic effects in studies with rats were evaluated by different authorities as not sufficiently evidenced for BBzP to be classified as carcinogenic (ECB 2007, NICNAS 2015).

Several epidemiological studies have been performed investigating the association of exposure to phthalates with reproductive and developmental effects in males. In a recent study of Radke et al., 2018 (U.S. EPA) human epidemiological evidence in literature has systematically been reviewed to investigate male reproductive effects and exposure to several phthalates. Parameters included were, among others, semen quality, anogenital distance (AGD), cryptorchidism and time to pregnancy. Five studies were identified investigating BBzP exposure and effects on the AGD of boys (Bornehag et al. 2015, Jensen et al. 2016, Suzuki et al. 2012, Swan 2008, Swan et al. 2015). The confidence attributed to the studies was classified as medium for three studies, of which two reported a negative association between urinary MBzP and AGD (Radke et al. 2018). However, these results were not significant. The other medium confidence study (Swan et al. 2015), as well

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 159

as two low-confidence studies (Suzuki et al. 2012, Swan 2008), showed no signs of association. The authors considered the overall evidence of an inverse association between AGD and exposure to BBzP as slight evidence. It was stated, that this might be due to only few studies available and/or due to low exposure levels (Radke et al. 2018). In an earlier study by Swan et al. (2005), which was not included in the review by Radke et al. (2008), who investigated 85 mother-son pairs, a correlation between the anogenital index (AGI) of 2-36 months old boys and prenatal maternal urinary concentration of MBzP was shown with calculated odds ratios of 3.8 for a shorter AGI when comparing boys with prenatal MBzP exposure in the highest quartiles with those in the lowest quartile. Shorter AGIs were also associated with a higher percentage of boys having one or both testicles incompletely descended (Swan et al. 2005). However, in a second study by Swan et al. (2008), where the findings of the previous study were repeated and extended to 106 mother-son pairs these results were not confirmed (Swan 2008).

Radke et al. (2018) revealed that most epidemiological studies investigated the effects of exposure to phthalates on semen parameters. In regard to BBzP in particular, ten studies (Axelsson et al. 2015, Bloom et al. 2015, Den Hond et al. 2015, Hauser et al. 2006, Jonsson et al. 2005, Jurewicz et al. 2013, Pan et al. 2015, Thurston et al. 2016, Wang et al. 2015, Wirth et al. 2008) were found to report an association of BBzP exposure and semen parameters, of which all but one (Den Hond et al. 2015) were identified as having moderate confidence (Radke et al. 2018). From these ten studies two demonstrated a significant association with lower sperm concentration (Bloom et al. 2015, Pan et al. 2015), and one with reduced motility with increased BBzP exposure. Others showed similar effects, however, these were not statistically significant. In the EU Risk Assessment Report (ECB 2007) and the ANSES report (ANSES 2016), one additional study was reported, which was not included in the review of Radke et al. (2018). Duty (2003) studied the correlation between urinary MBzP and MnBP levels and semen parameters. Main findings were dose-response relations between both metabolites and sperm concentration. Furthermore, they could demonstrate a dose-response relation between MnBP and motility and morphology of the sperms. However, no relationship between increased urinary MBzP concentration and lower sperm motility was observed in men from infertile couples (Duty et al. 2003). Hauser et al., 2006 confirmed both findings, the relationship of urinary MBzP with sperm concentration and the absence of a relationship with sperm motility (not reported in the EU RAR, but included in the Radke et al., 2018 review). Nevertheless, it needs to be noted, that the evidence of a relationship between MBzP exposure and sperm concentration were only suggestive and only for the highest quartile of MBzP exposure. The authors also stated that the association in this study were weaker than previously reported (Hauser et al. 2006). In another study by Wirth et al., 2008 (also included in the Radke review) no relationship between urinary concentrations of MBzP and changes in any of the sperm parameters (sperm concentration, motility, morphology) were observed (Wirth et al. 2008). However, the authors stated that the absence of an association is due to the small sample size (n= 43) and therefore the statistical power is not sufficient (Wirth et al. 2008). In 2004, the team of Duty et al. carried out a study showing a relationship between increased urinary concentrations of MBzP and changes in sperm motility parameters but results were not statistically significant (ANSES 2016, Duty et al. 2004). Another study by Jurewicz et al. (2013) revealed that sperm aneuploidy was increased with increase of BBzP concentration (Jurewicz et al. 2013). Taken all together, the evidence was considered as moderate evidence for an association of semen quality, especially motility and BBzP exposure (Radke et al. 2018).

In addition, a prospective cohort study on 501 couples assessing the relation to time to pregnancy or reduced fertility (Buck Louis et al. 2014) were identified by the authors as of high confidence (Radke et al. 2018). MBzP levels of males were significantly related to increased time to pregnancy

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 160

or reduced fertility (Buck Louis et al. 2014). The authors considered the evidence as moderate due to the good quality of the study and the because the findings are in line with the outcomes for semen parameters of the previous studies mentioned (Radke et al. 2018).

Concerning associations with testosterone, studies were contradicting and not statistically significant. A total of eight studies investigated the association of testosterone levels and BBzP exposure, of which six were of medium confidence and two of low confidence. Two studies (medium confidence) showed a negative correlation between testosterone levels and MBzP levels, but were not significant (Jurewicz et al. 2013, Pan et al. 2015). The authors therefore considered the evidence indeterminate (Radke et al. 2018). In comparison with findings on other phthalates the authors noted that lower exposure levels for BBzP were reported and that the lack of observed effects could be due to lower sensitivity of BBzP (Radke et al. 2018).

A cohort study of Main et al. (2006), which investigated the association of phthalate monoesters with cryptorchidism in Danish boys found trends of higher MBzP concentrations in breast milk samples with levels of reproductive hormones. A positive correlation was observed with sex hormone-binding globulin (SHBG) and with inhibin B and MBzP. However, neither of these findings were not statistically significant. None of the measured phthalate metabolites showed an association with cryptorchidism (Main et al. 2006). This study was excluded in the review by Radke et al., 2018 as they did not include studies which used tissues other than urine (Radke et al. 2018).

Few studies have assessed the possible role of phthalates exposure in female reproductive toxicity. The risk of endometriosis was specifically evaluated and the evidence from these few studies on a possible link between phthalates and endometriosis are insufficient. The study by Weuve et al. (2010) including 1200 women did not show any relationship between increased urinary concentrations of MBzP and the prevalence of uterine diseases (endometriosis and leiomyomata). In another study with a smaller study population, Itoh et al. (2009) did not find any relationship between urinary concentrations of MBzP and endometriosis (Itoh et al. 2009). Data from a study by Upson et al., 2013 in women of the U.S. Pacific Northwest suggested increased endometriosis risk with greater urinary concentrations of mono-benzyl phthalate (MBzP), even though not statistically significant (Upson et al. 2013). The effects of phthalate exposure on ovulatory function and certain hormonal levels (oestradiol, progesterone, LH, FSH) suggested in animal studies are not reported in women (INSERM, 2011). In a systematic review, conducted by Radke et al. 2019 on female reproductive outcomes and phthalate exposure, outcomes of the studies reviewed were lacking consistency, effect sizes were often small or no associations found. The authors concluded that there was indeterminate evidence for BBzP and pubertal development, time to pregnancy and spontaneous abortion. Only for the outcomes preterm birth the evidence was considered slight, even though study outcomes were not consistent. The reasoning by the authors was the rather low exposure levels of BBzP compared to other phthalates in these studies, which might prevent detecting an association (Radke et al. 2019).

In summary, Radke et al., 2018 evaluated the evidence of BBzP having effects on semen quality, i.e. motility and on decreased fecundity as moderate. The evidence for causing effects on AGD, hypospadias and/or cryptorchidism were considered as being slight and the evidence for pubertal development and testosterone was valued indeterminate. However, often the study results were inconsistently and sometimes lower exposure levels were reported or only few studies were available for BBzP compared to other phthalates, which might have an effect on the detectability of associations between BBzP exposure and health outcomes. In general, epidemiological studies are linked to some uncertainties and it is sometimes difficult to directly link exposures to a single chemical with health outcomes (ECB 2007). Nevertheless, they contribute to the understanding of the underlying mechanisms and to the overall evidence seen in animal studies, supporting the

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 161

validity of the biological relevance of adverse effects on the reproduction and development of the offspring. The outcomes of the epidemiological studies available are inconsistent, however, they do give a hint that BBzP exposure is associated with male reproductive effects, but the current knowledge base on human exposure to BBzP is not adequate to derive HBM-GVs directly based on human data, neither for the general population nor for the workers. Therefore, the HBM-GVs are not derived based on a human study but from a POD related to critical effects seen in animal studies, summarised below.).

5.2.2 Animal studies and *in vitro* tests

5.2.2.1 Acute toxicity

BBzP exhibits low acute toxicity in animals with oral LD50 values above 2000 mg/kg bw in rats, mice, and guinea pigs and dermal LD50 values >2000 mg/kg bw in rats, mice, and rabbits (ECB 2007, NICNAS 2015, Hartwig 2018).

5.2.2.2 Skin and eye irritation

BBzP is thought not to be skin irritating, but slightly eye irritating in rabbits (ECB 2007).

5.2.2.3 Sensitisation

In a study in rabbits, BBzP showed slight skin sensitising potential, however, negative results were obtained in ear swelling tests in other animals, as mice and guinea pigs (ECB 2007, NICNAS 2015, ECHA & Danish EPA 2016). According to the European Chemicals Bureau, there is no need for a classification of BBzP as sensitizer according to CLP criteria (ECB 2007).

5.2.2.4 Repeated dose toxicity

Repeated dose toxicity after oral administration of BBzP has been studied in different animal species as mice and dogs, but mostly in rats. In summary, rats showed to be the most vulnerable species after oral exposure. Here, increased organ weight of liver and kidney and histopathological changes of liver, kidney, pancreas and testes were observed in studies of different strains. Also, testicular atrophy and in one study additionally decreased testosterone levels were observed (Hammond BG 1987, Piersma et al. 2000). BBzP has been shown to induce peroxisome proliferation in the rat liver of both sexes. However, the pathway of peroxisome proliferation via PPAR alpha in rats is not considered to be relevant for humans (ECB 2007, RAC & SEAC, 2012, NICNAS 2015, Hartwig 2018).

For exposure via inhalation, only three studies in rats which are described in the review by Hammond et al. (1987) are available. Reduced body weight, atrophy of spleen and testes, increased liver and kidney weight and lower serum glucose levels were observed. In contrast to the other studies, the 13-weeks inhalation study in Sprague-Dawley rats included a complete histopathology, except for the larynx. Here, the critical effects observed were an increase of absolute and relative weights of kidney and liver with no histopathological changes at the highest concentration (789 mg/m³) in both sexes. A decrease of serum glucose levels in male rats at 789 mg/m³ (Table 2) was also observed. The effect on the liver was considered by the authors as not relevant to humans, as assumed to be due to peroxisome proliferation (Hammond BG 1987).

Limited data is available for repeated exposure via the dermal route as only one study was reported in the EU RAR having poor quality (ECB 2007, NICNAS 2015).

5.2.2.5 Genotoxicity and mutagenicity

According to EU criteria, BBzP is not considered to be mutagenic as most *in vivo* and *in vitro* tests showed negative results (ECB 2007). *In vitro* assays in several bacterial and fungal cells (e.g.

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 162

Salmonella typhimurium, E.coli, Saccharomyces cerevisiae) and in mouse lymphoma and hamster ovary cells a showed no signs of mutagenicity (NTP 1997a; ECB, 2007; NICNAS 2015; Hartwig, 2018). A bone marrow test for sister chromatid exchanges in mice showed positive results by demonstrating a positive trend in inducing sister chromatid exchanges (SCE) and chromosomal aberrations (CA). For the CA study, the percentage of the frequency of cells with CA was only significant at the highest dose (5000 mg/kg bw/d) and the number of CA per cell was not significantly altered compared to the controls. The results from the SCE study were only weak and the test was not repeatable (NTP 1997a, ECB 2007, Hartwig 2018). Therefore, the overall results were considered weak, but a cytotoxic effect cannot be excluded (RAC & SEAC 2012, Hartwig 2018).

5.2.2.6 Carcinogenicity

Long-term studies investigating the carcinogenicity of orally administered BBzP were conducted in rats and mice. For the latter species, no signs of carcinogenicity or other histopathologic effects were observed. However, in rats increased tumour incidences were observed. In summary, increased incidence of benign pancreas tumours were observed in male rats at the highest dose (12000 ppm), whereas this effect was only minimal in female rats. The effect was not seen at a low-caloric diet although higher doses were used. In addition, an increased incidence of mononuclear cell leukaemia was observed in female rats. However, the effect did not occur in studies on other mammalian species (RAC & SEAC 2012) and therefore is not regarded as relevant for humans. Female rats showed increased incidences of papilloma of the bladder. As no historic controls are available, these results are difficult to interpret (ECB 2007). The overall evidence does not allow to draw distinct conclusion. Several authorities evaluated the evidence base as not sufficient to classify BBzP as carcinogen. However, it was stated by the EBC, that BBzP might be in between lines of no classification and the classification as carcinogen Cat. 3 (ECB 2007). Further studies are needed to examine the relationship of BBzP exposure and carcinogenicity.

5.2.2.7 Effects on reproduction and development

The effects of BBzP and its metabolites on fertility, reproduction and development have been extensively studied and it has been shown that as for other anti-androgenic phthalates, BBzP induces the so-called "phthalate syndrome" in rats. This syndrome is characterised by different reproductive abnormalities in male offspring of rats exposed during pregnancy within the critical time window of gestational days 15-17, which marks the period of testosterone-driven sexual differentiation. The effects are among others malformations of the testes, epididymis and Gubernaculum testis, cryptorchidism, hypospadias, reduced semen count and others caused by interference with the development of foetal Leydig cells, reduced or inhibited testicular testosterone production and reduced production of insulin-like 3 peptide hormone (German HBM Commission 2011). It might be assumed, that many of these effects are biologically relevant for humans as the effects of the phthalate syndrome in rats have similarities with the observed testicular dysgenesis syndrome (TDS) in humans. According to the National Research Council (US) Committee on the Health Risks of Phthalates "there is a remarkable overlap in response between the phthalate syndrome and the hypothesised human testicular dysgenesis syndrome, except for responses for which rats are sexually dimorphic (retention of nipples)" (NRC 2008).

In several studies in rats (diet, gavage) with different durations, BBzP has been demonstrated to affect the reproductive organs and fertility of male animals. Main effects observed were a decrease in the relative weight of testis, testis degeneration, damage to epididymis, prostate and seminal vesicle and reduced sperm concentrations in the epididymis (RAR 2007, NICNAS 2015). On the contrary, a 2-year diet study in mice did not find any alteration of the reproductive organs related to

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 163

BBzP exposure (NTP 1982). At higher BBzP concentrations in rats, reduced fertility was observed, in addition to increases in relative liver and kidney weights. In studies investigating the developmental toxicity in rats and mice after exposure to BBzP or its metabolites (MnBP or MBzP), developmental toxicity in offspring included prenatal mortality, reduced fetal weight, and malformed reproductive organs. In maternal animals main results included reduced body weight gain and increased liver weight, accompanied by a decreased food consumption (RAC & SEAC 2012).

The European agencies EFSA and ECHA identified four key studies relevant to be used as basis for the identification of NOAELs and further derivation of a TDI or DNEL. These studies are summarised below:

A two-generation reproductive study was conducted by Nagao (2000) in male and female Sprague-Dawley rats after oral administration of BBzP (0, 20, 100, 500 mg/kg bw/ d). At the highest dose of 500 mg/kg bw/d, significantly decreased body weight was observed in F0 parental male animals, although no differences in food consumption were seen. Increased salivation in all animals at this dose was observed immediately after dosing, whereas at 100 mg/kg bw/d this effect was observed in 18 of 25 males and 10 of 25 females. No effects on body weight or food consumption were observed in female rats. Kidney weight was increased in both sexes in a dose-dependent manner and for males an increase in liver weight was observed at 500 mg/kg bw/d, whereas for females at that dose, a decrease of the ovary weight was seen. Levels of testosterone in serum were decreased and concentrations of FSH were increased in a dose-dependent manner in adult F0 male rats from the 100 mg/kg bw/d dose on. However, significant differences compared to controls were only observed in the highest dose group (500 mg/kg bw/d). Body weights of female and male F1-offspring were significantly reduced at birth in both dose groups, 100 and 500 mg/kg bw/d. The AGD was significantly decreased and preputial separation was delayed in male pups at 500 mg/kg bw/d. Additionally, an increase of AGD in female pups was noticed at the same dose. However, the latter was not as significant as the decrease of AGD observed in males ($p = 0.05$ versus $p=0.01$). At the highest dose, changes in testis and significant decreases in serum testosterone concentration and LH concentration were seen in male F1 rats after puberty. In addition, organ weights of testes, epididymis and ventral prostate were decreased significantly in F1-offspring post weaning. The authors identified a NOAEL of 20 mg/kg bw/d BBzP based on the reproductive effects in both parental animals and their offspring (Nagao et al. 2000).

In a two-generation diet study by Tyl et al. (2004), rats were given 0, 750, 3750, and 11,250 ppm BBzP corresponding to 0, 50, 250 and 750 mg/kg bw/d. Systemic toxicity was observed at 750 mg BBzP /kg bw/d for F0 and F1 adults as well as reproductive toxicity in F1 adults. Adult animals of F0 and F1 generations showed increased absolute and relative liver weights. In addition, F1 offspring showed delayed puberty onset in both sexes. The AGD was significantly reduced in F1 and F2 males and reduced body weights per litter were determined. For F1 and F2 male offspring nipple and areolae retention, as well as malformation of the reproductive system, were observed. At the lower dose of 250 mg/kg bw/d, significantly reduced AGD in F1 and F2 male offspring was still observed (Tyl et al. 2004). However, it needs to be noted that these findings were not accompanied with other effects on reproductive development, structures, or functions and AGDs were in the range of historic controls. Therefore the biological relevance of the results for this dosage are ambiguous (Hartwig 2018, Tyl et al. 2004). The authors concluded in identifying a NOAEL of 250 mg/kg bw/d for F1-parental systemic and reproductive toxicity. A NOEL for offspring toxicity was set at 50 mg/kg bw/d by the authors based on reduced AGD at birth at 250 mg/kg bw/ d with no other effects on development, function and organs of reproduction (Tyl et al. 2004). In contrast to the study of Nagao et al., testosterone serum levels or any other hormone levels were not measured.

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 164

Another two-generation study by Aso et al. (2005) revealed that BBzP exposure resulted in damage to the reproductive organs as testes, testicular seminiferous tubules, as well as sperm cells and/or residual germ cells in the epididymal lumina in F1 offspring at 100 mg/kg bw/d BBzP. At higher doses, epididymal weights of F0 generation was low, F1 offspring showed a delayed preputial separation of the penis. F1 adults showed a decreased fertility index. Decreased weight of the spleen was seen in both F0 and F1 generations. Furthermore, decreased body weights of F1-offspring and increase of AGD in F1-females and decrease of AGD in F2-males were observed. In this study, no changes on any serum hormone level (LH, FSH, testosterone, oestradiol) was found in the 400 mg/kg bw/d dose group compared to the controls. The authors stated that “[...] in the parental animals, the no observed effect level (NOEL) and the no observed adverse effect level (NOAEL) were less than 100 mg/kg/day, and no serious effects on the reproductive capacity were induced at doses less than 200 mg/kg/day. The NOEL and NOAEL for the growth and development of offspring were concluded to be less than 100 mg/kg/day. [...]” (Aso et al. 2005).

Ahmad et al. (2014) confirmed the results from previous studies and could demonstrate a significant reduction in body weight of the female F0 generation on gestational day 21, and a significant reduction of the body weight of F1 male offspring at doses of 20 and 100 mg/kg bw/d. In addition, in F1 adult male rats at doses of 100 mg/kg bw/d BBzP impaired sperm quality parameters as reduced motility was observed, the organ weights of kidney, epididymis and prostate was significantly reduced and a significant decline in serum testosterone level was observed at 100 mg/kg bw/ d. It is noteworthy, that serum testosterone was already reduced at 4 mg/kg bw/d, but not significantly. A non-significant decrease in testicular spermatid count and daily sperm production was also observed at this dose (Ahmad et al. 2014). It needs to be noted that the age of the parent animals was only about 10 weeks instead of 13-14 weeks when mated, which is necessary according to OECD guidance 443 and 416 (Hartwig 2018).

In addition to the multi-generational studies described above, further studies in male rats exposed orally to BBzP showed adverse effects on the male reproduction system or capacity, including lesions in reproductive organs, lowering of sperm concentrations and decreased fertility. The most comprehensive study is the ten-week NTP study (1997). In this study, male F344 rats (15 animals/group) were exposed to BBzP in the diet at levels of 0, 300, 2800, or 25000 ppm for 10 weeks (corresponding to approximately doses of 0, 20, 200, 2200 mg/kg bw/d). Each male rat was then mated to 2 unexposed females. The final body weights and body weight gain of the high-dose group were significantly lower than that of the controls. Minimal changes in haematological parameters and a decrease of both the absolute and relative weights of prostate and testis were observed in the high-dose group. The other effects observed at the highest dose included degeneration of the seminiferous tubular germinal epithelium and significantly reduced weight of right cauda, right epididymis, and right testis. Epididymal spermatozoa concentrations were significantly reduced in a dose-related manner at the two highest doses. However, histopathological evidence of hypospermia and a decrease in fertility index were observed only at the highest dose (NTP 1997a). According to the NTP-CERHR (2003), the effect on epididymal spermatozoal concentrations at the 200 mg/kg bw/d is not sufficient as starting point to estimate a NOAEL. On the one hand, the fertility in this dose group was not different from the controls, and on the other hand, the time required for sperm regeneration in the epididymis after ejaculation (4-7 days) was not respected. In addition, the results of the NTP work in rats exposed to BBzP for 26 weeks using a similar protocol did not show any effect on sperm reserve at 550 mg/kg bw/d. Therefore, a NOAEL of 200 mg/kg bw/d was identified based on effects on testes (lesions, weight), epididymis (lesions), prostate (weight), sperm reserve and fertility achievement observed at 2200 mg/kg bw/d (NTP-CERHR 2003).

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 165

The effects observed in the above-mentioned animal studies clearly show that BBzP induces the “phthalate syndrome”, however only few studies have investigated testosterone levels or in particular, inhibition of testicular testosterone production in rats as underlying mechanism for the “phthalate syndrome”. A study by Howdeshell et al., 2008 investigated the inhibition of foetal testicular testosterone by five different phthalates. On that account, pregnant Sprague Dawley dams were exposed by gavage to 0, 100, 300, 600 and 900 mg/kg bw/d BBzP from GD 8-18. BBzP significantly decreased maternal body weight gain in the dose groups of 300, 600 and 900 mg/kg bw/d. The number of live foetuses was significantly reduced from 13.8 ± 0.8 in the control group to 10.5 ± 0.5 and 5.0 ± 3.0 in the 600 and 900 mg/kg bw/d dose group, respectively. On GD 18 dams were killed and foetuses removed and killed immediately. Testes from the first three males were used for ex vivo testis hormone production testing as described by Wilson et al., 2004. BBzP was found to significantly inhibit foetal testicular testosterone production at doses of 300 mg/kg bw /d or higher.

The same was observed for DnBP, DEHP and DiBP. The authors concluded, that BBzP has a similar potency as the aforementioned phthalates with an ED50 of 440 ± 16 mg/kg/day. This was confirmed by a study of Furr et al. (2014) in which a short-term in vivo screening tool was described in order to test efficiently but with fewer animals than standard tests the chemical’s potential to disrupt foetal testosterone synthesis. Here, pregnant rats were repeatedly dosed on GD 14-18 with a high dose (750 mg/kg bw/d) of a selected chemical and necropsied on GD 18 to measure ex vivo testis testosterone levels. Testosterone levels were determined from three males per litter from three litters per chemical. Sample sizes were found to be sufficient to detect reduction of testosterone production greater than 50 % of the control, but not to detect effects of chemicals which only reduce testosterone production by 20-25%. In order to determine the effective dose 50 (ED50) values, dose-response studies for some of the chemicals were conducted. Here, Harlan SD rats were given 0, 11, 33, 100, 300, 600 or 900 mg/kg bw/d BBzP. BBzP was found to significantly reduce the testosterone production in a dose-dependent manner (from 100 mg/kg bw /d on) with BBzP showing intermediate potency in regard to testosterone production with an ED50 of 172.4 mg/ kg bw/ d. From this study, a NOEL of 33 mg/kg bw/ d can be determined. Kortenkamp and Koch (Kortenkamp and Koch 2019; Accepted manuscript, December 2019) have assessed new evidence about low dose male developmental effects and updated the intake values accordingly by calculating benchmark doses as POD inter alia in order to be able to refine and harmonise the phthalate mixture risk assessment (MRA).

The key event for inducing anti-androgenicity was regarded to be testosterone suppression. The authors suggested new reference doses for phthalates for use in MRA, among others 10 µg/kg/d for BBzP. This was based on a calculated BMDL05 of 1 mg/ kg bw/d as POD by using the study of Furr et al. (2014). This value is supported by results from the multi-generation study of Ahmad et al., 2014 which revealed significantly decreased serum testosterone levels of F1 adult rats at 100 mg/kg bw/d and non-significant reductions in serum testosterone levels were already seen at 4 mg/kg (Ahmad et al. 2014). In contrast, Aso et al. (2005) did not find changes in serum testosterone levels up to the highest dose tested (400 mg/kg bw/d) neither in F0 nor F1 parental animals. Nagao et al.,2000 only observed a significant decrease in testosterone serum levels at doses of 500 mg/kg bw/day in F1 and F0 adult rats (Aso et al. 2005, Nagao et al. 2000). It is noteworthy, that the studies mentioned measured serum testosterone in adult rats as compared to the studies by Howdeshell et al., and Furr et al., who measured inhibition of foetal testicular testosterone. As the effects related to the phthalate syndrome are caused by anti-androgenic action in the foetus, i.e. testosterone suppression at the critical window of testosterone-driven sexual differentiation, it might be better measuring foetal testosterone levels as indicator for possible

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 166

subsequent effects. It needs to be noted that the Ahmad study as well as the Furr study have some shortcomings. The former was not conducted according to OECD guidelines as the age of the rats when mated were only 10 weeks.

Nevertheless, the study was acknowledged and taken into consideration by ECHA for deriving the DNEL for BBzP. In one part of the study of Furr et al., 2014, namely the dose-response studies, high variations in the response were observed in the 100 mg dose group. Whereas in one block, more than 50% T suppression could be observed (T production 5.43 ± 0.58 ng/testis for 100 mg BBzP, n=2 vs. 11.63 ± 0.13 ng/testis for control, n=3), no effect could be seen in the other block at the same dose (T production 9.65 ± 1.08 ng/testis for 100 mg, n=4 BBzP vs. 10.94 ± 1.62 ng/testis for control, n=4).

However, in general testosterone level are known to vary (Bartke et al. 1973, Heywood 1980, Lee et al. 1975) and the clear dose-response relationship with a high statistical significance observed in one block gives confidence in the outcome.

Table 19: Overview of key studies and main findings for derivation of toxicity reference values (TRVs)

Author, Year, Type of study	Exposure Conditions	Results	NOAELs/LOAELs
Nagao et al., 2000; Oral, 2-generation study on Crj:CD (SD) IGS rats, 35 per sex	F0: from 12 weeks before mating until necropsy F1: after weaning (PND 22) until necropsy; Per gavage; Doses: 0, 20, 100, 500 mg/kg bw/d	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> F0: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *in F0 males: increased LH in 20 mg/kg bw/d group; salivation, TSH and serum FSH increased at 100 mg/kg bw/d and at 500 mg/kg bw/d increased salivation, increased absolute & relative kidney weights, increased relative brain, lung and liver weights, decreased body weights while no differences in food consumption, increased FSH, decrease in serum testosterone concentration, T3 and T4; *in F0 females: increased TSH at 20 mg/kg bw/d; salivation, absolute and relative kidney weights increased at 100 mg/kg bw/d or higher (not dose-dependent); and at 500 mg/kg bw/d increased salivation, absolute and relative weights of ovary reduced; T4 serum levels decreased and serum prolactin levels increased F1 offspring: at 100 mg/kg bw /d in males decreased body weight and decreased TSH; decreased body weight and decreased T3 in females; at 500 mg/kg bw/d decreased viability at PND 1-4; decreased AGD in male pups on PND 0 and increased AGD in female pups; body weight were decreased in both sexes at PND 22; in males decreased absolute and relative weight of testis, decreased weight of epididymis, serum FSH was decreased and decreased number of sperms in epididymis; in females absolute weights of ovaries was decreased and relative weights of uterus were increased Effect on body weight in F1 offspring was reversible after 4 days 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> NOAEL= 100 mg/kg bw/d for developmental effects as determined by

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 167

Author, Year, Type of study	Exposure Conditions	Results	NOAELs/LOAELs
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In F1 male adults, decreased body weight, absolute heart weight and absolute kidney weight was decreased after 10 weeks at 100 mg/kg bw/d; at 500 mg/kg bw/d delayed preputial separation was observed, increased absolute brain weights, increased relative liver, thyroid tissue and pituitary weights, decreased absolute spleen, epididymis, ventral prostate and testis weights, decreased serum, LH and T4 levels, atrophy in seminiferous tubules with decreased number of germ cells, increases in interstitial oedema, decreased number of sperm in epididymis 	
Tyl et al., 2004; Oral, 2-generation dietary study on CD Sprague-Dawley rats; 30 per sex/group	<p>F0: from 10 weeks before mating until weaning (PND 21)</p> <p>F1: after weaning (PND 21) for 10 weeks;</p> <p>Per feed;</p> <p>Doses: 0, 750, 3750, 11,250 ppm (~ 0, 50, 250, 750 mg/kg bw/d)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> F0: absolute kidney weights increased at 250 mg/kg bw/d in males; absolute and relative kidney weights increased at 250 mg/kg bw/d in females. At 750 mg/kg bw/d, body weight and body weight gain were decreased; absolute and relative liver weights were increased, relative kidney weights were increased, slight histological lesions in the liver in males; in females body weight and body weight gain was decreased, absolute and relative liver weights were increased, absolute and relative ovary weights and uterus weight was decreased; slight histological lesions in the liver in females F1 offspring: decreased AGD/litter in males at 250 mg/kg bw/d and at 750 mg/kg bw/d decreased body weight/litter, decreased food consumption and body weight, increased number of nipples per animal F1 adults: at 750 mg/kg bw/d mating and fertility index were significantly reduced for both sexes; reduced absolute (but not relative) testes, epididymis, seminal vesicles/coagulating gland weights, reduced absolute and relative prostate weights, reduced epididymal sperm number, motility, progressive motility, and increased gross and histopathologic findings in the testis and epididymis in males at 750 mg/kg bw/ d; in females at 750 mg/kg bw/d reduced uterine implantation sites, and total and live pups per litter on PND 0, increased absolute and relative uterine weight with no histopathologic lesions in female reproductive tract organs, reduced ovarian weights at 750 mg/ kg bw/d in the absence of any effects on ovarian primordial follicle counts at this dietary dose, F1 females carrying F2 litters at this dose exhibited reduced number of litters and reduced number of total and live pups/litter at birth, with no effects on pre- or postnatal survival 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> NOAEL = 50 mg/kg bw/d for reduced AGD in F1 and F2 male offspring at birth

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 168

Author, Year, Type of study	Exposure Conditions	Results	NOAELs/LOAELs
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> F2: significantly reduced AGD at 250 mg/kg bw/d and 750 mg/kg/bw/d, increased nipple retention at 750 mg/kg bw/d 	
Aso et al. 2005; Oral, 2-generation study on Crj:CD (SD) IGS rats, 24 per sex	Per gavage; Doses: 0, 100, 200, 400 mg/kg bw/d for 7 days per week	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> F0: increased absolute weight of left kidney at 200 mg/kg bw/d and at 400 mg/kg bw/d relative kidney, left kidney weights were increased and absolute weight of left epididymis was decreased in males; in females absolute and relative liver weights were increased as well as absolute and relative weight of left kidney at 200 mg/kg bw/d; at 400 mg/kg bw/d relative weights of left and right kidney was increased F1 parents: at 200 mg/kg bw/d increased relative liver and decreased absolute weight of left epididymis, softening of the testes and diffuse atrophy of testicular seminiferous tubules, decreased spermatozoa, residual germ cells I epididymal lumina were observed at 100 mg/kg bw/d or higher, at 400 mg/kg bw/d significantly lower absolute weights of the seminal vesicles, increased weights of the thyroid and decreased absolute weight of right and left epididymis were observed, the number of incidences of small testes were increased significantly and fewer animals had preputial separation of the penis; hypoplasia in epididymis, significantly diffuse atrophy in testes and Leydig cells in males; in females: significant increased ADG at 100 mkg/kg bw/d and higher and relative liver weight was increased at 400 mg/kg bw/d F2 adult males: significant decrease of AGD at 100 mg/kg bw/d and higher F1, F2 offspring: only in males decreased relative and absolute weights of spleen was observed at 400 mg/kg bw/d at PND 25-27 for F1 and PND 21 for F2 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> LOAEL = 100 mg/kg bw/d based on effects on growth and development of offspring
Ahmad et al. 2014; Oral, 1-generation study on Albino rats; pregnant rats were divided into 9 groups with minimum 6 individuals each	F0: from GD 14 to parturition; Per gavage; 0, 4, 20, 100 mg/kg bw/d	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> F0: gestational duration was increased at 4 mg/kg bw/d F1: significant reduction of F1 male pups body weight at doses of 4, 20 and 100 mg/kg; organ weights of kidney, epididymis and prostate was significantly reduced; significant decline in serum testosterone level at 100 mg/kg bw/d in addition to significant reduction in epididymal sperm count and sperm motility and significant increase in sperm abnormalities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> LOAEL = 100 mg/kg bw /d based on developmental and reproductive effects in F1 offspring
NTP, 1997; 10- week study in Fisher 344 rats; 15 males/group	Administration in the diet; 20, 200 and 2200 mg/kg bw/d for 10 weeks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> At doses \geq 200 mg/kg bw/d decreased epididymal spermatozoa concentration in F0 At 2200 mg/kg bw/d alterations in haematological values, decreased body, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> NTP-CERHR (2003), the effect on epididymal spermatozoal

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 169

Author, Year, Type of study	Exposure Conditions	Results	NOAELs/LOAELs
		prostate and testes weight, degeneration, in seminiferous tubules, no pregnancy after mating	<p>concentrations at the 200 mg/kg/d is not sufficient as starting point to estimate a NOAEL.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A NOAEL of 200 mg/kg/d was identified based on effects on testes, epididymis, prostate, sperm reserve and fertility in another study (NTP-CERHR 2003).

5.2.3 Conclusion and assessment of different bodies

According to the Restriction Report on 4 phthalates prepared by ECHA and the Danish Environmental Protection Agency, DEHP, DnBP, DiBP and BBzP are classified as toxic to reproduction in category 1B, as they exhibit a range of effects known as phthalate syndrome induced by anti-androgenic action in the foetus. BBzP is known for inhibiting foetal testosterone production, reducing male AGD, increasing incidence of genital malformations (hypospadias and cryptorchidism), delaying puberty onset, reducing semen quality and causing testicular changes. Key effects for identifying NOAELs for a DNEL setting were identified as the anti-androgenic effects observed in developmental animal studies, e.g. reduced AGD, reduced organ weight of prostate and epididymis, change in spermatid motility and sperm count observed in the studies from Aso et al., 2005; Tyl et al., 2004; Nagao et al., 2000 and Ahmad et al., 2014. In 2012, RAC identified the reduced AGD seen in rats as most sensitive endpoint for BBzP seen at 250 mg/kg bw/d in the Tyl study and at 500 mg/kg bw/d in the Nagao study with NOAELs determined of being 50 and 100 mg/kg bw/d, respectively (RAC & SEAC 2012). Aso et al. (2005) observed decreasing AGD in male offspring in all doses from 100 mg/kg bw/day, whereby no NOAEL could be determined and the LOAEL of 100 mg/kg bw/d was considered. An overall NOAEL of 50 mg/kg bw/d was selected by RAC (RAC & SEAC 2012). In addition to these studies, the Restriction Report considered the study by Ahmad, et al., 2014 which observed reduce weights of reproductive organs and decreased sperm motility and counts at 100 mg/kg bw/d, with a NOAEL of 20 mg/kg bw/d. In accordance with the conclusion of RAC 2017, ECHA and the Danish EPA, 2016 have determined an overall NOAEL of 50 mg/kg bw/day together with a LOAEL of 100 mg/kg bw/day as starting point for their DNEL derivation by combining these studies (RAC & SEAC 2017a).

An overall AF of 100 was chosen to derive a DNEL of 0.5 mg/kg bw/day for external oral dose as well as for internal dose (a 100% absorption fraction for the oral route being estimated). It was stated as uncertainty of the DNEL derivation, that endocrine sensitive endpoints that were investigated for DEHP and DnBP such as testicular and mammary histology of male adults and dysgenesis of external genitalia were not assessed for BBzP. In fact, Howdeshell et al., 2008

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 170

revealed that the potency of testosterone reduction in foetuses of BBzP is similar to DEHP and DnBP. Therefore, it cannot be excluded that further effects could be observed at doses lower than 50 mg/kg bw/d. For comparison, a LOAEL of 2 mg/kg bw/d was selected for DnBP based on male mammary gland alterations and a NOAEL of 4.8 mg/kg bw/d was set for DEHP based on testicular effects as reduced testis weight and germ cell depletion (ECHA & Danish EPA 2016). Re-evaluation of the DEHP data by Kortenkamp and Koch (Kortenkamp and Koch 2019; Accepted manuscript, December 2019) even led to a lower value of 1 mg/kg bw /d as NOAEL. In 2017, RAC noted that in light of the above mentioned uncertainties, the POD for BBzP might be reconsidered and “could potentially be considerably lower than the current PoD” (RAC & SEAC 2017a).

In fact, a recent study by Furr et al., 2014 confirmed the results by Howdeshell, showing that BBzP significantly reduced the testosterone production in a dose-dependent manner (from 100 mg/kg bw /d on) and has intermediate potency in suppressing foetal testosterone production. Based on this study a NOAEL of 33 mg/kg bw/ d can be determined.

In 2005, EFSA derived a TDI of 0.5 mg/kg bw/d based on a NOAEL of 50 mg/kg bw/d determined in the study of Tyl et al., 2004, where reduced AGD in F1 and F2 rat males at birth at 250 mg/kg bw/d were observed. An uncertainty factor of 100 was applied to this Point of Departure (POD). The BBzP reproduction and development effects, and in particular critical effects observed on the male reproductive system development, are according to EFSA the most sensitive endpoints (2005). This statement was recently confirmed in a draft scientific opinion of EFSA (2019). However, it has to be noted, that currently a group-TDI of 50 µg/kg bw/d is proposed for the sum of BBzP, DEHP, DiNP and DnBP, expressed as DEHP equivalents according to the following formula [GPDEq], µg/kg food) = DEHP*1 + DnBP*5 + BBzP*0.1 + DiNP*0.3) (EFSA 2019). The reasoning is the common mode of action, i.e. foetal testosterone reduction. For DiNP, however, effects on the liver are still the most sensitive endpoint, thus an additional assessment factor of 3.3 were applied to account for the differences in potency between the effects on liver and foetal testosterone (EFSA, 2019; Draft).

The German MAK Commission derived a MAK value of 20 mg/m³ based on a 13-weeks inhalation study in rats (Monsanto, 1982), the critical effects being identified as increased absolute and relative kidney and liver weights (Hartwig 2018). The MAK Commission states that the value is supported by multigenerational dietary studies showing effects on the male reproductive organs, on fertility and on the development at higher doses. The inhalation study was considered as being reliable except some minor methodological uncertainties (no histopathological investigation of larynx and lesser histological sections done than should be according to current criteria). At 789 mg/m³, an increase in absolute and relative liver and kidneys weights was observed in male and female rats and a decrease of serum-glucose levels was observed in male rats. This concentration was set as a LOAEC. As a result, 218 mg/m³ was determined as a NOAEC. However, it was noted that no micro- or macroscopic findings accompanied the increase in organ weights and therefore the NOAEC is considered to be conservative (Hartwig 2018).

The OEL Committee of ANSES derived an 8h-OEL of 13 mg/m³ to prevent the reprotoxic effects of this substance. This value is also protective for all others effects for the workers population. Since no appropriate human studies could be identified, the OEL is based on a NOAEL of 200 mg/kg bw /d from an oral animal study³⁴ (10-week study by the NTP (1997)), with the critical effects being

³⁴ Multi-generational study by Tyl et al. (2001, 2004), cannot be used to establish a reference value for the occupational field. Indeed, the end of pregnancy and perinatal exposure conditions are not considered relevant for an occupational exposure scenario, as pregnant women (as soon as they become aware of their pregnancy, most often by the end of the 1st trimester) and breast-feeding mothers should not be exposed to BBzP at the workplace.

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 171

the alteration of reproductive organs and impaired fertility in rat males related to anti-androgenic activity of BBzP and MBzP. However, no Biological limit value was derived due to i) the lack of epidemiological studies assessing a link between urinary MBzP concentrations and health effects, ii) no available field studies correlating atmospheric concentrations of BBzP with urinary concentration of MBzP and iii) as extrapolating a BBzP oral human equivalent dose into a corresponding urinary MBzP concentration was considered as involving too many uncertainties³⁵ (2016).

The U.S. Chronic Hazard Advisory Panel (CHAP) studied the health effects of phthalates and phthalate alternatives used in children’s toys and child care articles and gave recommendations whether any phthalate (or a combinations of phthalates) other than those permanently banned, including the phthalates covered by the interim ban, or phthalate alternatives should be prohibited. The Panel concluded that “[...] A relatively complete dataset suggests that exposure to BBP can cause reproductive or (non-reproductive) developmental effects. BBP can also induce other target organ effects, such as changes in body weight and liver weight. [...]” The authors determined a NOAEL of 100 mg/kg-d from the Nagao et al. (2000) study, but noted that the NOAELs ranged from 50 – 250 mg/kg bw/d and that based on the findings of the study of Howdeshell et al. (2008), who reported significantly reduced fetal testosterone production at 300 mg/kg bw/d or greater, the committee decided to use a conservative approach and to recommend a NOAEL of 50 mg/kg bw/d. They concluded that a permanently ban of BBzP in toys and childcare articles should be maintained.

Table 20: Overview of the derivation of toxicity reference values

Agency	Key study(ies)	Endpoint	Point of departure (µg/kw bw/d)	Assessment / Uncertainty factors	TRV
EFSA, 2019	For BBzP: Tyl et al., 2001; 2004 (2-generation rat toxicity study)	reduced anogenital distance (AGD) in F1-and F2- males at birth in the 250 mg BBzP/kg bw per day group	NOAEL 50 mg/kg bw/d	<p>100</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 2.5 for interspecies differences - 10 for intraspecies differences - 4 for allometric scaling for rats 	<p>Group-TDI (expressed as DEHP equivalents: BBzP *0.1)</p> <p>50 µg/kg bw/d</p>
EFSA, 2005b	Tyl et al., 2001; 2004 (2-generation rat toxicity study)	reduced anogenital distance (AGD) in F1-and F2- males at birth in the 250mg BBzP/kg bw per day group	NOEAL 50 mg/kg bw/ d	<p>100</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 2.5 for interspecies differences - 10 for intraspecies differences - 4 for allometric scaling for rats 	<p>TDI 0.5 mg/kg bw /d</p>

³⁵ The OEL Committee of ANSES proposed a biological reference value of 40 µg.L⁻¹ or 30 µg.g⁻¹ creatinine. This value corresponds to the 95th percentile of the distribution of urinary concentrations in men and women (over the age of 20 years), taken from the 2009-2010 campaign of American national NHANES survey.

Agency	Key study(ies)	Endpoint	Point of departure (µg/kg bw/d)	Assessment / Uncertainty factors	TRV
ECHA, 2017a	Tyl et al., 2001; 2004 (2-generation rat toxicity study)	reduced anogenital distance (AGD) in F1-and F2- males at birth in the 250mg BBzP/kg bw per day group	NOAEL 50 mg/kg bw/ d	<p>100</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 2.5 for interspecies differences - 10 for intraspecies differences - 4 for allometric scaling for rats 	DNEL internal dose: 0.5 mg/kg bw /d
	Aso et al., 2005 (2-generation rat toxicity study)	reduced AGD in F2-males at all dose groups (from 100 BBzP/kg bw per day group on)	LOAEL of 100 mg /kg bw/ d		
	Nagao, 2000 (2-generation rat toxicity study)	effects on reproductive organs and preputial separation at 200 BBzP/kg bw per day	NOAEL of 100 mg /kg bw/ d		
	Ahmad, 2014 (2-generation rat toxicity study)	reductions in the weight of the reproductive organs, altered sperm counts and motility at 100 mg/kg bw/d	LOAEL of 100 mg /kg bw/ d		
	Combined LOAELs with NOAELs and determined an overall NOAEL of 50 mg/ kg bw /d				
MAK Commission	Monsanto Co, 1982 (13-week inhalation study in rats)	Increase of absolute and relative weights of kidney and liver of male and female rats at 789 mg/m ³	NOAEC of 218 mg/m³	<p>0.125</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 0.5 for allometric scaling for rats - 0.5 for study duration - 0.5 for difference in respiratory volume 	MAK value: 20 mg/m³
ANSES, OEL Committee	NTP, 1997 (10-week inhalation oral in rats)	alteration of reproductive organs and impaired fertility in rat males	NOAEL of 200 mg/kg bw /d	<p>27</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 3 for interspecies differences - 3 for intraspecies differences - 3 for study duration 	8h-OEL: 13 mg/m³

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 173

6 Selected biomarker(s) for the HBM-GV proposal and analytical method

6.1 Choice of biomarkers of exposure

Only one study having assessed the BBzP metabolism in humans is available (see Chapter 5.1.2), showing that two metabolites MBzP and MnBP can be detected in human urine: MnBP, a common metabolite with DnBP has only been detected after a single oral dose of 0.506 mg d4-BBzP (equivalent to a dose of ~7 µg/kg assuming a volunteer of 75kg body weight), representing 6% of the BBzP dose excreted in urine, but not in the 0.253 mg d4-BBzP dose experiment of Anderson et al., 2001. Urinary MBzP has clearly been shown to be the major metabolite formed and excreted via urine accounting for approximately 67-78% (mean 73%) of the doses (0.253 mg and 0.506 mg) orally administered (Anderson et al. 2001). Thus, in contrast to MnBP which is also formed during the metabolism of DnBP, MBzP is specific to BBzP exposure. Therefore, urinary MBzP is the only biomarker of exposure selected for monitoring exposure to BBzP as was also proposed by partners of task 9.1 of HBM4EU and defined in Deliverable 9.2 "Prioritised list of biomarkers, matrices and analytical methods for the 1st round of substances".

Several Human Biomonitoring studies were conducted using MBzP as specific biomarker to assess the exposure to BBzP in the general population (Becker et al. 2009, Den Hond et al. 2015, Hartmann et al. 2015, Koch et al. 2017, Myridakis et al. 2015) and it has been shown that BBzP is eliminated within 24h in humans. The molar urinary excretion factor (F_{ue}) at 24h for MBzP after oral administration was determined to be 0.73 (Anderson et al. 2001). In consideration of all this, end-of-shift urine sampling can be performed in the occupational field (ANSES 2016).

6.2 Choice of analytical method

An established analytical method for the determination of MBzP in urine is the on-line high performance liquid chromatography coupled to tandem mass spectrometry (HPLC–MS/MS) using internal isotope-labelled standards as previously published (Blount et al. 2000, Frederiksen et al. 2011, Koch et al. 2003, Koch et al. 2017, Silva et al. 2008). The limit of detection for MBzP is 0.1 µg/L and the limit of quantification is 0.2 µg/L. Deliverable 9.2 "Prioritised list of biomarkers, matrices and analytical methods for the 1st round of substances" produced within HBM4EU is providing more details.

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 174

7 Choice of the HBM-GVs derivation method

7.1 Derivation of an HBM-GV for the general population

7.1.1 Method for the HBM-GV_{GenPop} derivation

The current epidemiological data on BBzP does not allow for the derivation of HBM-GVs for the general population (nor for workers), based on a relationship between human internal concentrations (parent compound or biomarker(s)) and health effects. There are a certain number of studies investigating the exposure to BBzP and to phthalates in general, in relation with specific health effects, especially the reproduction and developmental toxicity in both male and female adults. However, available epidemiological studies do not demonstrate a causal link between observed effects and specific exposure to BBzP. The general population is indeed exposed to a variety of environmental chemicals including several other phthalates, presumed to exhibit the same effects. In the Restriction Report for 4 phthalates from ECHA, it is stated that epidemiological studies are in general associated with reasonable uncertainties and thus clear conclusions cannot be drawn (ECHA & Danish EPA 2016). Nevertheless, they significantly contribute to and complement the understanding of internal exposure with exhibited effects observed in animal studies.

A derivation of an HBM-GV_{GenPop} from an existing health-based guidance value, i.e. TDI or DNEL would be a suitable starting point. EFSA and ECHA identified the same key studies and therefore the same POD as basis for their value derivation. EFSA derived a TDI of 0.5 mg/kg bw/d for BBzP in 2005 and in 2019 a group-TDI of 50 µg/kg bw/d for BBzP, DEHP, DiNP and DnBP taken together, expressed as DEHP equivalents incorporating an adjustment factor of 0.1 for BBzP. ECHA derived a DNEL of 0.5 mg/kg bw/d – all values are based on the NOAEL of 50 mg/kg bw/d derived from the two-generation diet study on reproductive toxicity in rats conducted by Tyl et al. (2004) and extrapolated by using an uncertainty factor of 100 (EFSA 2005, ECHA & Danish EPA 2016, EFSA 2019). The critical effect seen was reduced AGD in the F1- and F2- male generations at birth, at a dose of 250 mg/kg bw/d. An earlier study by Nagao et al., 2000 found significantly decreased AGD in male rats at doses of 500 mg/kg bw/d. In addition to these studies other, "newer" studies were taken into account, i.e. . of Aso et al. (2005) and of Ahmad et al. (2014). Aso et al. (2005) found a significant decrease of AGD in male offspring (F2) and a significant increase of AGD in female offspring (F1) at 100 mg/kg bw/d or higher doses (LOAEL of 100 mg/kg bw/d).

However, no effect on AGD in F2 females was observed, nor an effect on the AGD of male F1 offspring. The study by Ahmad et al., 2014 identified effects on the reproductive organs (reduced organ weights and changes in sperm count and motility) in adult male rats (F1) at 100 mg/kg bw/d with a NOAEL of 20 mg/kg bw/d based on these effects. However, this study has some gaps in the description of the study design and is not fully conducted according to OECD guidelines. It was stated by ECHA and the Danish EPA in their Annex XV Restriction Report, that there are some uncertainties left in regard to the DNEL derivation as some endocrine sensitive endpoints that were investigated for DEHP and DnBP were not assessed for BBzP which might result in an lower POD as also stated by RAC (RAC & SEAC 2017a). Since Howdeshell et al., 2008 revealed that the potency of testosterone reduction in foetuses of BBzP is similar to DEHP, DiBP and DnBP and this was confirmed by a study by Furr et al., 2014, it cannot be excluded that those effects could be observed at doses lower than 50 mg/kg bw/d. Indeed, when calculating HBM-GVs for the general population based on the TDI of 0.5 mg/kg/bw/d derived by EFSA, 2005, the obtained values are 15 mg/L for adults and 10 mg/L for children. Considering that BBzP has a similar potency to reduce testosterone production, these values are rather high when comparing to HBM-GVs_{GenPop} of DEHP

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 175

(sum of metabolites 5-oxo-MEHP and 5-OH-MEHP) or DnBP (for metabolite MnBP), for which the following HBM-GV_{GenPop} were derived: 500 µg/L for adults/ 340µg/L for children and 190 µg/L for adults/ 120µg/L for children, respectively. Therefore, it was abstained from using the TDI as TRV for deriving HBM-GVs for the general population, but rather decided to use other toxicologically relevant values derived from experimental studies with animals.

In light of the abovementioned uncertainties of the selected POD by EFSA and ECHA, the study by Furr et al., 2014 would be suitable as key study. A dose-dependent suppression of foetal testosterone was demonstrated from doses of 100 mg/kg bw/d BBzP on. Indeed, “reduction of the fetal testosterone production during a window of susceptibility in rats induced by DBP, BBP and DEHP“ was also defined by EFSA, 2019 “as a critical step in the reproductive toxicity of the phthalates” (EFSA, 2019).

Kortenkamp and Koch, 2019 also identified this endpoint as the critical endpoint for their mixture risk assessment of selected phthalates. In order to overcome inexactly defined effect sizes associated with NOAELs /LOAELs they used benchmark doses as much as possible. By using the dataset from Furr et al. (2014) a BMD5%L of 1 mg/kg/d (PROAST tool version 66.39) as POD for phthalate mixture risk assessment referring to male reproductive toxicity was calculated. By application of an overall assessment factor of 100 for animal-to-human extrapolation, they derived a RfD AA of 10 µg/kg bw/d.-The BMDL05 of 1 mg/kg bw/d as POD is in line with results of the Ahmad study (2014), where reduction of serum testosterone in adult rats is already seen at doses of 4 mg/kg, even though not significant (Ahmad et al. 2014). However, it can be discussed whether a 5% suppression of testicular testosterone can be seen as adverse and thereby used as POD for the derivation of an HBM-GV, given the considerable intra- and interspecies variability of the foetal testosterone production. Therefore, the BMDL₀₅ of 1 mg/kg bw/d is not selected as POD for deriving an HBM-GV_{GenPop}. However, it needs to be noted, that based on the current database available, it is not possible to give conclusions on the significance of smaller changes in testosterone levels in the foetus and the resulting possibility of adverse outcomes, thereby uncertainties remain. In light of future mixture assessments of the phthalate substance group, it might be considered to use the RfD_{AA} set by Kortenkamp and Koch, 2019 for the T suppression as POD as this is evaluated as common mode of action shared by many reprotoxic phthalates.

Instead, the LOAEL of 100 mg/kg bw/d determined in the Furr et al., 2014 study for reducing testosterone and additionally the LOAEL of 100 mg/kg bw/d BBzP observed in the Ahmad et al., 2014 study for effects on sperm motility, sperm counts and sperm morphology are combined and chosen as POD. Both studies have limitations as laid out above but by applying an assessment factor (AF) of 3 to account for LOAEL-NOAEL extrapolation a more conservative approach is used compared to the NOAEL of 50 mg/kg bw/d obtained in the Tyl et al., 2004 study. An extrapolation of the POD from rats to humans taking into account the same route of exposure (oral) is performed, by applying an interspecies AF of 10 and a further factor of 10 accounting for intra-species differences. All AFs are in line with ECHA’s R8 guidance for deriving DNELs for the general population (HBM4EU concept paper (Apel et al., 2020)). As mentioned before, there is substantial reasoning that BBzP will exhibit effects at doses lower than the POD chosen here due to its anti-androgenic potency. For this reason, a further AF of 3 accounting for uncertainties in the toxicological database is applied in order to be protective against other endpoints within the “phthalate syndrome” not assessed. Thus, an overall AF of 900 is applied to the POD of 100 mg/kg/d to obtain a TRV-like value of 0,111 mg/kg bw/d.

Factsheets summarising the key data used for deriving the BBzP HBM-GVs, as described here below, are provided in section 10 of this report (section 10.1 summarising the information used for

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 176

the HBM-GV derivation for the general population, and section 10.2 summarising the information used for the workers HBM-GV derivation).

7.1.2 Derivation of an HBM-GV_{GenPop}

HBM-GVs are derived for the metabolite MBzP according to the following mass balance equation:

$$\text{HBM - GV}(\text{GenPop}) = \frac{\text{TRV - like value} \cdot \left[\frac{\text{MW}(\text{Metabolite}) \cdot \text{F}_{\text{ue}}(\text{Metabolite})}{\text{MW}(\text{Substance})} \right]}{\text{Daily urine volume adjusted to the BW}}$$

TRV = Toxicity Reference Value; MW = Molecular Weight; F_{ue} = proportional urinary excretion factor; BW = Body Weight

A TRV-like value of 0,111 mg /kg bw /d is used for the calculation. By using the mass balance equation, it is assumed that a steady-state of the metabolite MBzP is reached in the body. Within 24h, 73% of the oral dose absorbed were excreted as MBzP in the urine, whereby the fractional urinary excretion factor(F_{ue}) is 0.73 (Anderson et al. 2001). As MBzP is rapidly excreted within 24h as shown in the Anderson et al., 2001 study a nearly complete excretion within 24h can be assumed. In addition, as the TRV-like value is given in relation to body weight, the daily urine is adjusted to body weight. As estimated by the HBM Commission (2014), the daily urine volume adjusted to the body weight is assumed to be 0.03 l/kg bw/d for children and 0.02 l/kg bw/d for adults. However, data on daily urine volume adjusted to the body weight are currently reassessed and dependent on the outcome, might need to be adapted later on.

HBM-GV_{GenPop} calculation for MBzP

a) Bodyweight-related urine excretion rate adjustment (0.02 l/kg bw/d for adults):

$$\text{HBM - GV}(\text{GenPop, adults}) = \frac{0.111 \text{ mg/kg bw/d} \cdot \left[\frac{256.257 \text{ g/mol}(\text{MBzP}) \cdot (0.73)}{312.4 \text{ g/mol}(\text{BBzP})} \right]}{0.02 \text{ L/kg bw/d}}$$

The HBM-GV_{GenPop} referring to the metabolite MBzP in urine for adults is: ~ 3,326 mg/L = 3 mg/L.

b) Bodyweight-related urine excretion rate adjustment (0.03 l/kg bw/d for children):

$$\text{HBM - GV}(\text{GenPop, children}) = \frac{0,111 \text{ mg/kg bw/d} \cdot \left[\frac{256.257 \text{ g/mol}(\text{MBzP}) \cdot (0.73)}{312.4 \text{ g/mol}(\text{BBzP})} \right]}{0.03 \text{ L/kg bw/d}}$$

The HBM-GV_{GenPop} referring to the metabolite MBzP in urine for children is: ~ 2,217 mg/L = 2 mg/L.

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 177

7.2 Derivation of an HBM-GV for the occupational population

7.2.1 Method for the HBM-GV_{worker} derivation

No epidemiological studies in the workplace linking urinary concentrations of MBzP and the occurrence of health effects are available. And as mentioned above, the epidemiological studies in the general population do not allow to derive an HBM-GV for BBzP.

The calculation of the urinary MBzP concentration at any recommended 8h-OEL value is also not possible, because no workplace studies reporting both urinary concentrations of MBzP and atmospheric concentration of BBzP are available; consequently no equation of a regression line is available (ANSES 2016).

Therefore, the last option for deriving an HBM-GV_{worker} is to select a POD related to the selected critical effect (i.e. reprotoxicity) from an animal key study and further extrapolate this POD into a human urinary MBzP level.

Albeit EU legislation ensures that the work environment is safe for pregnant workers and allows to changing working conditions or offering suitable alternative work if necessary, women are not always aware of their pregnancy or because of other reasons are not willing to discuss this at an early stage with their employers. Thus, in order to protect the health of the unborn child, the most sensitive effects as developmental and reproductive toxicity should be taken as critical endpoints for the HBM-GV derivation.

Choice of a POD from a key study

According to the BBzP toxicological profile, the most sensitive effects are observed in the male reproductive system and are related to the anti-androgenic activity of BBzP. Several studies indicate that in utero exposure corresponds to the most susceptible period for these effects. However, the available data, particularly the lowest NOAEL (50 mg/kg/d) identified in the multi-generational study by Tyl et al. (2000), cannot be used to establish a toxicity reference value for the occupational field. Indeed, the end of pregnancy and perinatal exposure conditions are not considered relevant for an occupational exposure scenario, as pregnant women (as soon as they become aware of their pregnancy, most often by the end of the 1st trimester) and breast-feeding mothers should not be exposed to BBzP at the workplace.

Workers are likely to be exposed to BBzP mainly by inhalation. Nevertheless, the most relevant study (a 13-weeks study conducted in rat) among the three inhalation toxicity studies available, reported effects (increase in relative liver and kidney weights with no other histopathological changes at 789 mg.m⁻³) that do not concern the sphere of the reproduction (ANSES 2016).

Among the experimental studies in animals on the reprotoxic effects of BBzP with exposure protocols which can be extrapolated to occupational exposure scenarios, two studies could be identified. The screening study by Furr et al., 2014 exposed Harlan SD rats with 0, 11, 33, 100, 300, 600 or 900 mg/kg bw/d BBzP from GD 14- GD 18. Rats were necropsied on GD 18 to measure ex vivo testis testosterone levels and BBzP was found to significantly reduce the foetal testicular testosterone production in a dose-dependent manner (from 100 mg/kg bw /d on). In addition, Ahmad et al., 2014 dosed parental albino rats from GD 14 to parturition with 0, 4, 20, 100 mg/kg bw/d BBzP per gavage and observed in F1 adult male rats at doses of 100 mg/kg BBzP impaired sperm quality parameters (reduced sperm count, reduced sperm motility and increased sperm abnormalities) and a significant decline in serum testosterone level. Indeed, these studies were conducted in a population of adult rats within which a critical effect transposable to the unborn children of potential pregnant workers were identified (impairment of reproductive organs and

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 178

fertility). First, an assessment factor (AF) of 3 to account for LOAEL-NOAEL extrapolation is applied to the LOAEL of 100 mg/kg/d. Then an extrapolation of the adjusted LOAEL from rats to humans taking into account the same route of exposure (oral) is performed, by applying an interspecies AF of 10. Regarding the exposure route-to-route extrapolation between oral and inhalation, it is assumed that the bioavailability for both exposure routes is 100%³⁶ and that the retrieved urinary total MBzP concentrations would be the same between both routes. In absence of data concerning the dermal exposure route, we would also consider a 100% bioavailability via this route for a conservative approach.

An AF_H of 10 accounting for intraspecies differences is further applied to the human adjusted NOAEL. Generally, the AF_H is set to 5 when workers are the targeted population for which the HBM-GV is derived, in line with ECHA's R8 guidance for deriving DNELs for worker (ECHA 2012). However, in case of BBzP the most sensitive endpoint(s) to be protected from are the effects on the unborn child. Thus, no differences can be assumed between the foetuses of the general population and the workers.

Finally, a further AF of 3 accounting for uncertainties in the toxicological database is applied in order to be protective against other endpoints within the "phthalate syndrome" not assessed.

An overall AF of 900 is applied to the POD of 100 mg/kg/day to obtain a "TRV-like value" of 0.111 mg/kg bw/d.

7.2.2 Derivation of an HBM-GV_{worker}

Calculation of the HBM-GV_{Worker} for MBzP

Within 24h, 73% of the oral dose absorbed is excreted as MBzP in the urine according to Anderson et al., 2001, whereby the fractional urinary excretion factor (F_{ue}) is 0.73 (Anderson et al. 2001).

The body weight-related urine excretion of 0,02 L/kg bw/day for adults is used for the HBM-GV_{worker} calculation.

$$\text{HBM - GV(Worker)} = \frac{0,111 \text{ mg/kg bw/d} \cdot \left[\frac{256.257 \text{ g/mol(MBzP)} \cdot (0.73)}{312.4 \text{ g/mol(BBzP)}} \right]}{0.02 \text{ L/kg bw/d}}$$

The HBM-GV_{Worker} referring to the metabolite MBzP in human urine is: = 3.32 mg/L ~ 3 mg/L.

In the occupational field, moments of sampling are part of the biological monitoring strategy and are set with considerations to the biomarker of exposure toxicokinetic properties. The sampling of the selected biomarker of exposure (urinary MBzP) should be performed at the end of the work shift, based on the information available on its elimination kinetic (the urinary half-live of MBzP is assumed to be short, less than 24h).

³⁶ In rodents, gastro-intestinal absorption of BBzP is close to 100% (INSERM, 2011). Since no data are available, it is considered by default that absorption by inhalation in rodents is 100%.

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 179

8 Level of confidence attributed to the derived HBM-GVs

As mentioned in the HBM4EU concept document to derive HBM-GVs, it is suggested to attribute a level of confidence (low, medium or high) to each calculated HBM-GV. The level of confidence should reflect the uncertainties identified during the elaboration of the value and could constitute a good incentive to revise later on values with estimated 'lower' level of confidence.

However, it should be specified that the levels of confidence proposed in this document are not determined according to an established recognised methodology, but rather rely on expert judgment regarding the reliability of the data and the calculation method used to derive the HBM guidance values.

The levels of confidence attributed to the HBM-GV for the general population are set to 'medium'. Please, refer to the n°2 note of the factsheet presented in section 10.1 for explanation on this level of confidence appreciation.

The level of confidence attributed to the HBM-GV for the working population is set to 'medium'. Please, refer to the n°2 note of the factsheet presented in section 10.2 for explanation on this level of confidence appreciation. Considering the high uncertainties underlying the HBM-GV_{worker} derivation, it is not recommended to use it for the effective control of the health risks related to BBzP in the practice of occupational health. The EU reference value for workers that will be established for BBzP under T10.4 of HBM4EU should be rather used to assess whether the exposure at the workplace is adequately controlled or not³⁷.

³⁷ If a biomonitoring results is greater than an EU reference value for workers, it does not necessarily mean that will occur, but it does indicate that control of exposure may not be adequate. Under these circumstances, employers will need to look at current work practices to see how they can be improved to reduce exposure.

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 180

9 Discussion

For evaluating internal exposure to BBzP of the general population as well as of workers it is recommended to determine the metabolite MBzP in urine and to compare the analytical results with the HBM-GVs derived here above: 2 mg/l for children, 3 mg/l for adults of the general population and for workers. In the occupational setting, the measurement of the biomarker of exposure (MBzP) should be performed at the end of the work shift. In addition, a measurement could be recommended prior to the work shift in order to assess non-occupational BBzP exposure and therefore, better estimate the exposure resulting from occupational activities. However, as the derivation of the values is based on endpoints identified in toxicity studies conducted in animals, uncertainties remain:

The PODs chosen for the derivation of values for the general population as well as for workers are based on effects seen in animal studies as no epidemiological studies demonstrating a causal link between BBzP exposure and health effects are available. Therefore, an extrapolation to the human equivalent dose using default assessment factors accounting for differences in toxicokinetics and toxicodynamics needed to be performed which comprises uncertainties due to assumptions being made. Additionally, it needs to be noted that there is substantial reasoning that BBzP will exhibit effects at doses lower than the POD chosen here (LOAEL of 100 mg/kg bw/d) due to its equivalent anti-androgenic potency of other phthalates such as DEHP or DnBP. For this reason, a further AF accounting for uncertainties in the toxicological database was applied in order to be protective against other endpoints within the “phthalate syndrome” not assessed in the animal toxicity studies available. However, when comparing the HBM-GV for BBzP with those of DEHP and DnBP, still the HBM-GV derived here is more than one order of magnitude higher. Considering similar potencies for anti-androgenic effects, this value has to be used with caution. Further toxicity studies for BBzP are needed in order to evaluate, whether critical effects not assessed so far (i.e. testicular and mammary histology; dysgenesis of external genitalia) are occurring at low-level exposure to BBzP.

The data for the conversion of the external human equivalent dose to the internal metabolite doses (F_{ue}) come solely from one study of controlled exposure with only two doses administered to 24 adult volunteers with no specification on the gender. However, the range of variability occurring in the general population is not known and the possible variability due to age, sex, level of exposure and other influencing factors has not been examined until now. Thus, potential under- or overestimations by taking a default F_{ue} cannot be excluded. Moreover, it needs to be noted, that in studies with rats it became evident that excretion of BBzP changes in a dose-dependent manner. At high exposures (1500 and 2000 mg/kg bw/ d; oral administration) the total recovery of the administered dose in urine decreased and higher amounts could be found in the faeces. The authors stated that this could be possibly due to a lower absorption of BBzP at higher doses. This can lead to an underestimation of the internal dose, when only urinary metabolites are measured given high exposures shortly before urine sampling.

These uncertainties need to be considered if interpreting biomonitoring results in terms of individual risks for developmental and reprotoxic effects. The derived HBM-GVs are most appropriate as a screening tool to evaluate population-based biomonitoring data in the context of possibly necessary risk management on a regulatory level. On that account, it should be noted that HBM-GVs are expected to be protective over a life time of exposure and that Human Biomonitoring results, particularly those of substances with a short half-life can only be a measurement at one specific point in time and thereby over- and underestimation of the risk can occur when comparing one single measurement to the HBM-GVs. Therefore, if exceedance is observed it is

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 181

recommended to repeat the biomonitoring measurement and to search for potential sources that can help to minimise the risk to exposure. Although Christensen et al. (2012) study shows that spot and 24h samples produce rather comparable results for phthalates on a population level, it should be considered that due to the short half-life of excretion of the monoester metabolites, more reliable evaluations of the extent of exposure could be made based on 24-h urine collections rather than spot samples. Moreover, a current publication by Casas et al. (2018) quantifying the variability of biomarker measurements of many non-persistent chemicals during several time windows shows that for many of these compounds a few dozen samples are required to accurately assess exposure over periods encompassing several trimesters or months.

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 182

10 Factsheet

10.1 Factsheet for the general population

FACTSHEET for Benzyl butyl phthalate (BBzP)			
Parameter	Note	Value / descriptor	Comments
HBM-GV_{GenPop} and Status			
Target population: general population			
HBM-GV _{GenPop}	1	Adults: 3 mg/L Children: 2 mg/L	
Level of confidence	2	Medium	
HBM-GV _{GenPop} status	3	Provisional	
HBM-GV _{GenPop} year of issue	4	2019	
General Information			
CLP-INDEX-Nr.	5	607-430-00-3	
EC-Nr.	6	201-622-7	
CAS-No.	7	85-68-7	
Harmonised CLP classification	8	H400, H401, Repr. 1B	
Molar mass	9	312.4 g/mol	
Biomarker(s)			
Identification	10	Urinary MBzP	
Molar mass of biomarker(s)	11	MBzP: 256.257 g/mol	
Toxicokinetic data			
Key study for TK data, authors, year	12	Anderson et al., 2001	
Type of study	13	Human study	
Route of exposure	14	Oral single dose: low: 253 µg high: 506 µg	
Half-life of biomarker(s) (second phase)	15	No half-life reported (< 24h) in humans; in rats approximately 6 h	
Factor for metabolic conversion (F _{ue})	16	For MBzP: 0.73 (at 24 h)	
Derivation method and calculation			
Derivation method	17	Based on an animal POD	
Key study: Author(s), Year	18	Furr et al., 2014/ Ahmad et al., 2014	
Species	18	Rat	

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 183

Route/type of study	18	By gavage, screening study/ Oral, 1-generation study	
Exposure duration	18	from GD 14-18/ from GD 14 to parturition	As the exposure was during critical window for inducing "phthalate syndrome" no AF for study duration is needed
Critical endpoint	18	Suppression of foetal testicular testosterone production/ reduction of serum testosterone and reduced sperm count and motility in adult male rats	
POD	19	LOAEL of 100 mg/kg bw/d	
TRV-like value	20	111 µg/ kg bw/ d	
			Global AF of 900 (AF for interspecies differences of 10; AF for intraspecies differences of 10; AF of 3 for extrapolation from NOAEL-LOAEL; AF of 3 for whole quality of the database)
Calculated HBM-GV_{GenPop}			
	21	Adults: 3 mg/L Children: 2 mg/L	
Additional Comments			

Explanation of notes:

1) HBM-GV_{GenPop}: numerical value of the HBM-GV_{GenPop} value in mg/l

2) Level of confidence of the HBM-GV_{GenPop}: reflects the reliability of the proposed HBM-GV. The level of confidence takes into account the various uncertainties underlying the derivation of the HBM-GV (e.g. reliability of the key study used, uncertainties related toxicokinetic data on the substance of interest, to the extrapolations and calculation of the final HBM-HBGV). An attribution of a global level of confidence is suggested for the proposed BBzP HBM-GV_{GenPop}, considering the assessment of the various uncertainties:

- regarding the nature and quality of the BBzP toxicological and epidemiological data: the database on BBzP is extended for animal toxicity studies, studies in humans are available. The determination of the factor for metabolic conversion (F_{ue}) is based on only one study with 24 volunteers, however it was not apparent whether this included both male and female volunteers. Therefore, the Loc for the overall database is set to → **medium**
- regarding the critical effect: the confidence in the evidence of reproductive/developmental effect and mode of action (suppression of foetal testicular testosterone production and reduction of serum testosterone in adult male rats) is medium as there is no clear consensus about the quantity of testosterone reduction that will lead to subsequent adverse effects. In addition, Ahmad et al., 2014 observed changes in sperm parameters (reduced cauda epididymal sperm count and sperm motility and increase in sperm head morphological abnormalities) at the same dose (LOAEL of 100 mg/kg bw/d). Overall, the effects seen in these studies are well in line with the effects of the phthalate syndrome. Evidence for these effects in humans is available from the scientific literature. → **high**
- regarding the selected key studies: Furr et al., 2014 is a short-term in vivo screening study and therefore does not correspond to a chronic nor life-time exposure. However, exposure of parent animals to BBzP took place in the critical window of sexual differentiation (GD12-14). The study of Ahmad et al., 2014 were conducted comparable to OECD guidelines, but with minor methodological shortcomings (age of adult rats when mated were only 10 weeks). Therefore, the LoC for the underlying key studies can be set to → **medium**
- regarding the selected POD: POD chosen is a combined LOAEL of 100 mg/kg bw/d from two animal toxicity studies (Furr et al., 2014 and Ahmad et al., 2014). Other endocrine sensitive endpoints not assessed that were seen in lower doses for DEHP and DnBP (testicular and mammary histology; dysgenesis of external genitalia). An BMDL would have been preferred. → **low**

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 184

- regarding the extrapolations from the POD value to the TRV-like value: the LOAEL determined from the above mentioned studies is being extrapolated to NOAEL (AF of 3); across species ($AF_A = 10$) and according to intra individual variability ($AF_H = 10$), but using a validated PBPK model or TK model for extrapolating from animal to human could have increased the level of confidence → **low**

The global level of confidence for BBzP HBM-GV for the general population is set to “**medium**”.

3) HBM-GV_{GenPop} status: the status value is set to ‘provisional’, thereby reflecting that this value could be revised later on in the project, if uncertainties underlying the data could be reduced. For example, the uncertainties of the TK data could be reduced by means of a validated PBPK model for BBzP. A higher level of confidence attributed to the value would lead to a ‘confirmed’ value status.

4) HBM-GV_{GenPop} year of issue: year of setting the HBM-GV_{GenPop} in the HBM4EU work frame.

5) CLP Number: according to Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 on classification, labelling and packaging (CLP) of substances and mixtures, implementing the globally harmonised system of chemical classification or GHS
http://guidance.echa.europa.eu/docs/guidance_document/clp_introduutory_en.pdf

6) EC Number: under European Inventory of Existing Commercial chemical Substances (EINECS), ELINCS (European List of Notified Chemical Substances) in support of Directive 92/32/EEC, the 7th amendment to Directive 67/548/EEC, NLP (No-Longer Polymers), see: ESIS: European chemical Substances Information System:
https://web.archive.org/web/20131106181548if_/http://esis.jrc.ec.europa.eu/

7) CAS Number: collection of disclosed chemical compound information by Chemical Abstracts Service. Almost all molecule databases can be searched by CAS Registry Number.

8) Harmonised CLP classification: CLP classification including CMR and other health relevant effects. In the case that classification is not harmonised, this should be stated. For self-classifications by industry the ECHA- CLP inventory can be searched at: <http://echa.europa.eu/web/guest/information-on-chemicals/cl-inventory-database>

9) Molar mass: mass of BBzP per amount of this substance expressed in g/mol

10) Biomarker identification: the biomarker identified as valid for a diagnosis of exposure to BBzP is the monoester MBzP (Anderson et al., 2001), and has been taken into consideration for the HBM-GV derivation.

11) Molar mass of the biomarker(s): mass of MBzP per amount of this substance expressed in g/mol

12) Study for TK data, Authors, Year: Anderson et al., 2001

13) Type of study: human oral study

14) Route of exposure: oral single administration

15) Half-life of biomarker: no half-life for BBzP were estimated in humans, in rats it was estimated to be approximately 6h

16) Factor for metabolic conversion (F_{ue}): fractional urinary excretion ratio of biomarker relative to the oral dose of BBzP taken up.

17) Derivation method: the existing data base on BBzP does not allow for the derivation of HBM-GVs from human data, based on a relationship between internal concentration of the selected biomarker and health effects. Therefore, the derivation method starts from an animal POD.

18) Key study: Furr et al., 2014 repeatedly dosed Harlan SD rats with 0, 11, 33, 100, 300, 600 or 900 mg/kg bw/d BBzP and necropsied on GD 18 to measure ex vivo testis testosterone levels. BBzP was found to significantly reduce the foetal testicular testosterone production in a dose-dependent manner (from 100 mg/kg bw /d on). Ahmad et al., 2014 dosed parental albino rats from GD 14 to parturition with 0, 4, 20, 100 mg/kg bw/d BBzP per gavage. Reduction of serum testosterone was observed at 4 mg/kg bw/d and significantly at 100 mg/kg bw/d. In addition, significantly reduced sperm count and sperm mortality was observed at 100 mg/kg bw/d and a significant increase of sperm abnormalities in the same dose.

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 185

19) LOAEL of 100 mg/kg bw/d observed in the study of Furr et al., 2014 and in the Ahmad et al, 2014 studies based on ~ 50% foetal testicular testosterone suppression and ~ 50% reduction in serum testosterone in adult male rats in addition to reduction of sperm motility and sperm counts, respectively.

20) HBM-GV_{GenPop}: the resulting HBM-GV for urinary MBzP calculated on the basis of a mass balance equation and a body weight-related excretion for adult (20 ml/kg bw/d) and children (30 ml/kg bw/d) is 3 and 2 mg/L.

21) Rounded values of the HBM-GV_{GenPop} in mg/L for both adults including adolescents and children.

Please note: Ideally, the HBM-GVs should refer to a complete 24-hour urine sample, stating the quantity of a substance in µg/d, especially if the monitored substance has a short half-life of excretion. For reasons of simplification, in accordance with the approach described in the concept document, the excretion is referred to a body weight-related urine excretion of 20 ml/kg bw per day for adults and 30ml/kg bw per day for children.

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 186

10.2 Factsheet for workers

FACTSHEET for benzyl butyl phthalate (BBzP)			
Parameter	Note	Value / descriptor	Comments
HBM GV_{Worker} and Status			
Target population: workers			
HBM GV _{Worker}	1	Urinary total MBzP: 3 mg/L, at the end of the work shift	Based on effects affecting the male reproduction system and the fertility
Level of confidence	2	Medium	See note for explanation
HBM HBGV _{Worker} status	3	Provisional	See note for explanation
HBM HBGV _{Worker} year of issue	4	2019	
General information			
CLP-INDEX-Nr.	5	607-430-00-3	
EC-Nr.	6	201-622-7	
CAS-Nr.	7	85-68-7	
Harmonised CLP classification	8	Repr.1B - H360Df (may damage the unborn child and is suspected of damaging fertility) Aquatic Acute Cat.1 - H400, Aquatic Chronic 1 - H401,	
Molar mass	9	312.4 g/mol	
Biomarker(s)			
Identification	10	Urinary MBzP	
Molar mass of biomarker(s)	11	MBzP: 256.257 g/mol	
Toxicokinetic data			
Study for TK data, authors, year	12	Anderson et al., 2001	
Type of study	13	Human study	
Route of exposure	14	Oral single dose: 0, 253 µg (low) or 506 µg (high)	8 volunteers/dose group
Half-life of selected biomarker(s)	15	No half-life reported (<24h)	
Factor for metabolic conversion (F _{ue})	16	For MBzP: 0.73 (at 24 h)	
Derivation method and calculation			
Derivation method	17	Based on animal POD	
Key study, Author(s), Year	18	Furr et al., 2014/ Ahmad et al., 2014	
Species	18	Rat	
Route/type of study	18	By gavage, screening study/ Oral, 1-generation study	

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 187

Exposure duration	18	from GD 14-18/ from GD 14 to parturition	As the exposure was during critical window for inducing "phthalate syndrome" no AF for study duration is needed
Critical endpoint	18	Suppression of foetal testicular testosterone production/ reduction of serum testosterone and reduced sperm count and motility in adult male rats	
POD value	19	LOAEL of 100 mg/kg bw/d	
TRV-like value	19	111 µg/ kg bw/ d	Global AF of 900 (AF for interspecies differences of 10; AF for intraspecies differences of 10; AF of 3 for extrapolation from NOAEL-LOAEL; AF of 3 for whole quality of the database)
Calculation of HBM-GV _{worker}			
HBM-GV _{Worker}	20	HBM - GV(Workers) $= \frac{0.111 \text{ mg/kg bw/d} \cdot \left[\frac{256.257 \text{ g/mol(MBzP)} \cdot (0.73)}{312.4 \text{ g/mol(BBzP)}} \right]}{0.02 \text{ l/kg bw/d}}$ $= 3 \text{ mg/L}$	Related to urinary volume (0.02 l/kg bw /day)
Additional Comments:			
urine sampling should be performed at the end of the work shift			

Explanation of notes:

1) HBM-GV_{Worker}: numerical value of the HBM-GV_{Worker} value in mg/l

2) Level of confidence of the HBM-GV_{Worker}: reflects the reliability of the proposed HBM-GV. The level of confidence considers the various uncertainties underlying the derivation of the HBM-GV (e.g. reliability of the key study used, uncertainties related toxicokinetic data on the substance of interest, to the extrapolations and calculation of the final HBM-HBGV). Attribution of a global level of confidence for the proposed BBzP HBM-GV_{Worker} is suggested, considering the level of confidence in:

- regarding the nature and quality of the BBzP toxicological and epidemiological data: the database on BBzP is extended for animal toxicity studies, studies in humans are available. The determination of the factor for metabolic conversion (F_{ue}) is based on only one study with 24 volunteers, however it was not apparent whether this included both male and female volunteers. Therefore, the Loc for the overall database is set to → **medium**
- regarding the critical effect: the confidence in the evidence of reproductive/developmental effect and mode of action (suppression of foetal testicular testosterone production and reduction of serum testosterone in adult male rats) is medium as there is no clear consensus about the quantity of testosterone reduction that will lead to subsequent adverse effects. In addition, Ahmad et al., 2014 observed changes in sperm parameters (reduced cauda epididymal sperm count and sperm motility and increase in sperm head morphological abnormalities) at the same dose (LOAEL of 100 mg/kg bw/d). Overall, the effects seen in these studies are well in line with the effects of the phthalate syndrome. Evidence for these effects in humans is available from the scientific literature. → **high**
- regarding the selected key studies: Furr et al., 2014 is a short-term in vivo screening study and therefore does not correspond to a chronic nor life-time exposure. However, oral exposure of parent animals to BBzP took place in the critical window of sexual differentiation (GD12-14). The oral toxicity study of Ahmad et al., 2014 were conducted comparable to OECD guidelines, but with minor methodological shortcomings (age of adult rats when mated were only 10 weeks). Also, inhalatory exposure would have been preferred as it reflects the most common exposure route in the occupational conditions. Therefore, the LoC for the underlying key studies can be set to → **medium**

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 188

- regarding the selected POD: POD chosen is a combined LOAEL of 100 mg/kg bw/d from two animal toxicity studies (Furr et al., 2014 and Ahmad et al., 2014). Other endocrine sensitive endpoints not assessed that were seen in lower doses for DEHP and DnBP (testicular and mammary histology; dysgenesis of external genitalia). An BMDL would have been preferred → **low**
- regarding the extrapolations from the POD value to the TRV-like value: the LOAEL determined from the above-mentioned studies is being extrapolated to NOAEL (AF of 3); across species (AF_A = 10) and according to intra individual variability (AF_H = 10), but using a validated PBPK model or TK model for extrapolating from animal to human could have increased the level of confidence → **low**

The global level of confidence for BBzP HBM-GV for the general population is set to “**medium**”.

3) HBM-GV_{worker} status: the status value is set to ‘provisional’, thereby reflecting that this value could be revised later on in the project, if uncertainties underlying the data could be reduced. For example, the uncertainties of the TK data could be reduced by means of a validated PBPK model for BBzP. A higher level of confidence attributed to the value would lead to a ‘confirmed’ value status.

4) HBM-GV_{worker} year of issue: year of setting the HBM-GV_{worker} in the HBM4EU work frame.

5) CLP Number: according to Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 on classification, labelling and packaging (CLP) of substances and mixtures, implementing the globally harmonised system of chemical classification or GHS
http://guidance.echa.europa.eu/docs/guidance_document/clp_introduutory_en.pdf

6) EC Number: under European Inventory of Existing Commercial chemical Substances (EINECS), ELINCS (European List of Notified Chemical Substances) in support of Directive 92/32/EEC, the 7th amendment to Directive 67/548/EEC, NLP (No-Longer Polymers), see: ESIS: European chemical Substances Information System:
https://web.archive.org/web/20131106181548if_/http://esis.jrc.ec.europa.eu/

7) CAS Number: collection of disclosed chemical compound information by Chemical Abstracts Service. Almost all molecule databases can be searched by CAS Registry Number.

8) Harmonised CLP classification: CLP classification including CMR and other health relevant effects. In the case that classification is not harmonised, this should be stated. For self-classifications by industry the ECHA- CLP inventory can be searched at: <http://echa.europa.eu/web/guest/information-on-chemicals/cl-inventory-database>

9) Molar mass: mass of BBzP per amount of this substance expressed in g/mol

10) Biomarker identification: the biomarker identified as valid for the BBzP exposure assessment is the monoester MBzP (Anderson et al., 2001), and has been taken into consideration for the HBM-GV derivation.

11) Molar mass of the biomarker(s): mass of MBzP per amount of this substance expressed in g/mol

12) Study for TK data, Authors, Year: Anderson et al., 2001. Anderson et al. (2001) examined the metabolism of BBzP in humans. The metabolites and the elimination kinetics were determined by means of chromatographic mass spectrometric methods (LC-MS) following hydrolysis of conjugates. **d**₄-BBzP was administered on toast at breakfast to 24 volunteers (8 controls, 8 receiving a low dose (253 µg) and 8 receiving a high dose (506 µg)). 24-h urine samples were collected one day before the administration, the next day, and subsequently 2 and 6 days after. MBzP is rapidly eliminated from the body within 24 hours.

13) Type of TK study: human oral study

14) Route of exposure: oral single administration

15) Half-life of biomarker: no half-life for MBzP was estimated in human, however it is completely excreted within 24h after administration of an oral single dose of BBzP.

16) Factor for metabolic conversion (F_{ue}): fractional urinary excretion ratio of biomarker relative to the oral dose of BBzP taken up. For BBzP, 67% and 78% on a molar basis, of a low and a high dose respectively was excreted as MBzP. MBzP, is rapidly eliminated from the body within 24 hours.

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 189

17) Derivation method: the existing database on BBzP does not allow for the derivation of HBM-GVs from human data, based on a relationship between internal concentration of the selected biomarker and health effects. In addition, no field studies are available correlating atmospheric concentrations of BBzP with urinary concentration of MBzP. Therefore, the derivation method starts from an animal POD.

18) Key study: Furr et al., 2014 repeatedly dosed Harlan SD rats with 0, 11, 33, 100, 300, 600 or 900 mg/kg bw/d BBzP and necropsied on GD 18 to measure ex vivo testis testosterone levels. BBzP was found to significantly reduce the foetal testicular testosterone production in a dose-dependent manner (from 100 mg/kg bw /d on). Ahmad et al., 2014 dosed parental albino rats from GD 14 to parturition with 0, 4, 20, 100 mg/kg bw/d BBzP per gavage.

19) LOAEL of 100 mg/kg bw/d observed in the study of Furr et al., 2014 and in the Ahmad et al, 2014 studies based on ~ 50% foetal testicular testosterone suppression and ~ 50% reduction in serum testosterone in adult male rats in addition to reduction of sperm motility and sperm counts, respectively. TRV-like value: an AF of 10 for interspecies differences, an AF of 10 for the intra-individual differences among the working population, an AF of 3 for extrapolation from NOAEL-LOAEL and an AF of 3 for whole quality of the database resulting in a TRV-like value of 0.111 mg/kg bw/d. The total assessment factor is 900.

20) HBM-GV_{worker}: the resulting HBM-GV for urinary MBzP calculated on the basis of a mass balance equation and a body weight-related excretion for adults (20 ml/kg bw/d) is 3 mg/L. Samples can be taken at end of shift and also prior to the work shift in order to assess non-occupational BBzP exposure and therefore, better estimate the exposure resulting from occupational activities.

D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 190

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D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 191

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D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 192

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D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 193

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D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 194

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D5.6 - Derivation of Human Biomonitoring Guidance Values (HBM-GV) for selected phthalates	Security: Public
WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 195

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WP5 - Translation of results into policy	Version: 1.0
Authors: Petra Apel, Eva Ougier, Rosa Lange, Christophe Rouselle	Page: 196

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